

**Symposium: Ethics in Education in Times of
Transformation**

Ethics in Education in Times of Transformation: An Introduction

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Questions like "*What is good action?*" and "*How should one act?*" lie at the heart of ethics and emerge repeatedly in educational settings. Ethical judgments and decisions in education often carry far-reaching societal consequences, given the reciprocal relationship between formal education and society. These judgments and decisions are inevitably shaped by principles that may at times conflict with one another. It is, therefore, essential to approach education-related ethical considerations with thorough reflection, drawing on both ethical and educational theories. In this endeavor, the field of ethics in education provides valuable guidance, fostering critical reflection on possible courses of action. Against this backdrop, formal education goes beyond the mere transmission of information that may eventually transform into knowledge. It also emphasizes the reflective engagement with norms and values, situating education as a cornerstone of hope for a better future. Education is frequently envisioned as a pathway to a "good" life, personal autonomy, and a responsible coexistence. It inherently reflects humanistic ideals and value systems.

This special symposium explores the intricate connections between ethics and education, aiming to shed light on the normative frameworks and principles that underpin educational practices. By examining the ethical dimensions of pressing contemporary issues, it seeks to contribute to a deeper understanding of how education can and should navigate and address the challenges of our time.

To start with, Jean-Luc Patry discusses the Is-Ought problem, emphasizing a strict separation between facts ("is") and values ("ought") but arguing for their connection. The author proposes Trans-Domain Approaches (TDA) to combine theoretical discussion (talk) and practical action (walk), exemplified by the VaKE (Values *and* Knowledge Education) approach that integrates values and knowledge education (paper: "Walking the Talk: *Is-Ought* as Transdisciplinarity and as a Trans-Domain Approach for Researchers, Teachers, and Students").

Christian Kraler demonstrates that addressing educational aims is inherently an ethical endeavor. He revisits Alfred North Whitehead's philosophy of education, which critiques traditional reliance on inert ideas and promotes a dynamic, process-oriented approach. Central to this is the emphasis on creativity, contextual understanding, and relational learning, encapsulated in his three-stage framework—Romance, Precision, and Generalization—which mirrors the natural progression of intellectual development (paper: "*The Aims of Education—Alfred North Whitehead's Ideas on Education and Learning Revisited After 100 Years*").

Sabrina Bacher examines the ethical responsibilities of schools within the educational system by providing a systematization of educational ethics with a focus on schools. She argues that

schools are not only centers of learning but also ethical communities that shape the future through value-driven decisions. Drawing on philosophical ethics and educational science, the author advocates for an interdisciplinary approach to foster a culture of reflection, adaptability, and ethical responsibility in response to societal changes (paper: “Schools as Ethical Decision-Makers—Educational Ethics at the Meso-Level”).

Luigina Mortari and Federica Valbusa introduce a project designed to promote ethical education in kindergartens and primary schools. Rooted in the philosophy of care and ancient virtue ethics, the *MelArete* Project regards ethical education as the cultivation of virtues through the lens of care. Its second edition places particular emphasis on friendship, conceptualizing it as a political virtue essential for building caring communities (paper: “‘The MelArete Project’: Education on Friendship as a Political Virtue for Caring Communities”).

Gabriele Schauer and Evelyn Christof explore whether pedagogical ethos can be taught and learned. They present a concept already integrated into teacher education, designed to help prospective teachers engage with their own pedagogical ethos. In a specially developed didactic setting, student teachers face challenging pedagogical scenarios, and through repeated practice, they are exposed to an approach that is intended to instill a lasting sense of pedagogical ethos (paper: “Is Pedagogical Ethos Teachable and Learnable? The Development of a Didactic-Methodical Approach for the Practice of Ethos in Teacher Education”).

Ammar Singh argues that dialogue and dialectic are interdependent, dynamic processes essential for intellectual development in higher education. They work together to build and continually refine shared understanding. In contrast, while Artificial Intelligence can support communication, it lacks the organic, relational qualities inherent in human dialogue and dialectic. The paper calls for integrating AI in an ethical way that enhances, rather than replaces, these fundamentally human processes (paper: “Exploring the Symbiotic Relationship between Dialectics and Dialogical Approach to Education in the Era of Artificial Intelligence: A Philosophical Perspective”).

Finally, Erica Hagström investigates the relationships between the human and the more-than-human, revealing two key educational implications. First, these interactions offer the possibility of engaging with forces beyond the human realm. Second, they highlight our responsibility to care for future generations. The author substantiates her claims through arts-based research, employing creative writing techniques—including a poem and two works of fiction—to vividly illustrate these connections (paper: “Unfazed by the More-Than-Human Face: Renegotiating Progress through Ethical Address”).

The breadth of topics underscores the multifaceted nature of educational ethics. What unites the contributors is their shared commitment to critically engaging with ethical dimensions of action-oriented inquiries within educational contexts.

Heartfelt thanks go to all the authors whose dedication and expertise have contributed to the success of this work. May this collection inspire a more visible approach to educational ethics in both theory and practice, encourage further reflection, and promote ethically reflective actions across all levels of the education system and beyond.

Walking the Talk: *Is-Ought* as Transdisciplinarity and as a Trans-Domain Approach for Researchers, Teachers, and Students

Jean-Luc Patry

Introduction

Since its very beginning, philosophy has been a system of statements, has been talking. Some philosophers have not only talked about the world and in particular about how it should be, but have also acted accordingly, i.e., they walked the talk. Among those who have done so, one can mention Socrates, who even created a method of dialogue that was named after him, but also lived up to his philosophy and went so far as to die in fulfillment of the principles he had established. Others were very active politicians in the first place, but had a strong philosophical background, like Mahatma Gandhi, Martin Luther King, and Nelson Mandela; they, too, walked their talk. However, while we can find prototypical people who did so, walking the talk itself has not been analyzed very often, and in particular, teaching people to walk the talk has rarely been addressed.

A central topic in both talking and walking is the so-called *Is-Ought* problem, i.e., the distinction between the two domains²⁵ *Is* and *Ought* and (possible) relations between them. In philosophy, this distinction was first addressed by David Hume (1739, pp. 244f.), and it has been an important topic in philosophy since. However, this debate has had little resonance for the walk side, or as Daston (2014, p. 579) said, among the “avant-garde and the rearguard, the devout and the secular, the learned elite and the lay public scientists,” in particular with respect to social issues, such as “deducing” practical recommendations from empirical research results (Friedrich, 2005; 2010). As regards the walk, however, both *Is* and *Ought* are of central importance, as people, in their practical decision-making regarding actions, need to consider both the actual conditions of the situation (the *Is*) and the goals they want to achieve (Patry, 1991b), which they are supposed to justify (the *Ought*). This holds in education, where the educators seek to achieve goals which they are asked to justify explicitly (Klafki, 1984), but in everyday situations as well, since people always want to achieve goals, even if they often do not think about justifying them.

In the present paper, the aim is to show how philosophical talk can have an impact on practice (the walk) in education and through education on students’ practical decision-making in (fictional) situations presenting dilemmas. In the second section, the *Is-Ought* problem is roughly sketched out from the philosophical perspective. Since *Is* and *Ought* are considered to be different disciplines, the “relationship” can be seen as an issue of transdisciplinarity, as discussed in the third section, resulting in the proposition to replace transdisciplinarity with Trans-Domain Approaches (TDAs), with a focus on TDA as a system of statements (talk). In the

²⁵ The term *domain* and how it is used in this paper will be explained below. These two domains will systematically be presented in italics and capitalized.

fourth section, the latter is distinguished from the practice-oriented TDA (walk), and the relations are discussed. In the fifth section, a practical approach—Values *and* Knowledge Education (VaKE)—is briefly introduced and analyzed with respect to *Is* and *Ought*, using the two TDA frameworks (TDA as theory and practice-oriented TDA). In the conclusions, the importance of the concept of TDA and its use for the *Is-Ought* problem on the talk and on the walk levels are discussed, and it is shown how VaKE can be a valuable tool for dealing appropriately with the *Is-Ought* problem and how to educate people to apply it.

1. *Talk: The Is-Ought Problem*

The *Is-Ought* problem as addressed in this paper deals only with types of statements, not with the many interpretations of the *Is-Ought* problem in history (see, for instance, Curry, 2006). The claim is that *Is*-statements and *Ought*-statements are different and that it is not possible to establish logical links between them. For this discussion, the following types of statements are distinguished:

- Descriptive statements (belonging to the domain *Is*) are statements of the type “x is (was, will be) the case.” They refer to (presumed) facts and can be tested, at least in principle, through observation of any kind. *In principle* means here that the following issues are acknowledged: (1) Observations depend on our perceptual apparatus with all its limits and biases; (2) observation of any kind is subject to random and systematic errors (which is a complex issue that I cannot deal with here—I did elsewhere with respect to many issues related with situation specificity [Patry, 2011]); (3) statements are considered as descriptive even if the described phenomenon (supposedly) does not exist (e.g., “Unicorns are white.”); (4) the described characteristics of a phenomenon can be inferred instead of directly observed; etc. Scientific descriptive theories have been tested empirically. For practical actions, people use subjective descriptive theories. Using a correspondence theory of truth, descriptive statements (whether scientific or subjective) can be true or wrong; in a constructivist perspective (Patry, 2016), they are statements expressing what the author believes to be (or not to be) fact or reality; these subjective theories usually have been shown to be useful and successful in achieving goals in practical situations.
- Normative or prescriptive statements (belonging to the domain *Ought*) are statements of the type “x ought to be the case.” or “x ought to be done.” They refer to requirements, to what must be done or what is normatively necessary. This is independent of whether one thinks this ought to be done or be the case. Evaluative statements belong also to the domain *Ought*; these are statements that ascribe a value (like “good,” “beautiful,” etc.) to a state of affairs (fact or action, etc.). These statements are descriptive insofar as they describe some characteristics of a state of affairs, and normative or prescriptive insofar as they express that the state of affairs is normatively or not normatively required (ought or ought not to be). In agreement with Schurz (e.g., 2004), such statements are considered as normative as well. How such statements can be justified is part of the *Is-Ought* problem, namely regarding whether they can be justified through facts.

- Mixed statements are statements that contain descriptive as well as normative components.

Hume (1739, pp. 244f.) was the first to pronounce the thesis that a strict separation exists between *Is* and *Ought*. In a simplified version, it states that one type cannot be justified by (reduced to, deduced from, or even logically related to, etc.) the other one (Schurz, 1995). The logical support for Hume's thesis is very complex (see Schurz, 1995, 1997, 2004, 2010, 2020; Morscher, 2018, 2021; etc.) and cannot be discussed here.

Normative statements are different from statements of the type “person y thinks that x ought to be the case,” as the statement is clearly descriptive; it can be checked, e.g., through asking this person what he or she thinks. According to Hume's thesis, the second part of the statement cannot be tested through observation of any kind. Rather, such statements need to be argued for through ethical justification.

Schurz (2010, p. 202) concretized Hume's thesis: “No purely normative conclusion which is not already logically true is inferable from a consistent set of purely descriptive premises.” However, many statements that are claimed to be purely descriptive contain in fact hidden normative components (Schurz, 1995, p. 163), either because the latter are considered as trivial or because nonrational processes are involved (e.g., Rogerson et al., 2011). It is a matter of scientific and argumentative honesty and transparency to identify and separate the descriptive and the normative components of such statements (Schurz, 2004, p. 15). This way, normative statements cannot be tacitly insinuated, whether intentionally or not; instead, arguments in favor of the normative statements can be put forward. For sake of transparency, such argumentative support is required, even if it consists simply in ascertaining that the normative component is trivial. Therefore, Hume's thesis is not only logically supported, but also an ethical requirement: We must avoid hidden values. This holds for science, where normative statements must be laid open so that they can be communicated and possibly criticized—such a procedure satisfies two important criteria of science: (1) that statements must be communicated, and (2) that they can be criticized within the scientific community. This holds also for everyday behavior, because people are often not aware of the values underlying their decisions (regarding sensitivity for values issues in given situations, see Reynolds & Miller, 2015; Hamlin & Tan, 2020); if they were to think about these values and their justification, they might decide differently.

One can conceive of mixed statements that establish a relation between descriptive and normative statements: so-called bridge principles. Some of them are sometimes claimed to be almost self-evident because they are plausible according to most ethical theories (“*fast analytisch wahr*,” Schurz, 2004, pp. 23f.). The first is “What is required [*Ought*-component] must be feasible at least to some degree [*Is*-component: feasibility]” (Kant, 1956, A548/B576, p. 534)—in the short version, “Ought implies Can”; in other words, One is not allowed to ask someone to do something that he or she is not able to do. The second example is “Necessary consequences of or necessary means for [*Is*-component] required [*Ought* component] actions or states of affairs are also required.” In other words, one can only require something where the conditions or consequences are also approved. Although these bridge principles are “almost self-evident,” it is imperative to make them explicit if applied; the reasons for that are the same as those for goals and their justification, as discussed above. And in situations when a person has to

give priority to one value or norm over the other—in moral dilemmas, for example—both bridge principles become problematic.

A moral dilemma consists of a decision situation in which the protagonist has to decide between two behavioral options which are incompatible, i.e., cannot be performed simultaneously; acting according to the first option will comply with a set of norms or values, but break another set of norms which is achieved through the second behavioral option—the latter, however, will break the norms that the first option fulfills. In such difficult situations, the respective values are contested, as the protagonist has to give priority to one set (related to one behavior option) to the detriment of the ones linked to the other option. In such dilemmas, “*Ought* implies *Can*” becomes problematic, as *Can* is impossible for the two options simultaneously, and hence if this bridge principle is applied, it is inappropriate to require both *Oughts* simultaneously, since this requirement cannot be fulfilled (Williams, 1973)—this is the bridge principle “*Ought* implies *Can*” on a meta-level, where the *Can* is impossible on logical grounds (since one cannot achieve two actions simultaneously that mutually exclude each other).

Ethical questions become relevant primarily in (moral) dilemmas. In such situations of contested values or norms, it is a necessity to discuss them. If there is agreement about the values or the protagonist does not recognize competing values (possibly because of lack of moral sensitivity), there is no need to worry about them. One must mention, however, that life is full of antinomies, i.e., opposing requirements or demands of the situation, or in other words, we are very often confronted with multiple goals that cannot be achieved simultaneously (Patry, 1991b, 2012)—however, we often recognize such conflicts only if we are asked to make our goals explicit (Patry, 2005).

The application of Hume’s thesis does not mean that scientists must avoid using values in their statements, like those that for instance Brezinka (1994) requires for educational research (“*Erziehungswissenschaft*”); indeed, a differentiated analysis shows that in empirical educational research, normative statements cannot be avoided. Science cannot be values-free (Kincaid et al., 2007); educational research, in particular, cannot restrain from values judgments since education itself always involves values goals, etc. (Patry, 2006), which need to be justified; further, the choice of the research topic is always based on (personal or societal) values, and the research process must follow research ethics (J.-L. Patry & P. Patry, 2003); and finally, often, authors of reports derive practical recommendations from their research results, which again are normative (Patry, 2006). It is inevitable, thus, that one addresses both *Is* and *Ought* in educational research, and this must be made explicit to satisfy the scientific criterion of transparency.

However, the support of the two types of statements follows different argumentation patterns (Zecha, 1984). Descriptive statements refer directly or at least indirectly to observation of some kind—with all the ensuing problems of descriptive research (once the normative issues of this research are dealt with appropriately). In contrast, normative statements can only be justified through referring to superordinate values, i.e., values that encompass, but are not identical with, subordinate value; for instance, the value *human dignity* is superordinate to the value *esteeming interaction*. Besides esteem, there are other issues pertaining to dignity, such as accepting that other people have different opinion, etc. (see the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, United Nations, 1948, where the general principle of dignity is addressed as a key issue of the preamble

on which all the subsequent articles are based). This leads to the so-called Münchhausen trilemma (see Albert, 1985, pp. 18f.): the justification of a value v_1 through a superordinary value v_2 requires that v_2 also be justified, which is only possible through a value v_3 that is superordinary to v_2 , and so on. The trilemma consists in three possibilities, each of which is unacceptable or not satisfactory. Albert called this situation “Münchhausen” in reference to the famous lying Baron who pretended to have pulled himself and his horse out of a swamp by his own hair. The three possibilities are

1. an *infinite regress*, which seems to arise from the necessity to go further and further back in the search for foundations, and which, since it is in practice impossible, affords no secure basis;
2. a *logical circle* in the deduction, which arises because, in the process of justification, statements are used which were characterized before as need in foundation, so that they can provide no secure basis; and, finally,
3. the *breaking-off of the process* at a particular point, which, admittedly, can always be done in principle, but involves an arbitrary suspension of the principle of sufficient justification. (Albert, 1985, p. 18)

Infinite regress is not feasible, and the circular argument (the Münchhausen solution) is unacceptable; hence only the third option can be considered. This means that one must decide on a “highest value” which is not scrutinized. For educational purposes, intuitively, the value “Human Dignity” is chosen, with reference to the United Nations’ (1948) Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

Although *Is* and *Ought* belong to different domains and cannot logically be related with each other, from a different perspective, and referring to practical decision-making, *Is* and *Ought* need to be considered simultaneously. The principle is: Values without knowledge is blind; knowledge without societal values leads to selfishness and is a threat to humankind. This means that just defending certain values (*Ought* values), even the most justified ones, will not help to change the world if there is no knowledge (*Is*) about the reasons for the respective problems and about possibilities to change them. On the other hand, someone who may have knowledge about such issues but does not prioritize the value of better conditions for mankind and the universe over his or her personal wellbeing will not be motivated to do anything about the problem at stake: quite the opposite. As Francis Bacon (1597, qtd.in Baggaley et al., 2013, p. 898) said, “*knowledge is power*,” and power is likely to be abused if not controlled by societal values.

Take as example one of the Great Challenges to humankind and the planet: the climate crisis. To address this challenge, one needs, on one hand, knowledge about the fact that there is global warming, what this means, and the reasons it is occurring (*Is*); but one also needs the motivation to do something about it, which means reducing one’s comfort in favor of the greater good. This is a values preference (personal comfort vs. greater good) which can only be decided on ethical grounds (*Ought*). Commitment for the greater good without knowledge about facts (in particular what can be done, e.g., how to reduce CO₂, and arguments against intervening, e.g., the economic consequences of doing so), i.e., *Ought* without *Is*, leads to blind activism and fundamentalism and will have little impact on the climate. In contrast, knowledge of issues concerning global warming without prioritizing the greater good (*Is* without *Ought*) increases the climate problem

because the person will not do anything to fight it or even deny that there is a climate change; our perception is dependent on our values! More generally, for all Great Challenges (discrimination, global warming, corruption, lies, pandemics, racism, sexism, violence, to name just a few) and for most personal decisions, considering both *Is* and *Ought* is required.

The concept “Values without knowledge is blind; knowledge without societal values is dangerous” has been stated thus by Hume: “Human nature being compos’d of two principal parts, which are requisite in all its actions, the affections and understanding; ‘tis certain, that the blind motions of the former, without the direction of the latter, incapacitate men for society” (1739, p. 256). For science, it follows that *Is* and *Ought* need to be related to each other. For education, this leads to the requirement that one should educate for both knowledge (education in the domain of *Is*: acquiring knowledge of viable descriptive statements) and values (education in the domain of *Ought*: acquiring viable values systems), and also that these two domains are to be related to each other; knowledge and values must address the same topic (e.g., a Great Challenge) and cannot be seen as independent.

2. *Transdisciplinarity, Domains, and Trans-Domain Approaches (TDAs) as Systems of Statements*

Is and *Ought* refer to different scientific disciplines; establishing a relationship between them, hence, is an issue of transdisciplinarity. *Is* is dealt with in different descriptive scientific disciplines like science, technology, psychology, sociology, etc. In contrast, *Ought* is the topic of philosophy, more precisely of ethics (and meta-ethics). Establishing a relationship between *Is* and *Ought*, as required at the end of the last section, hence, means that these disciplines cannot be seen independently, but must be addressed simultaneously under a common framework. This is dealt with in the literature under the title of transdisciplinarity (see also Scholz & Steiner, 2015, p. 528; Bauer & Meyerhuber, 2020; and many others). Transdisciplinarity can be defined as consisting of a “shared conceptual framework drawing together disciplinary-specific theories, concepts, and approaches to address (a) common problem” (Rosenfield, 1992, table 3). Referring to transdisciplinarity permits us to connect the *Is-Ought* problem addressed in the previous section with the discussions that have been underway since Jantsch (1947) first introduced the term (see also OECD/CERI, 1972, which will also be capitalized on in the following discussion (see also Patry, 2022a, 2022b).

However, the word *disciplines* opens up a sociological category (Patry, 2022a) in several regards:

- Disciplines are intellectual and social structures;
- they diffuse types of social organizations for the production of particular knowledge (Weingart & Stehr, 2000, p. xiv);
- they define themselves and can be defined in several ways (Van Assche, 2013);
- they serve to defend territories within the scientific community (Weingart, 2000, p. 28);
- they have institutional consequences (Mittelstrass, 2018);
- they are biased, among others by a Western (and often Eurocentric) concept of a valid approach to knowledge (Judge, 1991);

- they underwent important changes in history, as some disciplines disappeared, and most of the remaining ones underwent increasing specialization (Bromme & Kienhues, 2014, p. 56);
- they refer to the historically grown organization of science and not to a stable category (Balsiger, 2005, pp. 51-57; Mittelstrass, 2018, p. S71);
- today's disciplines are so heterogeneous and defined so differently that it is impossible to find common denominators and boundaries (Van Assche, 2013);
- disciplines are interrelated in different ways, and the science system is considered "as non-linear, but turning on itself in an endless spiral, to say nothing of the numerous inter-connections among the terms" (Piaget, 1972, p. 131);
- they refer to social structures to be addressed in the sociology of science (Van Assche, 2013).

This means that disciplines are used to organize science according to criteria which are not epistemological but historical, sociological, organizational, etc.; hence, the concept of disciplines is inappropriate for the purpose of finding a common underlying theoretical framework (such as combining *Is* and *Ought*), which is an epistemological endeavor.

Instead of *disciplines*, it is proposed to use the concept of *domain*. In the present context, this term does not refer to the structure of internet addresses according to the Domain Name System (DNS). Rather, the root is in the domains of knowledge, i.e., the "semantic knowledge for a particular field" (Newberry et al., 2021, p. 660). A domain consists of the knowledge of specialists in a specific, delimited field, including, but not restricted to, a specialized discipline. It is, hence, a relatively closed system of statements, a set of research topics or thematic fields that is addressed with a homogeneous system of related theories that are studied with similar methods; such a system is clearly distinct from other such systems, with the delimitations being scientifically grounded. These theories will be called Domain-specific Theories (DT). The definition of domains is kept open to permit its application in different contexts. In particular, the focus will not be on the domains themselves, but on the lack of obvious relations *between* two or more domains. The goal of TDA research is the same as the one for transdisciplinarity: to provide as much insight as possible about a research topic, notwithstanding the boundaries that may exist or have been erected between different fields of research. However, the concept of domains is wider and more flexible than the one of disciplines, and can be argued about more precisely since the relationships or lack thereof are scientific and do not depend on the haphazardness of the distinction between disciplines.

Instead of transdisciplinarity, consequently, the concept of Trans-Domain Approaches (TDA) will be used. A TDA is defined as *a system of scientific statements that relates to the theories of different domains and adds new issues to the ones already contained in the respective domain-specific theories in order to achieve a goal that cannot be reached within one domain* (Patry, 2022a, p. 3). The different aspects of this definition are addressed in a theory of TDA.

This theory of TDA is proposed as follows (for details, see Patry, 2022a, 2022b; Patry et al., 2022; Patry & Weyringer, 2019). First, one can distinguish a TDA as system of statements (or theories) and as actions:

A TDA consists of a scientific system of theories that includes a [General Theory] GT that connects, integrates, and transcends a set of specialized (domain-specific) theories (DTs), but does not replace them. This goes beyond a simple combination of the domains (which would be called interdisciplinarity or inter-domain approach); rather, the GT contains more information than can be found in the combined theories of the respective domains or DTs alone, but does not include all information contained in the respective DTs. The GT, hence, is a superordinate theory.... The DTs, in turn, address some issues of the research topic with more details but narrower bandwidth than the GT as they focus only on certain issues and do not consider other ones that, from the perspective of TDA, would be important as well. (Patry, 2022a, p. 3)

A superordinate theory is a theory that addresses issues that are already the topic of two or more other theories (subordinate theories) and that relates them with each other; for instance, the Cognitive-Affective Personality System (CAPS; Mischel & Shoda, 1995) is superordinate to six subordinate theories that the authors call Cognitive-Affective Units (CAUS): competence, perception, expectancies, values and goals, self-regulatory plans, and emotions. Each of these, in turn, is superordinate to a set of subordinate theories (the theory of competences, for instance, includes theories dealing with different types of intelligence, creativity, subjective theories, etc.), which again are superordinate to sets of subordinate theories on a lower level (for intelligence, for instance, the different types of intelligence according to the theory of multiple intelligence; Gardner, 1993). Some have called such superordinate theories “meta-theories” (e.g., Shoda & Mischel, 2006 with respect to the CAPS), but this is inappropriate, since meta-theories are theories *about* theories, whereas superordinate theories are theories that *include* other theories (for details, see Patry, 2014). In the case of meta-theories, the object is theories, which have as object phenomena or norms, while in the latter case, the object can be the same for superordinate and subordinate theories, namely phenomena and/or norms.

The TDA is represented graphically in figure 1, showing the distinction of the General Theory (GT) from the Domain-Specific Theories (DT), with the former being superordinate to the latter (this figure was inspired by Rousseau et al., 2018, p. 53). Applying this principle to the *Is-Ought* problem results in the hierarchy presented figure 2, with two levels: the superordinate level addresses the General Theory about education, since the aim of the present paper is to show how philosophical talk about *Is* and *Ought* can have an impact on practice (the walk) through education. The Specific Theories are *Is* (DT 1) and *Ought* (DT 2). On the subordinate level, new TDAs can be established (TDA' 1, TDA' 2); the prime symbol should signal that the TDAs are on a subordinate level. The respective Domain-Specific Theories DT 1 and DT 2 become General Theories GT' 1 and GT' 2, respectively, for the subordinate Domain-Specific Theories DT' 1.1 etc. For instance, a descriptive framework about education (G' 1) could present the distinction between instruction (telling people what they are supposed to know; DT' 1.1), construction (letting people find out for themselves the content, following the principles of constructivism, e.g., von Glasersfeld, 1995; DT' 1.2), and other educational principles; a distinction in the *Ought* domain could be between deontic concepts (I should do x because the principle underlying x must be applied; DT' 2.1) and teleological concepts (I should do x because the consequences of doing x must be achieved; DT' 2.2). This hierarchy can be extended, with the DT's becoming GT''s on the subordinate level double-prime (this is not

represented in fig. 2). One can imagine different concepts of differentiation; for instance, one can conceive an alternative TDA' 2*, where content-oriented domains, like justice (DT' 2,1*), care (DT' 2.2*), truthfulness (DT' 2.3*), etc., are distinguished—the asterisk should signal that this is another possibility on the same level. Which alternative to choose will depend on the topic of research or on the problem addressed, or on the preferences of the researcher.

Figure 1: TDA as relationships between General Theory (GT), Domain-specific Theories (DTs), domains, and a research topic (from Patry, 2022a, p. 4)

Super-ordinate level (TDA)	General Theory (GT) Theory about Education					
	Domain-Specific Theory DT 1 <i>Is</i>			Domain-Specific Theory DT 2 <i>Ought</i>		
Sub-ordinate level (TDA's)	GT' 1 = DT 1 <i>Is</i>			GT' 2 = DT 2 <i>Ought</i>		
	DT' 1.1 Instruction	DT' 1.2 Constructi on	DT' 1.3 ...	DT' 2.1 Deontic concepts	DT' 2.2 Teleological concepts	

Figure 2: TDA for *Is-Ought* in education: a hierarchy

3. Practice-oriented TDAs

The theory-practice transfer—or, in the terminology used here, the move from the talk to the walk—is hampered by many problems (Patry, 2018). Among them, the generality-concreteness antinomy is particularly important (Patry, 2017). This antinomy states that the more general a statement is, the less concrete it can be (based on Herrmann, 1979a, pp. 160ff.; 1979b, pp. 232). This holds in particular for social interactions because they are situation specific, and it also applies to descriptive (Patry, 1991a) as well as normative statements (Elliott, 2015). The talks in science and philosophy, e.g., the TDA about *Is* and *Ought* (figure 2, superordinate level), are

usually very general: the claim in most studies is that the statements apply for all possible situations, people, times, etc.: only a few studies express explicit restrictions with respect to the bandwidth of the validity of the statements. Further, when referring to research studies from the literature, researchers almost never consider that the statements they cite might not apply to the situation studied in their own research. However, this claim is not justified for many reasons (see Patry, 2019, for some of these reasons), and the application might be erroneous. Only the theories that have been tested might have a certain validity across different situations and conditions, but if so, only on a very abstract level, so that the specific conditions (e.g., the concrete situation) in which people must decide what to do cannot be taken into account.

Practical decision-making (walk) requires concreteness. When I have to decide what to do in a specific situation, I must take into consideration all specificities that may be important in this situation; a slight change in one of the characteristics may lead to a completely different decision. For example, how I decide to act in a conflict situation will depend on the type of conflict, on its history, on the type of relationship to it, on the goals I want to achieve and the respective importance of goals that can be antinomic, on other people involved, etc. All these issues cannot be taken into account at the talk level (e.g., in philosophical theories). The move from talk to walk, then, is the transfer of abstract, general statements to concrete decisions to be taken while considering all the relevant details of the given specific situation.

This problem cannot be solved within a TDA as a system of statements because statements will always be general and abstract (an exception might be found in action research in the sense of Elliott, 1978, but its results are then highly limited in the generalizability scope), and actions need a specific and concrete decision base. Instead, a *TDA as action* is required. For this, the model of theory-practice transfer developed by Patry (2022a, p. 5, based on Patry, 1989) can be used (an adapted version with particular consideration of *Is* and *Ought* is presented in fig. 3).

Figure 3: Model of the theory-practice transfer, focusing in particular on *Is* and *Ought* (based on Patry, 2022a, p. 5)

According to this model (which can be considered as a superordinate theory with a series of subordinate theories), one can distinguish three roles: those of researcher, mediator, and practitioner²⁶:

- The *researchers* produce and test theories. For this, they need to refer to both the *Ought* and the *Is* domains: they decide on the research topic, which depends on, among other things, their values (*Ought*), and capitalize on the work of previous researchers, which is described in the literature or through other communication channels (*Is*); they develop and test theories, which may include descriptive (*Is*) and normative (*Ought*) theories; from the results, they draw conclusions, in particular with respect to practice, which depends on normative premises (e.g., what goal do I want to achieve, and why?).
- The *mediators* process scientific theories so that practitioners can grab their central messages and use them in their decision-making; examples are textbooks or teacher education courses. For this, the mediators use scientific theories (which can be found in the literature—descriptive), of which they select those that they think to be important for the practitioners—this is a decision based on normative premises along with other criteria. Further, they present the selected theories in a form they judge to be appropriate for the practitioner, which also depends on normative premises (e.g., when emphasizing certain issues and neglecting others, or when providing concrete examples chosen for good—normative—reasons) along with other things.
- The practitioners, first, integrate the communicated information from the mediators into their system of subjective theories, i.e., their system of beliefs and convictions—both descriptive and normative—about the world and themselves (Groeben et al., 1988); Piaget (1985) calls this assimilation and accommodation. However, the practitioners do not integrate the information as presented; rather, they select what seems important to them, and they add interpretations (e.g., prototypical examples from their own experience) that are not included in the mediator’s message. Such selections and additional interpretations depend on the practitioner’s normative concepts, among other things.
- Based on their system of subjective theories—which contains not only scientific insight but also many concepts they may never have thought about, as well as further goals and other norms—and on their perception and interpretation of the given situation, the practitioners decide what they want to do in this situation. Which elements of their system of subjective theories they select for decision-making, how they transfer them into an action decision, and how they implement the decision will depend on, among other things, normative premises, most importantly on the goals they want to achieve. (These goals and possibly their justification are parts of the system of subjective theories).

²⁶ It is possible that the same person performs two or even three roles successively, such as a teacher (practitioner) who acts also as researcher, or a researcher who writes textbooks for practitioners (mediator), or even a teacher who does research and does teacher-training.

As can be seen in the above, all of the roles involve both descriptive (*Is*) and normative (*Ought*) components and combine them in some way (how this is done is a complex topic which cannot be dealt with here; see Gastager & Patry, 2018, for some considerations in this regard). The respective person (researcher, mediator, practitioner) takes some decision based on both descriptive and normative premises. In the terminology used above, those premises are the *talk* (even the subjective theories must be considered talk, as they consist of, or can be reconstructed as, systems of statements), always capitalizing on several domain-specific theories from the domains *Is* and *Ought* and the respective subordinate domain-specific theories, thus based on the respective TDAs.

In any case, this TDA will distinguish the domains *Is* and *Ought*, as in figure 2 (superordinate level). One can analyze the possibilities on the subordinate level to identify the three roles. This is rarely done for the researcher; one can interpret Mahoney (1976) and Faust (1984) for the *Is* domain (GT' 1 in fig. 2) and Patry & Patry (2003) for the *Ought* domain (GT' 2) as such TDA's, although they are not discussed in that way and with that terminology. As to the role of mediator, discussion has mainly been on teacher trainers; an example is the analysis of the mentors' subjective theories when discussing the lesson of a pre-service teacher in internship (Roither, 2014), where *Is* as well as *Ought* is addressed. For the practitioners, several analyses have been done, in particular those discussed in Gastager & Patry (2018). While the respective TDAs and TDA's of the researchers were discussed on a general (and therefore abstract) level, the discussions of the other two roles of TDAs and TDA's, addressed in Roither and in Gastager & Patry, referred to specific situations to permit the discussions to be very concrete. However, one must mention that addressing situation-specific issues in practice, as would be necessary for such an endeavor, is rather rare in educational research.

In all the decisions of the researchers, mediators, and practitioners, the theoretical framework available (descriptive and normative: talk) is general and abstract (although to a different degree), whereas the decision itself as preparation to the walk requires a specific and concrete base. The generality-concreteness antinomy with which the practitioner is confronted here leaves a vacancy between the respective talks and the concrete situation-specific base for the walk. To fill this vacancy, the decider has to be creative and formulate his or her own ideas and transfer concepts. This creative act has been called *pedagogical tact* by Herbart (1802/1896), and is discussed in detail by, among others, Burghardt et al. (2015), Burghardt & Zirfas (2019), and Gastager & Patry (2018). One can see that the TDA as action is an achievement of the respective actors; it rests on TDAs as systems of statements, but clearly goes beyond them.

4. *Walk: Values and Knowledge Education (VaKE)*

So far, the movement from talk to walk has been discussed with respect to the practitioners. In the present section, I will go a step further and address the question of teaching students to achieve this transfer, taking into account *Is* and *Ought*. The teaching-learning method to be presented is called Values and Knowledge Education (VaKE; Weyringer et al., 2022). It is a constructivist approach that combines values education (educating for *Ought*) and knowledge education (acquiring knowledge about *Is*) with mutual reference. The starting point of the process is a moral dilemma. As said above, such a dilemma consists of a situation in which a protagonist has to decide which of two alternatives to undertake. Whatever he or she does, he or she will violate some value. For instance, the protagonist has to decide whether to support or to

oppose the building of a freeway around a small town. If he or she supports this to comply with values like keeping traffic out of the city center, seeking economic advantages, etc., he or she will break values like reducing traffic and instead increase the emission of harmful substances, avoid the sealing of the soil surface, etc. The two groups of values cannot be achieved simultaneously. And as mentioned above, it is in the discussion of such dilemmas that moral issues become relevant; hence, they are at the core of practical ethics.

In such a moral dilemma, the students are highly motivated to discuss the justification of their normative preferences. Research has shown that such discussions foster competence in arguing in favor of or against values (e.g., Lind, 2016). A framework to analyze this can be based on Kohlberg's (1984) stage theory of moral judgment competence, which goes from egoism (stage 1) to principle-guided morality (stage 6). However, the theoretical framework of VaKE is not Kohlbergian in the sense of Kohlberg (1981, 1984), not even neo-Kohlbergian (e.g., Rest et al., 2000; Thoma, 2014); rather, it can be called *post-Kohlbergian* (see also Arnold, 2000; Lapsley & Narvaez, 2005). In agreement with the Kohlbergian or neo-Kohlbergian approaches, some key issues are kept, such as the constructivist background with assimilation, disequilibrium and accommodation as modus operandi of development, autonomy and universality as overarching values—i.e., the approach is *prescriptivist* and not ethically relativistic (Kohlberg, 1971), and the focus is on *reasoning* and on the *justification* of values instead of on values indoctrination. In contrast, VaKE differs from the (neo-) Kohlbergian concepts in the following regards, dealing with *Is* and *Ought* (other differences are not discussed here; see Patry et al., in prep.):

- By its very concept, in VaKE, the values education framework (education of *Ought*) is *combined with theories of knowledge acquisition* (acquisition of *Is*)—in the sense of the TDA on the superordinate level, see figure 2—and with other theories.
- It refers not only to moral principles underlying one's actions (*deontic* perspective; see DT' 2.1 in fig. 2), but also to the consequences of one's action (*teleological* concepts; see DT' 2.2).
- It refers not only to moral, but also to *other values* (e.g., personal interest, such as caring for one's own safety and health).

In VaKE, the moral dilemma is discussed by the participants, with the focus on the justification of the chosen values preferences. However, the dilemma is conceived in such a way that to discuss it competently, the students need some knowledge. For instance, in the freeway construction dilemma presented above, the students ask questions about the economic advantage of having freeways, whether freeways lead to more traffic, how much soil is needed for a freeway, what the consequences of the sealing of the soil are, which harmful substances are emitted by cars and how harmful they are, whether fast driving pollutes more than slow driving, etc. They soon recognize that they need information, and ask questions about facts (*Is*). The students are then asked to search for answers to these questions themselves, using any available source like the internet, books, etc.; they can also ask the teacher, who might be competent in the domain of knowledge. The procedure involves a typical constructivist approach (see DT' 1.2 in fig. 2) and follows the principles of inquiry-based learning (e.g., Dobber et al., 2017; Furtak et al., 2012; Pedaste et al., 2015).

After the search phase and the exchanging of information, the students engage in a new discussion on the values preferences, this time on a higher level since they now can capitalize on the newly acquired knowledge. They proceed in a similar way as do the practitioners of figure 3, although in contrast to those, they have time to discuss and to come to a collaborative decision, and they decide not for themselves but for a fictional protagonist so that they can disregard personal values if they so want. In particular, in these discussions they combine values arguments (*Ought*) with facts they have identified in their search (*Is*), thus performing a TDA as action on the superordinate level (fig. 2). Experience shows that the students always combine several knowledge domains and refer to different ethical theories; this means that their discussions are also based on TDA's²⁷ on the subordinate level (fig. 2), with the content domains (GT' 1) adapted to the topic, as in figure 4. According to the principles of super- and subordinate TDAs, each of the domain-specific theories DT 1, DT 2, etc., can be a TDA' of its own—in the ecological issues, for instance, one can distinguish the domains of pollution, soil sealing, noise, etc., and within pollution a TDA' with CO₂, nitric oxides, hydrogen sulfides, etc. And the same principle can be applied to the *Ought* domain.

Figure 4: Possible TDA' for the DT 1 (*Is*) for the freeway dilemma

One can also conceive of a TDA where *Is* and *Ought* are related to each other on a subordinate level, as shown in figure 5 for the topic of the nitric oxides that are emitted by cars. These have an impact on human health, on acid rain, on ozone, etc., which in turn have specific consequences (for simplification, the impact and its consequences are combined on the subordinate level in fig. 5). These impacts and consequences are scientific facts, hence belonging to the *Is* domain. With respect to the *Ought* domain, the values of the respective issues (e.g., health and its consequences) are addressed. There is therefore a link between the *Is* issues and the corresponding *Ought* issues as they address the same topic, respectively, but once from the descriptive (DT' 1.1, etc.) and once from the normative (DT' 2.1, etc.) perspective.

It is important to emphasize that in VaKE, the respective TDAs are achieved not (only) by the individual students, but as a collaborative endeavor and achievement, with all students contributing their respective perspectives, values priorities and justifications, and knowledge base to the final decision about what the protagonist in the dilemma should do; this decision,

²⁷ The prime symbol does not always refer to the same super- and sub-ordinate level; rather, it represents the super- and subordinate structure in the direct context, hence the same level is sometimes called TDA when superordinate and TDA' when subordinate.

then, is supported by arguments relating to *Is* as well as to *Ought*. Such a collaborative work requires communication, i.e., the students need to make their knowledge base and their values and justifications explicit and expose them to a check whether they are considered valid by the peers; the latter, in turn, have to make explicit why they do or do not accept the respective arguments. This satisfies the requirement of transparency that has been expressed above as a condition for scientific work—tacit insinuations of values are not eliminated, but reduced to a minimum. In particular, the values on which the participants spontaneously agree are not discussed as they are not contested. These collectively accepted values can, to some degree, have the function of “highest value” in the third possibility of the Münchhausen trilemma discussed above.

Super-ordinate level	General Theory (GT) Theory about nitric oxides							
	Domain-Specific Theory DT 1 <i>Is</i>				Domain-Specific Theory DT 2 <i>Ought</i>			
Sub-ordinate level	GT' 1 = DT 1 <i>Impacts and consequences</i>				GT' 2 = DT 2 <i>Related values</i>			
	DT' 1.1 Impact on health and consequences	DT' 1.2 Impact on acid rain and consequences	DT' 1.3 Impact on ozone and consequences	DT' 1.3 ...	DT' 2.1 Value of health and consequences	DT' 2.2 Value of acid rain and consequences	DT' 2.3 Value of ozone and consequences	DT' 2.4 ...

Figure 5: Addressing the same issues from the *Is* and from the *Ought* perspective

In consequence, the students learn three competences:

- Within the *Is* domain, they learn many walk competences (in the sense of the competence to do something): to ask questions about necessary knowledge in specific situation; to search for responses to their questions; to judge which information (and information sources) are trustworthy and which ones are not (“fake news”); to put information from different domains in relation to each other (TDA’ with respect to the *Is* domain); to apply information in a given concrete situation; and to use information on a higher level according to the Bloom et al. (1956) taxonomy (analysis, synthesis, evaluation)—in contrast to traditional teaching which, it seems, focuses on the lower taxonomical levels (knowledge, understanding, application); etc. And they learn talk competence by acquiring knowledge.
- As to the *Ought* domain, they learn a series of walk competences: to recognize that most situations with which they are confronted in their everyday life involve values (moral sensitivity); to make the values involved in such situations explicit; to consider different values and different types of values simultaneously (TDA’ with respect to the *Ought* domain); to recognize the need to argue in favor of or against values; to see that other people may defend other values, and with good

reasons, and to accept that they do so without taking over their position; to argue in favor of or against values on a higher competence level than heretofore; to put themselves in the shoes of others who defend different perspectives; etc. On the talk level, they learn to esteem general values like human dignity, care for the environment, etc.

- With respect to walking the relationship between *Is* and *Ought*, finally, the students learn that the different issues or topics addressed in their discussion can be seen—and need to be seen—from both the *Is* and the *Ought* perspectives; to separate the two perspectives, but to relate them to each other; to understand that the two perspective require different types of argumentation and criticism; etc.

All these learning effects have either been shown in systematic empirical studies (for an overview, see Weyringer et al., 2022), or at least there is anecdotal evidence for them. They involve both talk and walk competences. The talk competences refer to knowledge, sensitivity for values issues, and acknowledgment of the need to use both *Is* and *Ought* but to distinguish the different types of argumentation. The walk part that the participants learn refers to all the activities mentioned above.

Conclusion

The *Is-Ought* problem is a crucial topic in educational research as well as in educational practice. To be able to deal competently with it is further an important goal of education because it is a pre-requirement for solving crucial challenges to mankind. However, the problem has mainly been discussed on the levels of philosophy (meta-ethics, to some degree also ethics) and of practitioners' concepts (e.g., teachers' goals and the means they have to achieve them), which can be considered as *talk*, whereas little has been said about how actors actually handle this problem in practice and how this can be improved through education (*walk*). Because *Is* and *Ought* are addressed in different disciplines, the concept of transdisciplinarity can be used for the discussion of these issues; however, since disciplines are a sociological category and not an epistemological one, as would be necessary for the discussion of the *Is-Ought* problem, it seems appropriate to replace transdisciplinarity with another basic framework which we have called the Trans-Domain Approach (TDA). Doing this permits us to avoid the restrictions and disadvantages met when discussing the disciplines but still to capitalize on insight gained in discussions of transdisciplinarity. In particular, the distinction between TDA as a system of sentences (theories) and TDA as actions is relevant, and within the former, provides more detailed concepts of theory systems—both can be found in the literature on transdisciplinarity and have proved fruitful in the concept of TDA.

The analyses presented above showed how useful the concept of TDA is. In particular, it was possible to deal with all the issues that were addressed without caring whether the frameworks at stake were from different disciplines or not. Admittedly, the concept of domains as used above is to some degree fuzzy, and the definition of a domain may vary from one analysis to another—for instance, what was treated as one domain on the superordinate level was divided into several sub-domains in the subordinate level—and there is not one and only one way to conceive domains and sub-domains for a given topic (research problem, dilemma, etc.). Rather, one can conceive of different TDA structures depending on the topic, the type of problem one

addresses, and the way one attempts to solve it (this was also the reason why transdisciplinarity was required in the first place; OECD/CERI, 1972). But on the other hand, the topics we have to deal with in today's world are so complex that there is no one single way to deal with them; in fact, it is necessary to use different approaches simultaneously (Patry, 2013).

The analysis also showed that transdisciplinarity or Trans-Domain Approaches are not just academic constructions or research concepts. Rather, they have a direct impact on our lives. With respect to the *Is-Ought* problem, the concept of TDA with its treating *Is* and *Ought* as different domains permits, on the level of the talk (theory-building), to overcome the deadlock advanced in Hume's (1739) thesis of the strict separation of *Is* and *Ought* with claims like the requirement that educational research must not make normative statements (Brezinka, 1994) or that science is values-free. Both claims cannot be satisfied, as research will always be values laden, especially educational research, since education aims at achieving goals which necessarily have a normative base. On the level of walk (acting or deciding to act based on more or less general principles), the TDA as action as proposed in figure 3 (theory-practice transfer) has proven to be fruitful. And finally, with respect to values and knowledge education for students, the TDA was fruitful in analyzing the students' discussions in *VaKE* as well as in accounting for their learning, with respect to both the talk and the walk.

On the other hand, *VaKE* was shown to be quite a useful teaching-learning tool in helping students talk and walk in the field of *Is* and *Ought*. In particular, our world and its challenges need people who recognize the urgency of intervening beyond one's immediate benefit but in the interest of humankind or even the planet, including its future, as can be seen with the climate crisis. This need requires that the people defend societal values (*Ought*). But such values are blind if not combined with knowledge about facts (*Is*) which permit the diagnostics and targeted interventions needed to overcome the challenges. In other words, the two domains must be combined on the different (superordinate and subordinate) levels. *VaKE* is an educational approach that does just this. The claim is not that it is the only approach to achieving that goal, but at least it is one possible way.

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***The Aims of Education*—Alfred North Whitehead’s Ideas on Education and Learning Revisited After 100 Years**

Christian Kraler

The education of a human being is a most complex topic, which we have hardly begun to understand. The only point on which I feel certain is that there is no widespread, simple solution. (Whitehead, 1948, p. 9)

Introduction

The aim of this article is to take the reader on a guided tour of Alfred North Whitehead’s thoughts and concepts concerning education and learning. Although he published his most influential work in this context—*The Aims of Education and Other Essays*—nearly a century ago, his insights remain strikingly relevant today. Yet despite their enduring significance, Whitehead himself and his philosophy of education remains relatively little known.

A. N. Whitehead is primarily known for his fundamental work on mathematics, *Principia Mathematica*, written together with Bertrand Russell (his former student). *Principia Mathematica* is a three-volume work on the foundations of mathematics, published between 1910 and 1913. In a smaller circle, among specialist philosophers and theologians, he is also known as a philosopher and especially as a metaphysician for his concept of process philosophy. In *Process and Reality* (1929/1978) Whitehead developed a distinctive and original model of process philosophy (process thought and process metaphysics) influenced by concepts from Hegel, Bergson, James, Dewey and the—at that time—latest developments in physics (General Theory of Relativity and Quantum Theory). This book also contains his probably most famous and widely known quote: “The safest general characterization of the European philosophical tradition is that it consists of a series of footnotes to Plato” (Whitehead, 1929/1978, p. 39). The quote can be read as a criticism of European academic philosophy at the beginning of the 20th century. Whitehead compared its status with that of the deadlocked medieval scholasticism of around 1400. He saw his three books, *Science and The Modern World*, *Process and Reality*, and *Adventure of Ideas*, as an intellectual exploration of a New World surpassing the philosophical deadlock (Whitehead, 1933, p. 6-7), especially in the field of Natural Philosophy and Metaphysics.

Whitehead experienced and argued against a similar stagnation in his own time, serving as an academic teacher in the field of education and working in universities. For instance, he campaigned in vain for the full admission of women to Cambridge University around the 1890s (Whitehead, 1896). He felt that the traditional universities, especially Oxford and Cambridge, had developed into rather backward-looking institutions, rigid in their educational aims and forms. Whitehead was convinced that academic institutions could only preserve an evolving,

vibrant culture and scientific progress by avoiding dogmatism. He felt they had to be constantly challenged (Hampe, 1998, p. 21). The situation, which he personally perceived as an academic standstill, and in particular as the institutional neglect of empirical sciences, finally prompted him to move from Cambridge to London.

There, first as a lecturer in (applied) mathematics and physics at the University College, and later as Professor at the Imperial College for Science and Technology, Whitehead was successful in establishing new academic institutions such as experimental-polytechnical training centres. He was also involved in teacher training and held a number of administrative positions where he worked to develop technical education and reform university education in general.

The interplay and interlocking of theoretical and application-oriented elements within the framework of study programmes was of central importance to him throughout his whole academic career, especially in an environment that still was traditionally and conservatively theoretically oriented, with a curriculum and teaching philosophy tracing back to the mid-19th century. He writes,

The students are alive, and the purpose of education is to stimulate and guide their self-development. It follows as a corollary from this premiss, that the teachers also should be alive with living thoughts. (Whitehead, 1929, p. v)

This quote from the introduction to his book *The Aims of Education* can be seen as an education-oriented summary of Whitehead's philosophy. The language shows that his roots are in mathematics. The word 'corollary' points to the aliveness of teachers as a by-product of the stated purpose of education. The aliveness of pupils and teachers indicates the experience and (indirectly) the process orientation of Whitehead's philosophy. And stimulation and guidance give a hint to a relational, student-teacher configuration in the setting of formal education, where students and teachers stand each in relation to themselves and also in relation to each other, with the goal to stimulate and guide self-development. Of course, one needs to know a little about Whitehead's philosophy to make such a reading of the quote. Whitehead's work shows a high degree of coherence in terms of content.

In *Principia Mathematica* Whitehead and Russell introduced a specific notation of the theory of classes (sets) and relations (connections between elements of classes). Establishing the importance of relations between elements of logical or mathematical structures was a fundamental step in his metaphysical conception, in which processes and their development through processes rather than dualistic Cartesian ontology (*res cogitans*, *res extensa*) play a central role. (In simple terms, Whitehead interprets processes as the fundamental ontological entity and as the driving force of development). Thus, according to Whitehead, a lively relation between students and teachers is an expression of life in general.

In addition to this programmatic statement, the preface to *The Aims of Education* contains a second sentence that can be read as Whitehead's mission statement as an academic teacher and an educator. As he puts it, "The whole book is a protest against dead knowledge, that is to say, against inert ideas" (Whitehead, 1929, p. v)

Dead knowledge and inert ideas are the antithesis of processes and a lively development, one core not only of Whitehead's philosophy, but also of his professional biography. Twice in his academic life he felt trapped in a backward-looking, structure-bound academic environment. From Cambridge (as described above) he moved to London in 1910. There, he held academic positions in the field of (applied) mathematics and increasingly took on important functions in academic self-administration (Dean of the Faculty of Science at the University of London, member of the University of London's Senate, and Chairman of the Senate's Academic Council). Thus, he was able to promote reforms, but he was also increasingly integrated into existing viscous academic structures and had less and less time for scientific activities. In order to concentrate more fully on philosophy, he accepted the offer from Harvard University to join the faculty as a professor of philosophy. The already 63-year-old Whitehead moved with his family to the United States.

At Harvard, he brought with him the weight of a long and accomplished academic life. It became the foundation for his following major philosophical publications from 1924 on: *Science and the Modern World* (1925), *Process and Reality* (1929), *Adventures of Ideas* (1933), and *Modes of Thought* (1938).

With his concept of process philosophy, Whitehead offers an alternative interpretation to both Cartesian ontology and, for example, the Heideggerian approach of a question-oriented phenomenology and ontology. What Whitehead and Heidegger share can be described as a linguistic struggle for a precise verbal description of complex (ontological) relations. Thus, both use a peculiar, creative language with semantically charged words (e.g., the term 'entity'). That makes Whitehead's major works quite challenging to read. It usually takes several attempts and a comprehensive examination of his concepts to fully understand his thoughts and argumentation. In Blasius's (1997) words, "It must be admitted that much of Whitehead's philosophy is complicated and is in fact quite difficult" (p. 303).

But this is certainly not the case in his essays on education collected in his 1929 book *The Aims of Education and Other Essays*. Most of the essays and addresses were intended for a wider audience, such as teachers, academics, and people working in education. To completely understand the ideas discussed in the book in their full scope, a knowledge of the philosophical work may be helpful. But it is certainly not necessary to understand the primary concern as well as the argumentation and the essential connections.

What characterises Whitehead is his 'mathematical' writing style. For instance, he defines education as "the acquisition of the art of the utilisation of knowledge" (Whitehead, 1929, p. 4). In the following paragraphs, he then unfolds, explains, and further develops his understanding of this definition (or rather characterization) of education. Each of the essays can be read coherently and is characterised by a clear thread of argumentation.

I suppose that the very specific date of publication, 1929, is one major reason for the relatively limited response to this book. *The Aims of Education* was published parallel to Whitehead's main work *Process and Reality*, which is, like his other major philosophical books, quite difficult to read. So, the author's name and the reception of his thoughts as being challenging probably led to a similar assessment of his book on education. This is all the more unfortunate given that

some of the concepts developed and discussed in the articles of *The Aims of Education* were far ahead of their time and only found their way into educational science discourse much later. To name some of the ideas and concepts, a thorough reading shows that Whitehead discusses a well elaborated, culturally embedded notion of stage concept (Chapter II, Chapter III), self-similarity (Chapter II, p. 19, p. 27), education as a process (Chapters I, II III, and VIII), and also of the importance of creativity (Chapters I, II, and VII), curriculum design (Chapters I-III, Chapters IV-VI), fundamental ideas (Chapter I, p. 10), learning-process-centred approaches to the tension between freedom and discipline (Chapter III), and the importance of mental constructions (Chapters II, III, and VIII). Well known learning theorists developed these concepts some decades later; Bandura since the 1940s, Bruner from the late 1950s on, and Piaget, especially in the 1960s, to name some of them.

Whitehead's reputation as a difficult author to read may have been one reason why this book was and is not more widely received in the field of education. Another reason may be that, in contrast to his mathematical and philosophical subject areas, he did not leave behind his thoughts on education in a coherent text. *The Aims of Education* is a collection of essays and addresses, as Whitehead states: "The separate chapters have ... been delivered as addresses at various conferences of educational bodies and of scientific societies" (Whitehead, 1929, p. v). His main thoughts are discussed in the first three chapters, "The Aims of Education," "The Rhythm of Education," and "The Rhythmic Claims of Freedom and Discipline." They do not all contradict each other, but were written at different times for different specific purposes. Therefore, one has to reconstruct the "big picture" from the individual chapters based upon cross-references in terms of content. The individual chapters do provide an easily understandable presentation of the respective ideas. At the same time, however, one reading does not seem to be enough to fully grasp the connections between the chapters, especially with regard to the underlying overall ideas. For instance, Whitehead develops a concrete idea of the necessary basic design of a curriculum, in which he considers developmental psychology, content, and didactic aspects in relation to the entire educational programme and the course of education. The ideas are spread over Chapters I, II, and III and contextualised in Chapters I and VIII with some specific parts on subjects being elaborated on in Chapters IV, V, and VI. The task for the reader is, therefore, to collect and collate the various parts of the concept from the different chapters to obtain an overall picture and understanding.

Assuming that Whitehead compiled the book himself, the following logic of the sequence of chapters can be surmised: as is often the case in his approach, he begins with practical questions, builds on experience and findings, suggests models and concepts, and becomes increasingly generalising and abstract. This becomes clear if we compare the first chapter, an address to non-specialists on the aims of education, with the last, which is closely linked to his philosophy of process.

Furthermore, we can identify a subdivision consisting of chapters that are rather closely related to each other. Chapters I to III provide a coherent general introduction to his ideas and concepts. The following chapters, IV to VII, focus on specific fields and the institutions of formal education. He starts here with a study of his recently completed area, reflecting his time in London at the College of Science and Technology and his role in the Faculty of Science at the University of London (Chapter IV, "Technical Education and Its Relation to Science and

Literature”), which is significant as regards the compilation of the book in 1929. The next three chapters follow Whitehead’s own educational and professional path, from a classics-oriented school education (Chapter V, “The Place of Classics in Education”) to the study mathematics at university (Chapter VI, “The Mathematical Curriculum”), to his own scientific work as a researcher and teacher at universities (Chapter VII, “Universities and their Functions”). Chapters VIII to X then focus on thinking and thoughts in general, the (exemplary) structure of scientific ideas, and the very general philosophical question of how all this is related to the universe.

In the following, I will provide an overview, accompanied by additional explanatory notes, in order to illuminate Whitehead’s philosophy of education. I divide the discussion into three sections, following the layout described above (i.e., Chapters I-III in section 1, Chapters IV-VII in section 2, and Chapters VIII-X in section 3).

The Aims of Education

1. Chapters I – III: Aims, Rhythm, and Rhythmic Claims

1.1. Chapter I – “The Aims of Education”

In this chapter, Whitehead discusses his basic concept of education and learning. His position can be interpreted as a somewhat updated version of Humboldt’s concept of *Bildung* (cf. Bacher, 2024), although he does not explicitly mention Humboldt’s name:

What we should aim at producing is men who possess both culture and expert knowledge in some special direction. Their expert knowledge will give them the ground to start from, and their culture will lead them as deep as philosophy and as high as art. We have to remember that the valuable intellectual development is self-development.... (Whitehead, 1929, p. 1)

Whitehead advocates for a transformative approach in education that prioritizes the cultivation of knowledge through both practical application and specialized study. He criticizes the (at that time) reigning focus on inert ideas—concepts taught without context or application—which led to a lack of engagement and understanding among students.

Based upon this stance, he then argues for the importance of integrating theoretical ideas with their practical uses within the curriculum, in order to maintain the vitality of knowledge. This approach requires considering the unique capabilities of the teacher, the nature of the students, and the specific opportunities provided by the school’s environment.

As the quote shows, Whitehead frames education as a process of self-development with crucial periods. The role of early education is also emphasized as foundational. The overall aim of education should be to produce individuals who are culturally aware and possess expert knowledge in a particular field.

With regard to the organization of learning at schools and universities, Whitehead strongly criticizes uniform external examinations, which fail to account for the individual needs of

schools and students, and instead advocates that schools develop their own curricula based on their specific circumstances. The author calls for educational reform that views the school as the central unit of change, with a curriculum that has been evolved by its own staff and tailored to its needs.

For readers familiar with his process philosophy, Whitehead's ontological approach shines through. The text is driven by his concepts of activity, creativity, and relational development. Surprisingly, in this context he comes to similar conclusions as do reform pedagogues such as Maria Montessori (stressing the importance of teachable moments and the here and now):

The mind is never passive; it is a perpetual activity, delicate, receptive, responsive to stimulus. You cannot postpone its life until you have sharpened it. Whatever interest attaches to your subject-matter must be evoked here and now; whatever powers you are strengthening in the pupil, must be exercised here and now; whatever possibilities of mental life your teaching should impart, must be exhibited here and now. That is the golden rule of education, and a very difficult rule to follow. (Whitehead, 1929, p. 9)

Furthermore (and without going into further detail), Whitehead stresses the importance of beauty and aesthetics in education.

1.2. Chapter II – “The Rhythm of Education”

Whitehead's rhythmic concept of education describes what later became popular as the idea of the stage concept in developmental psychology and educational science (cf. Bruner, 1960; Piaget, 1971; Havighurst, 1972; Bandura, 1977):

The principle is merely this—that different subjects and modes of study should be undertaken by pupils at fitting times when they have reached the proper stage of mental development. (Whitehead, 1929, p. 24)

Thus, he emphasizes the importance of aligning educational content and methods with the natural developmental stages of a student's mental growth. Whitehead criticizes the traditional linear progression of subjects without considering the psychological readiness of students and suggests that education should follow a rhythmic cycle consisting of three stages: romance, precision, and generalization.

1. ***The Stage of Romance***: this stage is characterized by a child's initial excitement about and engagement with new knowledge, where facts and ideas are encountered with a sense of wonder and novelty. In an adequate didactic environment, this stage is characterized by a vividness of new knowledge and an exploration of its unexplored connections and possibilities. This stage is not dominated by systematic procedure, but by immediate cognizance of fact.
2. ***The Stage of Precision***: here, the focus shifts to exactness and detailed understanding. It involves systematic analysis and the addition of new knowledge that fits into this analysis. This stage is akin to learning the grammar of a language

or science, where students are expected to understand and apply a given way of analysing facts.

3. ***The Stage of Generalisation***: in this final stage the knowledge and skills acquired in the precision stage are synthesized and applied to broader concepts. It is a return to the romance stage, but with the added advantage of classified ideas and relevant techniques. This stage involves the application of principles to concrete detail and is essential for both theoretical interest and practical application, both in complex and in real-world situations.

The document emphasizes that these stages should not be seen as sharply distinct but rather as involving an alternation of dominance, with each stage present throughout the learning process:

Education should consist in a continual repetition of such cycles. Each lesson in its minor way should form an eddy cycle issuing in its own subordinate process. Longer periods should issue in definite attainments, which then form the starting-grounds for fresh cycles. (Whitehead, 1929, p. 30)

Whitehead, thus, not only anticipates Bruner's spiral concept (Bruner, 1960), but was also far ahead of his time. To the best of my knowledge, he was the first to formulate not only the cyclic but also the self-similar structure (Abbott, 2001) of learning processes (Kraler & Schratz, 2012). He describes this as "the rhythmic character of growth" (Whitehead, 1929, p. 43), and also draws conclusions for didactics:

We should banish the idea of a mythical, far-off end of education. The pupils must be continually enjoying some fruition and starting afresh—if the teacher is stimulating in exact proportion to his success in satisfying the rhythmic cravings of his pupils. (Whitehead, 1929, pp. 30-31)

The educational approach should adapt to the stage of the rhythm that the pupils have reached, ensuring that the curriculum is aligned with the natural mental development of the students. Whitehead also stresses that the true goal of education is not merely the accumulation of knowledge but more the cultivation of mental power and the ability to apply principles to new situations. He advocates for a harmonious educational approach that respects the natural rhythms of mental development and prepares students for life's complexities.

1.3. Chapter III – "The Rhythmic Claims of Freedom and Discipline"

In this chapter, Whitehead shifts the perspective of his analysis onto demands resulting from the previous chapter and further explores consequences. As the title indicates, Whitehead is aware of the well-known tension between self-directed freedom and a compulsory curriculum in formal education. He does not explicitly mention Kant in this book (but had a very profound knowledge of his philosophy; cf. Whitehead, 1948, p. 10), and his philosophical position differs from that developed in Kant's concepts (especially on causality; see Whitehead, 1927). But their basic approach to education is very similar. The title of Chapter III of Whitehead's book may indirectly refer to Kant's famous quote from his writings on pedagogy:

One of the greatest problems of education is how to unite submission to the necessary, restraint with the child's capability of constraint exercising his freewill—for restraint is necessary. (Kant, 1900, p. 27)

Whitehead might be thinking of this quote in connection with the title of the Chapter. Kant's and Whitehead's basic approaches to education are surprisingly similar. Whitehead argues, "The only avenue towards wisdom is by freedom in the presence of knowledge. But the only avenue towards knowledge is by discipline in the acquirement of ordered fact. Freedom and discipline are the two essentials of education" (Whitehead, 1929, p. 30). We can compare this with Kant's words, "Man can only become man by education. He is merely what education makes of him" (Kant, 1900, p. 6).

While being aware of the problem of translation, one can argue that even their writing styles seem similar to some extent. In fact, the following argument from Kant more or less covers Whitehead's position:

[T]he greatest and most difficult problem to which man can devote himself is the problem of education. For insight depends on education, and education in its turn depends on insight. It follows therefore that education can only advance by slow degrees, and true conception of the method of education can only arise when one generation transmits to the next its stores of experience and knowledge, each generation adding something of its own before transmitting them to the following. (Kant, 1900, p. 11)

Culture, reason, discipline, development, and freedom (though on the latter they have different positions) are pivotal aspects of education for both of them. They build their argumentation on similar fundamental terms. But Whitehead developed his position just over 100 years later than Kant did. Additionally, Kant focussed more on the external moment of constraint, whereas Whitehead took free development as the initial momentum for individual and collective cultural development.

In his chapter on rhythmic freedom and discipline, Whitehead revisits his stage concept from an administrative and didactic perspective. He criticises traditional education systems for focusing excessively on the accumulation of text-book knowledge, a practice which stifles intellectual curiosity and initiative. Instead, he advocates for a balanced approach that aligns with the natural developmental rhythm of the human mind, consisting of the three stages described above.

Whitehead—like Kant—underscores the importance of self-discipline, guided freedom, and the active utilization of knowledge to cultivate wisdom. He warns against rigid, overly disciplined methods that dull the mind and hinder progress. Education should nurture the whole personality, including its aesthetic and emotional dimensions, to achieve a harmonious development of intellect and character.

Ultimately, Whitehead calls for an education system that begins and ends with freedom, with discipline as a necessary but subordinate phase, ensuring a dynamic and fulfilling learning experience for students. For Whitehead, freedom and discipline are not antagonistic but

complementary. Freedom fosters curiosity and engagement, while discipline ensures the structured acquisition of knowledge. Both must be harmonized to align with the natural growth of the learner's personality.

Most discussions of Whitehead's educational concepts focus solely on the first three chapters, which lay the foundation for his ideas. However, if you want to understand his approach in contextual terms—and learning and education are always contextualised—attention to the chapters following the first three is essential.

2. Chapters IV – VII: Technical Education, Classics, Curricula, Universities and Beyond

In Chapters IV-VII, Whitehead discusses specific areas of education and learning, and finally extends the analysis by incorporating fundamental considerations of his process philosophy.

2.1. Chapter IV – “Technical Education and Its Relation to Science and Literature”

Throughout his academic career in Cambridge and London, Whitehead taught applied mathematics and supported the curricular development of technical sciences in various positions, believing in the need for a balance between theoretical and practical education. Consequently, Chapter IV explores the nature of technical education and its relationship to science and literature. Whitehead emphasizes once more the need for a balanced and integrated approach to education. He critiques the traditional Platonic ideal of liberal education, which prioritizes intellectual and aesthetic appreciation through the study of literature, art, and philosophy. While acknowledging the contributions of this model to European civilization, such as fostering curiosity and maintaining intellectual dignity, the text argues that it neglects practical and technical skills that are essential for modern life. This demonstrates Whitehead's differentiated reception of fundamental (philosophical) texts, which is always based on a detailed knowledge of the respective authors (like Kant, the British philosophers, and the Greek classics, especially the Pre-Socratic philosophers, and Plato and Aristotle)

On the other hand, Whitehead also discusses the limitations of both liberal and technical education when pursued in isolation. Liberal education, focused on literary and intellectual pursuits, often fails to address the practical needs of society, while technical education, if overly specialized, risks producing narrow-minded individuals lacking intellectual breadth and adaptability. Instead, he advocates for an educational model that combines the strengths of both approaches, ensuring students acquire both theoretical knowledge and practical skills. This integration fosters intellectual vision, creativity, and the ability to apply general principles to specific problems, as presented in Chapters II and III.

Whitehead describes in detail technical education as much more than manual training; it involves a creative process that combines thought and action. It emphasizes the coordination of hand, eye, and mind, enabling students to connect theory with practice:

A technical education is in the main a training in the art of utilising knowledge for the manufacture of material products. Such a training emphasises manual skill, and the co-ordinated action of hand and eye, and judgment in the control of the process of

construction. But judgment necessitates knowledge of those natural processes of which the manufacture is the utilisation. Thus, somewhere in technical training an education in scientific knowledge is required. (Whitehead, 1929, p. 77)

Whitehead criticizes the overemphasis on specialization in education, advocating for a broader approach that highlights general principles and their application across disciplines. He also underscores the role of art and literature in providing intellectual and emotional stimulation, both of which are essential for a healthy and productive life.

The antithesis between a technical and a liberal education is fallacious. There can be no adequate technical education which is not liberal, and no liberal education which is not technical: that is, no education which does not impart both technique and intellectual vision. In simpler language, education should turn out the pupil with something he knows well and something he can do well. This intimate union of practice and theory aids both. The intellect does not work best in a vacuum. (Whitehead, 1929, p. 74)

As his argument shows, Whitehead calls for a better integration of practical-technical and theoretical-artistic content not only for practical or pedagogical reasons. Rather, he assumes that both are constitutively dependent on each other and represent basic anthropological constants of human beings.

2.2. Chapter V – “The Place of Classics in Education”

Whitehead lived in a time of fundamental change, socially (world wars, change of the imperial age, etc.), scientifically (developments in the natural sciences and elsewhere) and technically (communication systems, mobility possibilities, and so on). His own education had been traditional:

On the intellectual side, my education ... conformed to the normal standard of the time. Latin began at the age of ten years, and Greek at twelve. Holidays excepted, my recollection is that daily, up to the age of nineteen and a half years, some pages of Latin and Greek authors were construed, and their grammar examined. Before going to school pages of rules of Latin grammar could be repeated, all in Latin, and exemplified by quotations. The classical studies were interspersed with mathematics. Of course, such studies included history—namely, Herodotus, Xenophon, Thucydides, Sallust, Livy, and Tacitus. I can still feel the dullness of Xenophon, Sallust, and Livy. Of course, we all know that they are great authors; but this is a candid autobiography.

The others were enjoyable. Indeed my recollection is that the classics were well taught, with an unconscious comparison of the older civilization with modern life. I was excused in the composition of Latin Verse and the reading of some Latin poetry, in order to give more time for mathematics. (Whitehead, 1948, p. 9)

Due to fundamental changes in social conditions as well as scientific and technological advances, Whitehead realized that the traditional education system had to change in terms of both content and didactics. But similar to his argument about the practical and theoretical aspects of knowledge, he argued for both as two necessary sides of the same coin. One cannot be fully developed without the other.

In this Chapter, he discusses—well informed by his own course of education—the historical and contemporary significance of classical studies, during his time particularly of Latin and Greek, in shaping intellectual and cultural development. He emphasizes that the future of classics in education is not solely dependent on the joy they bring to scholars or their utility for academic pursuits, but on their broader relevance to modern education and society.

Whitehead acknowledges and argues that the long era of dominance of the classics in higher education, where they once reigned unchallenged alongside mathematics, has passed, as modern disciplines of widespread interest and practical application have emerged:

There are now other disciplines each involving topics of wide-spread interest, with complex relationships, and exhibiting in their development the noblest feats of genius in its stretch of imagination and its philosophic intuition. Almost every walk of life is now a learned profession, and demands one or more of these disciplines as the substratum for its technical skill. (Whitehead, 1929, p. 61)

At the same time, Whitehead holds the classics in high regard, viewing them as a unique pathway to intellectual development through their insights into logic, philosophy, history, and aesthetics. He viewed the study of Latin and Greek as a means to cultivate analytical thinking, linguistic precision, and an appreciation of literary beauty. Moreover, he describes the process of translation as a rigorous exercise in thought analysis, fostering clarity and depth of understanding.

These fundamental qualities of classical languages face practical challenges that Whitehead was familiar with from his functions:

We must remember that the whole problem of intellectual education is controlled by lack of time. If Methuselah was not a well-educated man, it was his own fault or that of his teachers. But our task is to deal with five years of secondary school-life. Classics can only be defended on the ground that within that period, and sharing that period with other subjects, it can produce a necessary enrichment of intellectual character more quickly than any alternative discipline directed to the same object. (Whitehead, 1929, p. 96)

He therefore advocated for a balanced approach, combining the study of original texts with translation, to ensure accessibility while preserving the richness of the original language. This method should allow students to grasp the broader vision of Rome and Greece, their contributions to European civilization, and their influence on modern thought. So, his curricular goal would be to ensure that classics remain relevant by demonstrating their value in fostering

intellectual character and cultural understanding within the limited timeframe of modern education.

To sum it up, Whitehead argues that critical thinking, cultural awareness, and intellectual enrichment largely benefit from classical studies.

2.3. Chapter VI – “The Mathematical Curriculum”

Whitehead had studied mathematics at Cambridge and lectured in the subject (pure and applied mathematics) from at least 1885 (Whitehead, 1948, pp. 10-11) until 1924, when he joined the faculty of Harvard University in the Department of Philosophy. His strong commitment to modernising the teaching of mathematics should therefore come as no surprise.

In this chapter, Whitehead discusses the purpose of mathematics education, emphasizing its role in fostering logical reasoning, abstract thinking, and practical application. He criticizes traditional approaches to teaching mathematics, which often focus on rote memorization of theorems and formulae, and advocates for a reform of the curriculum to prioritize understanding fundamental ideas and their relevance to modern thought:

in education we proceed from the particular to the general. Accordingly, children should be taught the use of [mathematical] ideas by practice among simple examples. My point is this: the goal should be, not an aimless accumulation of special mathematical theorems, but the final recognition that the preceding years of work have illustrated those relations of number, and of quantity, and of space, which are of fundamental importance. (Whitehead, 1929, p. 121)

Whitehead thus anticipates Bruner’s concept of fundamental ideas (basic ideas/fundamental structures) as the cornerstone of curriculum design and didactics. In his ground-breaking *The Process of Education* (1960), Bruner writes,

Students ... have a limited exposure to the materials they are to learn. How can this exposure be made to count in their thinking for the rest of their lives? The dominant view among men who have been engaged in preparing and teaching new curricula is that the answer to this question lies in giving students an understanding of the fundamental structures of whatever subjects we choose to teach. This is a minimum requirement for using knowledge, for bringing it to bear on problems and events one encounters outside a classroom....

[T]he basic ideas that lie at the heart of all science and mathematics and the basic themes that give form to life and literature are as simple as they are powerful. To be in command of these basic ideas, to use them effectively, requires a continual deepening of one’s understanding of them that comes from learning to use them in progressively more complex forms. (pp. 11-13)

To the best of my knowledge, Bruner never quotes Whitehead. Therefore, the similarity in their arguments may come from the logical consequence of their deep knowledge of the educational system and necessary reforms.

In this chapter, Whitehead highlights the importance of using practical examples and applications to illustrate mathematical ideas. He also criticizes the overemphasis on specialized topics, such as the addition formulae in trigonometry or the detailed study of conic sections, which are deemed unnecessary for general education. Instead, the curriculum should focus on topics that illuminate broader ideas. And ultimately, the chapter calls for a shift in mathematics education to align with the intellectual needs of the modern era. It advocates for a curriculum that balances logical rigor with accessibility, ensuring that students not only acquire technical skills but also develop the capacity to think abstractly and apply mathematical reasoning to diverse fields. It was not until the mid-1990s that these ideas began to be widely discussed in mathematics education. This was particularly the case in Germany (Heymann, 2003).

2.4. Chapter VII – “Universities and Their Function”

Whitehead spent his entire professional life in universities. Critical, concerned with the social responsibility and further development of these institutions, he became aware of the possibilities and limitations of universities in his various academic functions and as a researcher. At Cambridge, he criticized the refusal to admit women to the university. In London, he was concerned with the valorisation of applied sciences. Finally, at Harvard, he was involved in adapting the structure and content of the institution to the demands of a modern, rapidly changing society.

So, in Chapter VII, Whitehead explores the evolving role and function of universities in modern society, emphasizing their critical importance in fostering intellectual and imaginative growth. He argues for the justification of universities in the following way:

The justification for a university is that it preserves the connection between knowledge and the zest of life, by uniting the young and the old in the imaginative consideration of learning. The university imparts information, but it imparts it imaginatively. At least, this is the function which it should perform for society. A university which fails in this respect has no reason for existence....

Imagination is not to be divorced from the facts: it is a way of illuminating the facts. It works by eliciting the general principles which apply to the facts, as they exist, and then by an intellectual survey of alternative possibilities which are consistent with those principles. It enables men to construct an intellectual vision of a new world. (Whitehead, 1929, p. 139)

Whitehead highlights the rapid expansion of universities globally during his time. However, he warns that this growth, if not guided by a clear understanding of the primary functions of universities, risks undermining their usefulness. Whitehead identifies the integration of imagination and experience as a key theme of modern universities. Universities are tasked with nurturing imagination during youth, free from the immediate responsibilities of action, while also

fostering disciplined thought. This balance is essential for preparing individuals for their later life.

In London Whitehead supported the then new colleges of science and technology. Ten years later, at Harvard, he discussed the role of business schools as a modern addition to universities, reflecting the intellectualization of business as a vocation. He describes these schools as examples of how universities can adapt to societal needs while maintaining their core mission of imaginative education.

Whitehead lived at a time of profound economic and social change as well as transformation. During his lifetime, the foundations were laid for today's ubiquitous quantification in all areas of life. He was well aware of this transformation. Universities, particularly in the US, were beginning to measure their scientific output.

Whitehead defined universities the following way: "The universities are schools of education, and schools of research" (Whitehead, 1929, p. 92). He saw the two as fundamentally and existentially intertwined. One cannot function successfully without the other. His thoughts, written down 100 years ago, seem more relevant than ever in the current debate on the ranking-oriented, purely quantitative contemporary assessments of universities worldwide.²⁸ Since he was a mathematician, Whitehead did not argue against quantitative measures. But his final goal was always qualitative, substantial development. What he says seems so clear and central that I would like to quote it in full below:

It must not be supposed that the output of a university in the form of original ideas is solely to be measured by printed papers and books labeled with the names of their authors. Mankind is as individual in its mode of output as in the substance of its thoughts. For some of the most fertile minds composition in writing, or in a form reducible to writing, seems to be an impossibility. In every faculty you will find that some of the more brilliant teachers are not among those who publish. Their originality requires for its expression direct intercourse with their pupils in the form of lectures, or of personal discussion. Such men exercise an immense influence; and yet, after the generation of their pupils has passed away, they sleep among the innumerable unthanked benefactors of humanity. Fortunately, one of them is immortal—Socrates.

Thus it would be the greatest mistake to estimate the value of each member of a faculty by the printed work signed with his name. There is at the present day some tendency to fall into this error; and an emphatic protest is necessary against an attitude on the part of authorities which is damaging to efficiency and unjust to unselfish zeal.

But, when all such allowances have been made, one good test for the general efficiency of a faculty is that as a whole it shall be producing in published form its

²⁸ See for example "World University Rankings 2025" at <https://www.timeshighereducation.com/world-university-rankings/latest/world-ranking>.

quota of contributions of thought. Such a quota is to be estimated in weight of thought, and not in number of words. (Whitehead 1929, pp. 148-149).

In summary, Whitehead stresses the importance of faculty as imaginative scholars who inspire students. He criticizes the (then nascent) tendency to measure the value of teaching by published work alone, and emphasizes the irreplaceable impact of direct interaction and intellectual stimulation.

Ultimately, the chapter asserts that universities are vital for societal progress, serving as hubs where the adventure of thought meets the adventure of action. Their success depends on fostering a culture of imagination, collaboration, and intellectual freedom, ensuring their relevance in an ever-changing world.

3. Chapters VIII – X

3.1. Chapter VIII – “The Organisation of Thought”

Chapters I (“The Aims of Education”) and VIII (“The Organisation of Thought”) were among the earliest chapters of the book to be published or presented as addresses, both dating back to 1916 (see Whitehead, 1917, p. vii). Whitehead was 55 years old at the time, had the experience of almost a complete professional lifetime of research and teaching in mathematics behind him, and was already putting together, without publication, his fundamental thoughts on process philosophy. So, Chapter VIII seems to be about ‘putting things together.’ Whitehead specifically explores the intricate relationship between logic, science, and the structuring of human understanding. He emphasizes that organized thought is the foundation of organized action—which is what human beings in an organized society need to have flourish—and that science represents a specific type of thought organization aimed at understanding and explaining the universe:

It is no accident that an age of science has developed into an age of organisation. Organised thought is the basis of organised action. Organisation is the adjustment of diverse elements so that their mutual relations may exhibit some predetermined quality. (Whitehead, 1929, p. 153)

Whitehead also highlights the dual origins of science: the practical source, which seeks to direct actions toward achieving specific goals, and the theoretical source, which arises from the desire to understand the underlying principles of phenomena. Both aspects must, therefore, be present in universities, subject-wise, both in the area of research (theoretical and applied sciences) and in the area of teaching (content and didactics).

The chapter delves into the inductive nature of modern science (Bacon, Mill), because “Science is the organisation of thought” (Whitehead, 1929, p. 103). In line with his philosophical approach, Whitehead interprets science as a process;

Success [in science] is never absolute, and progress in the right direction is the result of a slow, gradual process of continual comparison of ideas with facts. (Whitehead, 1929, pp. 156-157)

For Whitehead, induction, combined with deductive reasoning, forms the backbone of scientific inquiry, as both are essential for deriving meaningful knowledge. The text critiques the historical stagnation of logic, attributing it to an over-reliance on authority and a lack of innovation, which hindered its progress for centuries.

A significant portion of the chapter is devoted to the structure of logical theory, which he divides into four sections: the arithmetic stage, the algebraic stage, the general-function theory stage, and the analytic stage. These stages reflect the progression of thought from simple propositions to complex logical constructions, mirroring the development of mathematical concepts like numbers, functions, and correlations.

Whitehead also addresses the challenges of aligning abstract scientific concepts with the messy, fragmented nature of human experience. He argues that science begins with common-sense thought and experience and then refines and reorganizes it to create precise, interconnected ideas. This process involves both observation and imagination, as well as the formulation of idealized concepts (Whitehead, 1929, p. 159-ff.).

Whitehead finally interprets science as a continuous process of comparing ideas with facts, aiming to construct a coherent understanding of the universe. He states, “Science is a permanent record of premises, deductions, and conclusions, verified all along the line by its correspondence with facts” (Whitehead, 1929, p. 162). Therefore, it calls for a balance between theoretical exploration and practical application, emphasizing that neither can progress without the other.

3.2. Chapter IX – “The Anatomy of Some Scientific Ideas”

Chapter IX contains the longest text in the book. It differs in structure and organisation from the other chapters, containing five parts: I. Facts, II. Objects, III. Time and Space, IV. Fields of Force and V. Conclusion. Here Whitehead explores the foundational principles and methodologies underlying scientific thought and perception. He emphasizes the distinction between physical science and other domains of thought, such as metaphysics and value judgments, which are excluded from scientific inquiry to maintain objectivity and practicality. Focusing on Whitehead’s reflections on education, I will leave this chapter aside, as it mainly delves into metaphysics, ontology, and aspects of Whitehead’s process philosophy.

3.3. Chapter X – “Space, Time, and Relativity”

For an experienced reader of Whitehead, nothing unusual happens in the final chapter. The initial questions, observations, analyses, and conceptualisations begin with a practical and experiential approach. The situation is similar with to that found in “The Aims of Education.” As the pages and chapters progress, the discussion becomes more theoretical, abstract, and philosophical. Eventually, one ends up with very fundamental metaphysical and ontological discussions. This is also the case here.

Whereas in the previous chapter Whitehead argued from the point of view of the physical sciences, here he explores the intricate relationships between space, time, and relativity, examining these concepts from various scientific, philosophical, and psychological perspectives, finally concentrating on ontological and metaphysical aspects of his process philosophy. Educational questions seem to be very far away from this discussion. He ends his analysis with some very relevant remarks in relation to the context of education:

I emphasise the point that our only exact data as to the physical world are our sensible perceptions. We must not slip into the fallacy of assuming that we are comparing a given world with given perceptions of it. The physical world is, in some general sense of the term, a deduced concept. (Whitehead, 1929, p. 247)

In particular, this means that we cannot do without normative concepts in education. A purely empirical approach to education would fall short. Education starts with people and has people as its end. Generalized, as Whitehead always strives to do, this means that “[o]ur problem is ... to fit the world to our perceptions, and not our perceptions to the world” (Whitehead, 1929, p. 165).

Culture is part of us, as is education. We create culture and education. But Whitehead is no radical constructivist. He much more generalizes the pre-Socratic, primarily cosmological reference of philosophy. For him, nature and the world contain all phenomena, let it be in natural sciences, humanities, the outside world, consciousness etc. His approach is—as we have seen—integrative and holistic.

Conclusion

Alfred North Whitehead was a thorough and comprehensive thinker. He was what we would now call competent on a number of levels.

First, as a scientist and researcher as well as being a mathematician and logician, he made fundamental contributions to the further development of these disciplines in the 20th century. The same is true of his work in the field of philosophy, in particular in ontology and metaphysics (process philosophy).

Secondly, as a (university) teacher, he was well aware of the different needs of different groups of students, whether mathematicians or engineering students, math and physics teacher students, etc. His concepts, ideals and didactic demands as discussed in this paper were the result of a profound knowledge of teaching practice. And, as far as we know, he was very successful in this way. Whitehead’s first publication after *Principia Mathematica* (1910) was, for instance, his *An Introduction to Mathematics* in 1911. The book “was published in the series ‘The Home University Library of Modern Knowledge,’ which published concise introductions on a broad range of topics for a general audience” (Hales, 2024, p. 83). Hales compares its scope to Roger Penrose’s successful approach to making fundamental aspects of mathematics and physics more popular and understandable to a wider audience.

Using the teaching of mathematics as a blueprint for teaching in general, Whitehead gives an explanation for and an analysis of the phenomenon of why this area of study often fails to be sustainable and attractive by referring to the concept of fundamental ideas that Bruner (1960) broadly popularized in education 50 years later:

The reason for this failure of the science to live up to its reputation is that its fundamental ideas are not explained to the student disentangled from the technical procedure which has been invented to facilitate their exact presentation in particular instances. Accordingly, the unfortunate learner finds himself struggling to acquire a knowledge of a mass of details which are not illuminated by any general conception. (Whitehead, 1911, p. 8)

Thirdly, during his long academic career, he held a number of academic and administrative positions in which he sought to contribute actively to the reform and development of teaching:

During the later years ... I was Dean of the Faculty of Science in the University, Chairman of the Academic Council which manages the internal affairs concerned with London education, and a member of the Senate. I was also Chairman of the Council which managed The Goldsmith's College, and a member of the Council of the Borough Polytechnic. There were endless other committees involved in these positions. In fact, participation in the supervision of London education, University and Technological, joined to the teaching duties of my professorship at the Imperial College constituted a busy life. (Whitehead, 1948, p. 13)

This threefold professional biographical approach (research, teaching, administration) was the basis for his modelling and conceptualisation of education as well as for his well-founded criticism of existing conditions and his proposals for further development and improvement.

Ultimately, Whitehead's pedagogical considerations are permeated by the concepts of his process philosophy. The seeds of this may lie in his preoccupation with the logical foundations of mathematics, where he saw relations as a fundamental principle. Aware of the profound social changes and developments of the late 19th and early 20th centuries, he was convinced of the need for development in all areas of life. Whitehead saw science and learning as positive means of addressing social, technological, and economic challenges. He believed in the positive contribution of science to solving human problems and challenges, but was not naïve in this respect, as he assumed a specific, responsible scientific way of thinking and acting within science. In terms of his (professional) biography and his achievements and positions, Whitehead is a person of high integrity and authenticity. First, he observed and experienced, then he drew preliminary conclusions, took part in processes, and finally arrived at profound positions. This was usually the starting point for the integration of his findings into the constantly evolving concept of his process philosophy—creating a complete integrity such as we rarely find it in one human being.

If we finally try to summarize his basic educational concepts, the following seven aspects are of fundamental importance:

The need for a *process-oriented, relational and holistic approach*: in education, different aspects and actors are intertwined in various different ways. This needs to be manifested in thought and action.

Avoidance of inert ideas: education should not focus on the passive reception of disconnected or unutilized ideas. Such inert ideas are not only useless but also harmful, as they fail to stimulate intellectual growth and creativity. Instead, ideas should be tested, applied, and integrated into fresh combinations to remain alive and relevant.

The *cycles of learning*: education is described as a rhythmic process involving three stages: the “stage of Romance” (initial curiosity and wonder), the “stage of Precision” (discipline and systematic learning), and the “stage of Generalization” (synthesis and broader understanding). These cycles repeat throughout intellectual development, fostering a balance between freedom and discipline.

Theory and practice are constitutively linked to one another.

Integration of knowledge: the curriculum should avoid fragmenting subjects into isolated components, but rather concentrate on fundamental ideas and present knowledge as interconnected and relevant to life, helping students see the woods through the trees. This approach ensures that education reflects the complexity and unity of life.

Freedom and discipline: effective education requires a balance between freedom and discipline. Freedom fosters creativity and curiosity, while discipline ensures focus and precision. Over-disciplinary or rigid structures can dull the mind and stifle intellectual growth, while excessive freedom without structure can lead to aimlessness.

Holistic development of the individual: education should nurture the whole personality, including the intellectual, emotional, and aesthetic dimensions, by fostering a sense of wonder, curiosity, and appreciation for beauty. This ensures a balanced development of character and intellect, enabling students to achieve wisdom and actively apply their knowledge in life. These elements are also essential for intellectual and emotional development, as they inspire deeper engagement with ideas and foster a love for learning.

A well-known standard volume on current learning theories is Knut Illeri’s *Contemporary Theories of Learning: Learning Theorists ... in their Own Words* (Illeris, 2018). When reading individual chapters of this book, one has the impression of recognising many of Whitehead’s ideas. Details and contexts have changed somewhat. But the basic concepts seem timeless. They are as relevant today as they were when they were written.

We are experiencing our time today as a period of transformation. Process-oriented approaches, profound analysis, competencies and knowledge, responsible collaboration, and above all communication appear to be of paramount importance in meeting the environmental, societal, and technological challenges we face. Whitehead was very interested in Wittgenstein’s approach to fundamental questions. But he heavily contradicted early Wittgenstein’s seventh and last proposition of the *Tractatus Logico-Philosophicus* “Whereof one cannot speak, thereof one must be silent” (Wittgenstein, 1922, p. 189). He believed in language:

Philosophy is an attempt to express the infinity of the universe in terms of the limitations of language. (Whitehead, 1948, p. 15)

Whitehead's fundamental approaches and concepts are more relevant today, in a time of change and misinformation, than ever. He is worth reading, especially because "much of Whitehead's philosophy is understandable ... this is especially so of Whitehead's philosophy of education" (Blasius, 1997, p. 303).

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Schools as Ethical Decision-Makers—Educational Ethics at the Meso-Level

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Introduction

Education and ethics are intrinsically intertwined, with the very interpretation of “education” being an inherently ethical endeavor. Our definitions of education are shaped by normative conceptions of what it means to be human—conceptions that, in turn, inform our educational aims and practices (e.g., Dewey, 1909; Jäger, 1934, p. 24; Nida-Rümelin, 2013, p. 21; Pieper, 2017, p. 129). This relationship is particularly evident within formal education, where teaching, learning, and training are organized and carried out within the framework of established educational systems (Rohlf, 2011).

Schools are far more than places for acquiring facts and passing tests. They are dynamic environments that influence and are influenced by cultural, social, political, and ethical considerations (Dewey, 1909, part I). The underlying philosophy of education rests on a fundamental ethical foundation, which profoundly influences and shapes our understanding of the true purpose of schooling. Hence, different perspectives offer distinct views on the role of schools in shaping individuals and society, as illustrated by the following examples.

According to *essentialism* (e.g., William C. Bagley, 1934), schools should focus on teaching essential academic subjects to prepare students for life and citizenship, emphasizing core knowledge and skills. In contrast, *progressivism* (e.g., John Dewey, 1916) advocates hands-on, problem-solving learning environments that foster critical thinking, creativity, and social responsibility. *Perennialism* (e.g., Robert Hutchins, 1952) argues that education should focus on enduring truths and classical works to cultivate intellectual rigor and understanding of fundamental ideas. Meanwhile, *reconstructionism* (e.g., George Counts, 1932) views schools as instruments of social change, urging education to address societal issues and prepare students to contribute to justice and progress. *Existentialism* (inspired by Jean-Paul Sartre, 1946) emphasizes personal freedom and self-creation, encouraging students to explore their identity and meaning in life, while *critical pedagogy* (e.g., Paulo Freire, 1970) seeks to challenge power structures, promote social justice, and empower students through dialogue and active engagement with societal norms. Given their normative perspective on what schools *should* or *ought to* pursue, it is evident that the approaches outlined above are fundamentally ethical in nature.

Education systems involve numerous actors who each bear significant responsibility for their decisions. These decisions are not only administrative or logistical in nature, but often involve

deeply ethical considerations, particularly when it comes to children and adolescents—groups whose life trajectories are profoundly shaped by the choices made within their educational journey (Fend, 2008a, 2008b; Brumlik, 2017). Ethical decisions in the context of formal education span across various levels, from the overarching policies set at the national level to the autonomous choices made within individual schools, and down to the day-to-day decisions made by teachers within the classroom. In every instance, stakeholders are tasked to make judgments that have the potential to impact not only the present but also the future of those in their care.

Historically, in the Western world, the connection between formal education (as well as pedagogy in general) and ethics was considered self-evident, from antiquity through the Middle Ages and into modern times (Horster & Oelkers, 2005, p. 7). However, in the 20th century, this relationship began to fade from the foreground, receiving less attention in educational discourse (Wigger, 1998, p. 193; cited in Prengel, 2020, p. 48). Despite this shift, ethical questions within the educational and schooling context have continued to be explored, albeit in more fragmented ways. However, in the broader philosophical field of applied ethics, educational ethics has often occupied a marginal position, rarely addressed in standard works on the subject, and remaining an almost invisible presence in contemporary discussions.

The present paper seeks to address this gap by focusing on schools as key sites where ethically relevant decisions are routinely made. Drawing on Helmut Fend's systematization of formal education (Fend 2008a, 2008b), which distinguishes three levels of education—macro (education policy), meso (actual schools), and micro (teaching)—the focus is placed on the meso-level: schools. The paper explores how schools function as ethical decision-making bodies and identifies the central ethical themes that arise within these institutions. It begins by conceptualizing the ethical responsibilities across all levels of formal education, from policy to classroom practice. It then delves into the role of schools in shaping and making ethical decisions, exploring which choices are (or can be) made at the institutional level. Finally, the paper outlines the ethical responsibilities of schools and underscores their role in shaping the educational experience in a way that is both ethically grounded and socially responsible.

I. Educational Ethics within the Ethical Framework

Ethics should not be reduced to applied ethics; rather, applied ethics—which includes educational ethics—can only be understood within the broader context of ethics (Turnherr, 2000, p. 7). Ethics can be categorized in various ways, and Figure 1 presents one such classification: the distinction made here between philosophical and non-philosophical ethics is based on differing methodological approaches. While both religious and philosophical ethics share the same tasks and objectives, religious ethics do not rely solely on experience and reason to justify their principles. Instead, they may also draw on supernatural sources of knowledge (Morscher, 2012, pp. 54–55).

Despite this methodological difference, moral theology remains significant in the context of educational ethics. Historically, religious moral concepts have played a crucial role in shaping educational systems and the norms and values embedded within them (e.g., Reble, 2004; Seel, 2010; Tenorth, 2010). Furthermore, although Wilhelm von Humboldt (1792/2016) and other

philosophers advocated for a clear separation between education and religion, this division has yet to be fully realized in many places.

Fig. 1.: Categorization of Ethics and Embedding of Educational Ethics (Bacher, 2025)

Descriptive ethics, on the other hand, focuses on empirical research on norms and value systems, primarily within the social and cultural sciences. While not a philosophical discipline in a strict methodological sense, it can still contribute significantly to philosophical ethics (von Kutscherer, 1999, pp. 42–43) by providing valuable insights and data (Hübner, 2021, p. 24). For example, empirical studies on moral values can inform the development and justification of principles in educational ethics.

As illustrated in Figure 1, philosophical ethics can be divided into three sub-disciplines: (1) metaethics, (2) normative ethics, and (3) applied ethics. These three areas are closely interconnected and build upon one another. Applied ethics applies principles developed within normative ethics, while normative ethics is grounded in metaethics to ensure a consistent justification of its principles. The relations can be expressed as follows:

- (1) Metaethics can be referred to as the theory of science of ethics (Pieper, 2017, p. 73). It serves as the foundation of ethics by seeking to clarify the fundamental

status of moral concepts, statements, and arguments, thereby providing the basis for consistent ethical reasoning. Metaethics explores the justification of ethical statements on ontological, epistemological, and linguistic levels. It analyzes the structure and origins of moral beliefs, aiming to understand what it means to speak of right and wrong, good and bad—without addressing specific moral questions or making normative judgments. (Hübner, 2021, p. 37).

- (2) Normative ethics focuses on evaluating actions in terms of their moral rightness or wrongness and establishing principles that guide moral behavior. It is generally divided into deontic (norm-based) and axiological (value-based) ethics (Morscher, 2012, p. 61). Normative ethics encompasses philosophical theories that establish standards for what ought to be done (Pauer-Studer, 2020, p. 14), as well as what is prohibited, good, or bad. Its primary aim is to formulate well-founded principles for human action and develop approaches for assessing moral dilemmas and decision-making in ethically significant situations.
- (3) Applied ethics (also known as practical ethics) aims to apply principles from normative ethics to concrete issues, providing guidance for decision-making in complex and often controversial areas of human life (Turnherr, 2000, p. 14). According to Morscher (2012), the role of applied ethics is to critically examine various moral positions in light of their theoretical foundations and to establish a consistent, ideally coherent, yet revisable set of moral principles that can serve as a basis for discussion. Classical subfields of applied ethics include medical ethics, business ethics, scientific ethics, and animal ethics. Educational ethics is also part of this domain.

Philosophical ethics provides the ethical framework for multi-perspective reflection and argumentation on education-related ethical issues. However, to identify which themes take center stage, insights from educational sciences are essential. Therefore, the perspective shifts at this point to systematically identifying the key thematic areas of educational ethics.

2. The Thematic Range of (Formal) Educational Education

One effective way to systematize the formal education system is to break it down into different levels, each involving distinct actors who play key roles in shaping the educational landscape (Candia et al. 2023; Fend, 2008a; 2008b; Garira, 2024). This approach provides a solid foundation for structuring educational ethics, as decisions and judgments made at each level often carry significant moral weight (Bacher, 2025). By focusing on the various actors involved at each stage of the educational process, we can better understand how ethics is inherently tied to the decisions being made, bringing us back to the core of ethics itself—the question of what constitutes right and wrong human action.

In this context, I turn to Fend's multi-level model of formal education (Fend, 2008a; 2008b). He divides the education system into three distinct levels: the macro-level (educational policy), the meso-level (the schools), and the micro-level (teaching). Each of these levels is associated with decision-making processes that involve various actors, and at each level, decisions are made that

can have ethical implications for students, teachers, and society at large. This approach serves as a framework for understanding how educational ethics plays a role in guiding these decisions.

Importantly, Fend’s analysis goes beyond simply examining the “is” or “can” states of education (i.e., the current state and potential possibilities of the education system). It also addresses the “should” state—what ought to be the case in terms of moral responsibility. This dimension is at the heart of educational ethics, which is concerned with the values, principles, and ideals that should guide the actions of those involved in the educational process. In other words, it is not only about understanding how education functions or can function, but also about determining how it should function in an ethical, responsible way.

At each level of the system, from policy decisions to classroom practices, different stakeholders—such as policymakers, school administrators, teachers, students, and their caregivers—are involved in making decisions. These decisions, often with profound implications, shape the educational experiences of individuals and influence the broader social and cultural fabric. Therefore, it is essential to recognize the ethical dimensions of decision-making at each of these levels.

Building upon this framework, Figure 2 provides a schematic representation of a categorization of educational ethics, which further illuminates how these different levels intersect and interact in the context of formal education.

Fig. 2: Content-Related Categorization of (Formal) Educational Ethics with Focus on the Meso-Level (Bacher, 2025)

As demonstrated in Figure 2, ethically relevant decisions are made at every level of formal education. At the macro-level, educational policy establishes ethical standards by stipulating the definition of educational goals and content and by shaping the structural design of the educational system. At the meso-level, schools exercise autonomous decision-making that governs the organization of school culture and daily life, thereby embedding ethical practices within the institutional framework. Finally, at the micro-level, teachers make daily ethical decisions and are responsible for ensuring that students receive an education grounded in ethical principles. These layers are intertwined and create a comprehensive approach where ethics is deeply integrated into both policy and practice throughout the educational landscape.

In the following section, the focus will be on the meso-level of (formal) educational ethics.

3. Educational Ethics at the Meso-Level

Institutional structures are flexible and can be shaped (Prenzel, 2020, p. 74). At the meso-level of formal education, as Fend (2008a, 2008b) describes, schools recontextualize the educational frameworks (designed at the macro-level) to fit their local conditions. Thus, decisions are guided by institutional frameworks but are adapted to reflect the unique conditions and needs of each individual school. In doing this, schools have to not only organize classes in terms of time and space, but also tackle a variety of tasks that involve numerous ethically relevant decisions. While traditional models emphasize schools primarily as administrative units executing orders, new approaches compel them to make independent pedagogical and ethical decisions. At the same time, all actions take place within a detailed legal framework structured by formal procedures. This complex task structure illustrates how schools, as corporate actors, implement their institutional mandates into a living school development. The key actors at the meso-level are school principals or school leadership teams, school quality assurance officers, teachers, students, and students' guardians.

The role of educational ethics at the meso-level is to ensure that school-autonomous decisions are made transparently, are understandable, and are based on sound reasoning within the specific context of each school. This means that schools must engage in ethical reflection to ensure that their decisions contribute to a positive and inclusive educational environment. Furthermore, creating a “good” (a concept fundamentally rooted in ethics) school environment involves addressing ethical questions that are deeply intertwined with values and principles, including how schools respond to changing societal values (Gardner, 2006; Zecha, 2018). Therefore, a thoughtful ethical approach in shaping school life is vital for maintaining the quality of education and fostering a positive atmosphere for all members of the school community.

The meso-level encompasses school policy, leadership, development, community engagement, and school culture (Fend, 2008a, p. 17). It is structured by autonomy rules and leadership regulations. As a result, decisions at this level—including those with ethical implications—primarily focus on (1) school-autonomous decision-making and (2) organizing of school culture and school life.

3.1. Developing School-autonomous Decision Guidelines

Western European schools have increasingly been granted significant autonomy in decision-making over the last years (Christ & Dobbins, 2016; Directorate-General for Education, 2008; Fend, 2008a), but what does this autonomy truly entail in practice? At its core, the concept of school autonomy raises ethical questions about the authority behind decision-making, the principles that should guide these decisions, and the processes by which they are made. Who, ultimately, should hold the power to make decisions within a school, and on what basis should these decisions be grounded? Are decisions to be guided solely by operational needs and logistical concerns, or should they be influenced by broader ethical frameworks? These are fundamental questions that must be addressed when considering the nature of autonomous decision-making in schools.

One key element in understanding school autonomy is the recognition that decisions can be shaped by specific guiding principles, such as a school's mission statement or its focus areas. These guiding principles often reflect a deeper ethical vision, rooted in a normative understanding of education and the role of schools in society. School values are not just abstract ideals but serve as the foundation for the decision-making process at all levels of the school (Fend, 2008a). For instance, the distinct school type of (Accredited) European Schools (Office of the Secretary-General of the European Schools, 2025) incorporates a key element known as the European dimension, which encompasses a set of core values, including respect for other cultures, tolerance, peace, democracy, and solidarity (Silian, 2024, p. 150). Although these values are often established at the macro-level, their realization depends fundamentally on meso-level implementation. When decisions are made in alignment with these principles, the autonomy of the school is not merely operational but is also infused with a deeper ethical commitment to shaping students' development and well-being.

The autonomy of schools allows them to make decisions in a variety of areas, depending on the type of school and the legal regulations that govern them. Depending on the respective education system, school autonomy varies. For instance, in Austria, as of 2025, school autonomy encompasses a range of decisions, including curriculum adaptations, organization of instruction (such as class structuring, group arrangements, and lesson scheduling), experimental school projects (which may involve implementation and collaboration with external school partners), school hours (including school-free days, whether Saturday is considered a school day, the start and end times of school periods, and supervision policies), and the implementation of full-day school models. In addition to these areas, schools have the authority to make decisions regarding staff selection and development, school partnerships, and collaboration with other educational institutions (BMBWF, 2018).

When schools are viewed as corporate actors (Fend, 2008a), school leadership assumes a central role. The principal holds primary responsibility for implementing legal requirements and shaping the school both administratively and pedagogically—especially within the framework of growing autonomy. This so-called recontextualization task demands not only leadership skills but also the ability to collaborate, emotional intelligence, and a strong sense for pedagogical

development. Effective school leadership (MacBeath, 1998; Browne, 2021) means guiding the school in dialogue with the teaching staff, encouraging participation in decision-making, fostering a positive school climate, and striking a balance between adherence to regulations and openness to innovation. The quality of leadership is especially reflected in how it is perceived by the staff—as involving trust, oversight, humor, openness to new ideas, and the capacity for constructive communication and problem-solving. While fulfilling formal duties is expected, it is attributes like confidence, fairness, integrity, and a forward-thinking mindset that truly define strong leadership. Good school leadership inspires, motivates, and creates a shared sense of responsibility for a vibrant and future-oriented school.

In the spirit of inclusion and participation, it is often emphasized that school-autonomous decisions should be made with input from a broad range of stakeholders within the school community (Solhaug, 2018; Williams, 1989). This could involve teachers, students, parents, and administrative staff, all of whom bring different perspectives and experiences to the decision-making table. Democratic voting processes are one way to engage the community in school-level decisions, ensuring that the voices of all those affected by these decisions are heard and considered. These participatory processes not only foster a sense of ownership and accountability among stakeholders, but also enhance the legitimacy of the decisions made. However, this approach touches on the broader issue of who is considered a legitimate participant in shaping the direction of a school and the ethical implications of such inclusion.

Moreover, school autonomy is not universally viewed as positive. It is linked to neoliberal trends in education, as increased school autonomy may foster a more competitive environment among schools (Niesche & Thomson, 2017). Wermke and Solokangas (2021) examined teachers' perceptions of professional autonomy in Finland, Ireland, Germany, and Sweden, finding that increased autonomy does not necessarily correlate with improved outcomes. Instead, it can increase complexity, pressure, and anxiety, sometimes causing teachers to resist autonomy. This insight, termed the “autonomy paradox,” challenges the common belief that more autonomy is always beneficial. Furthermore, Sholderer et al. (2017) found that school autonomy improves performance in countries with high social capital but can harm performance in countries with lower social capital. This suggests that the effectiveness of granting schools more decision-making power depends on the surrounding social environment, highlighting the need for tailored educational reforms.

Thus, the process by which decisions are made within schools requires careful consideration. Schratz (2003) argues that it is vital for school organizational structures to be transparent, flexible, and responsive to the specific needs and conditions of the school community. These structures must be clearly documented and should facilitate efficient decision-making processes that align with the educational mandate of the institution. Schools should be able to clearly communicate how decisions are made, who is responsible for making them, and the rationale behind these decisions. Transparency not only builds trust within the school community but also ensures that decisions are made in a fair and accountable manner. At the same time, the structures must be designed to be adaptable, allowing schools to respond to changes in the local context, evolving educational needs, and emerging challenges.

In order to foster an environment conducive to pedagogical development, it is essential that the focus of decision-making be on the needs of students, particularly their learning, rather than solely on the logistics of teaching (Schratz, 2018). Pedagogical school development should center on the improvement of learning processes, aiming to create an environment that nurtures intellectual curiosity, critical thinking, and personal growth. It is not enough to focus on improving teaching methods or expanding curricula; schools must also consider how to create an environment that supports students' emotional and social development. By placing learning at the heart of decision-making, schools can ensure that their autonomous decisions contribute not only to operational efficiency but also to the overall educational experience and well-being of students.

This underscores how complex decision-making can be in autonomous schools. Clear and transparent guidelines are essential, but they must also remain flexible to address the unique needs of each school community. This is why it is especially important that such decisions are rooted in strong ethical principles. When grounded in ethics, school autonomy becomes more than just an administrative tool—it reflects the school's values and its commitment.

3.2. Shaping School Life

The way schools design their environments reflects their deeper guiding principles and (implicit) moral beliefs. The organization of school culture and school life is a deeply ethical undertaking, as the well-being, personal development, and overall happiness of both students (Konu & Rimpelä, 2002) and teachers (Viac & Fraser, 2020) are profoundly influenced by the way schools structure their environments and activities. School life is not merely a backdrop to academic instruction; it plays a central role in shaping the lives of everyone involved. As Heis and Mascotti-Knoflach (2022) point out, schools are places of growth, offering not only intellectual education but also emotional, social, and ethical development. These factors make the shaping of school life a complex and significant process, demanding careful ethical reflection on the values and principles that should guide every aspect of it.

The implementation of institutional guidelines and the shaping of school life at the level of individual schools necessitate numerous ethically relevant decisions. As schools gain more autonomy, their responsibility increases because they are required to make decisions that often involve significant ethical considerations. The process of developing a school in an ethically responsible manner must be driven by the schools themselves, with careful reflection on the ethical dimensions of each choice (Wiesner & Schreiner, 2021).

The establishment of curricular and didactic priorities at a school raises further ethical questions about what is taught, how it is taught, and the purpose of education itself. Schools must decide which subjects or topics take priority in their curricula and how to approach the teaching of these subjects. These decisions are not neutral but are infused with values—values about what knowledge is most important, what skills are most necessary for students to acquire, and what it means to lead a fulfilling life. Whether a school emphasizes scientific literacy, social-emotional learning, or the arts, each decision reflects an underlying belief about the goals of education and its role in shaping individuals and society. These curricular and extracurricular choices carry

ethical implications, as they influence not only what students learn but how they learn to think, engage with the world, and relate to others.

According to Altrichter et al. (2016), key elements that contribute to the quality of a school extend far beyond the realm of subject-specific instruction. These elements include opportunities for personal development in various spheres, such as cultural, social, and athletic activities. Personal development, in this sense, refers to the holistic growth of students as individuals—developing their creativity, social skills, athletic abilities, and emotional intelligence. Schools that provide rich opportunities for such development foster well-rounded individuals who are prepared not only academically but also socially and emotionally for the challenges they will face in life. The process of establishing school-specific priorities is not limited to academic and performance-oriented decisions but also encompasses aspects related to school life, such as organizing celebrations and fostering a positive school culture (Weinert, 2000, p. 10).

Schools are often viewed as living spaces where extracurricular activities make a significant contribution to the quality of childhood and adolescent experiences (Dewey, 1916; Fend, 2008a; von Hentig, 2007). The inclusion of extracurricular activities—whether in the arts, sports, or community service—serves to enrich students' lives and provide them with avenues to explore their interests and passions. These opportunities contribute to the creation of a school culture that values and supports the full spectrum of human potential. Good schools offer a variety of positively valued events (e.g., festivals, concerts, parental involvement) that foster staff engagement and social integration, whereas underperforming schools often exhibit a negative attitude and lower participation. Vibrant school events substantially contribute to educational effectiveness by making the “hidden” educational spirit visible and tangible.

In this context, schools play an essential role in fostering a sense of community (Sergiovanni, 1994) and social integration. Schools should not only be places of individual growth but also spaces where students, teachers, and staff interact and collaborate in ways that promote a sense of belonging and mutual respect. A strong, inclusive community within the school is crucial for creating an environment in which students feel safe, supported, and understood. Schools should make conscious efforts to recognize and value diversity in all its forms and work to ensure that every student, regardless of background, feels respected and included. Additionally, schools should develop transparent strategies for addressing and resolving conflicts constructively (Harris & Morrisson, 2013). Conflict is inevitable in any community, but how it is managed can determine the health and success of the school environment. It is important for schools to cultivate an atmosphere where disagreements are handled respectfully, where individuals can express differing opinions without fear of retaliation, and where all parties are encouraged to work together toward peaceful solutions.

One of the most significant tensions in shaping school life is the balance between freedom and regulation (Fend, 2008a; Havinghurst, 1973). On the one hand, schools must create rules that enable a harmonious and non-violent coexistence among students and staff. These rules are necessary to establish order, promote fairness, and ensure that everyone in the school community can engage in their work and activities in a safe and supportive environment. On the other hand, schools must be cautious not to impose excessive restrictions on individual freedoms. Education

is not merely about following rules but about empowering students to think critically, make their own decisions, and develop into independent, responsible individuals. Overly restrictive rules can stifle students' autonomy and creativity, limiting their ability to grow and learn in ways that are meaningful to them. Thus, schools must carefully consider the types of rules and regulations they implement, ensuring that these rules strike a balance between providing structure and respecting individual rights.

In this context, rules and rituals serve as essential tools for fostering a democratic school culture. They provide guidance and structure, helping students understand how to interact with others respectfully and responsibly. The goal is to create a school environment where everyone—students, teachers, staff, and parents—feels part of a shared mission to foster mutual respect and democratic values. Prengel (1999) emphasizes that these rules and rituals should support democratic community life and promote mutual respect. They should encourage students to consider the needs and perspectives of others, to engage in dialogue, and to contribute to the collective well-being of the school community. In this way, the shaping of school life becomes an ethical endeavor that goes beyond administrative tasks to encompass the very values that a school seeks to impart to its students.

The design of school life involves a complex interplay of values, principles, and practical considerations. By carefully considering these ethical dimensions, schools can create environments that not only promote academic achievement but also nurture the personal and social growth of students, preparing them to become ethically responsible members of society.

Conclusion and Outlook

Schools are not merely sites of knowledge transmission; they are ethical communities that shape the lives of future generations. As this paper has argued, recognizing schools as ethical decision-makers at the meso-level of the education system is crucial for understanding the value-laden nature of educational practices and institutional life. By drawing on philosophical ethics and educational science, this paper has demonstrated that the decisions made at the meso-level are not simply technical or administrative but deeply normative. Given the multifaceted nature of educational ethics, an interdisciplinary approach is essential to effectively addressing the complex ethical issues that schools encounter daily. Bridging philosophical ethics and educational science offers valuable insights for navigating the ethical dimensions of school governance and practice. The complexity of educational ethics at the meso-level is illustrated in Figure 3, which categorizes various elements of this field and emphasizes its importance in understanding and guiding school decision-making.

The increasing autonomy of schools within many educational systems presents both opportunities and ethical responsibilities. It requires schools to reflect on the values guiding their decisions, to involve diverse stakeholders in shaping school life, and to prioritize the well-being and development of students. At the meso-level, educational ethics plays a central role in guiding school-autonomous decisions to be transparent, well-reasoned, and aligned with the core values and mission of the institution. As societal values continue to evolve, schools must engage in ongoing ethical reflection, adapting to new challenges while maintaining their ethical integrity. Shaping school culture and everyday school life is also an ethically charged endeavor, requiring

careful consideration of how policies and practices impact the students and communities they serve.

Looking ahead, ethical foundations as well as the development of robust frameworks for educational ethics at the meso-level are essential. In an era of rapid change, educational institutions will need to rethink their approaches to ethical decision-making in response to new societal challenges. Schools must continue to develop strategies that allow them to act as ethical decision-makers, balancing the pressures of educational policy, societal expectations, and the ever-changing needs of students.

It will be essential to deepen the discussion on ethical decision-making in schools by involving all stakeholders—teachers, students, guardians, and policymakers. By fostering a culture of ethical reflection and collaboration, schools can build stronger, more resilient educational environments that better prepare students to thrive in an increasingly complex world. Educational ethics at the meso-level will remain a vital field of inquiry, guiding schools in their mission to nurture future generations. Through ongoing engagement with ethical challenges, schools can ensure that their decisions promote not only academic success but also holistic growth and the well-being of all members of the school community.

Fig. 3: Categorization of (Formal) Educational Ethics within Ethics with Focus on the Meso-Level (Bacher, 2025)

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“The MelArete Project”: Education on Friendship as a Political Virtue for Caring Communities

Luigina Mortari and Federica Valbusa

Introduction

The human condition rests on an ontological paradox. Humans have no sovereignty over their own being, which is fragile, vulnerable, and fleeting. Simultaneously, they are bound by the responsibility to shape their own becoming, making their existential possibilities flourish. Cultivating the art of existing means learning to accept and take on this responsibility, which is expressed in caring for one’s life. However, to make one’s own life good, it is not enough to care for oneself. One must also be cared for by others (Tronto, 1993; Kittay, 1999; Held, 2006; Mortari, 2022).

Humans are singular beings because each one has an individuality that expresses its unrepeatable originality. However, they are also plural beings, since their ontological consistency is essentially relational. In the human condition, being-there is being-with-others (Heidegger, 1927/2010). Because humans have a plural consistency, the possibility of achieving a good life does not concern humans as individuals, but as beings in relationships with one another. As a fundamental existential phenomenon, care is the modality in which the condition of being-with-others finds an essentially ethical qualification. Reflecting on how to give good form to our living with others means reflecting on how to promote an ethical education for citizenship, so caring relationships can facilitate the flourishing of the community and individuals in their differences and originality.

Specifically, this is the educational purpose of the second edition of the MelArete programme, developed by the Center of Educational and Didactic Research (CRED) of the University of Verona (Italy). After an original implementation focusing on courage, generosity, respect, and justice, starting from the scholastic year 2020-2021, the programme was updated with a specific focus on friendship, conceptualised as an ethical and political virtue, according to the Aristotelian interpretation. The title ‘MelArete’ combines the Greek terms ‘*melete*’ and ‘*arete*,’ which, respectively, mean ‘care’ and ‘virtue,’ the main conceptual cornerstones of the programme, which addresses kindergarten and primary school children.

In this essay, we will 1) outline the theoretical framework on which the programme is rooted, which conceptualises an education on friendship in the perspective disclosed by the philosophy of care and the ethics of virtues; 2) briefly compare the theory underlying MelArete with the main cultures in ethical education presented in the international literature; 3) describe one of the educational activities proposed to the children in the MelArete programme, specifically an

activity that fosters their reflection on friendship, sparked by the selected thoughts of important philosophers; and 4) present and comment on data collected from the implementation of this activity in some Italian kindergarten and primary school classes.

1. Theoretical Framework: Philosophy of Care and Ethics of Virtue

MeLarete can be defined as a programme of education on virtues from the perspective of care. Including a reflection on friendship as a political virtue developed to construct caring communities, its second edition gives form to a programme of ethical education for citizenship. Given this definition, some conceptual connections must be clarified: the connection between ethics and care, given the priority of justice in ethical Occidental thought; the connection between care and virtues, given the possibility that the concept of virtue is not framed in a theory of care; the connection between virtues and education, given Socrates' scepticism about the possibility of teaching the virtues; and the connection between friendship and citizenship, given the common consideration of friendship as an elective form of affective relationship.

1.1. Ethics and Care

The intimate connection between care and ethics is confirmed in the reflections of Paul Ricœur, renowned for his studies on phenomenology and his contribution to philosophical hermeneutics, who delved into the concepts of ethics and morality in an essay published in 1990. In this essay, after defining ethics as aiming for a good life with and for others in just institutions, Ricœur notices that the term 'aiming' (*souhait* in French) is too generic and suggests substituting it with the term 'care' (*souci* in French). Consequently, 'ethics' is defined as discourse about care for oneself, care for others and care for institutions (Ricœur, 1990). Given this definition, it is possible to establish a connection between ethics and care by concluding that the ethics of a good life must be an ethics of care. However, importantly, in Occidental culture, ethics has been mainly interpreted over time through the concept of justice. Going back to ancient Greek philosophy, in the Socratic and Platonic perspective, justice finds a primary position. This is evident, for example in the following Socratic declaration: "I thought I should run any risk on the side of law and justice rather than join you, for fear of prison or death, when you were engaged in an unjust course" (Plato, *Apology*, 32b-c). In *Gorgias*, Socrates states that the most excellent way of life consists in practicing justice and all other virtue (527e). Because of this primacy, which must be reserved for justice, the main principle to which one must adhere is that "doing what's unjust is more to be guarded against than suffering it" (Plato, *Gorgias*, 527b). The *Republic*, where Plato stages the ideal city, opens with a long discourse about the essence of justice. The importance given to justice leads Socrates to say that if someone "finds many injustices in his life, he awakes from sleep in terror, as children do, and lives in anticipation of bad things to come" (Plato, *Republic*, 330e). Nevertheless, the primacy assigned to justice must be considered from a broader perspective that recognises the practice of caring for the soul as the very core of the Socratic *paideia*. The ancient Greek philosopher Aristotle considers justice a complete virtue because it addresses others (*Nicomachean Ethics*, V, 1129b 25–27) and because every virtue is included in the virtue of justice (*Nicomachean Ethics*, V, 1129b 29–30). However, another virtue addresses others, namely friendship, which he seems to prioritise over justice: "If people are friends, they have no need of justice, but if they are just they need friendship in addition; and the justice that is most just seems to belong to friendship" (Aristotle,

Nicomachean Ethics, VIII, 1155a 27-29). This position is significant because, according to a phenomenological analysis of the practice of care, friendship results in a virtue in which care realises itself intensely. Moreover, friendships can be conceptualised as caring relationships (Mortari, 2006, 2016).

A fundamental reference for contemporary ethical reflections can be found in the theory of justice outlined by John Rawls, who considers justice as fairness. His fundamental book, *A Theory of Justice*, was published in 1971. The same year, Milton Mayeroff published an important work about care entitled *On Caring*. According to Rawls (1971), “each person possesses an inviolability founded on justice that even the welfare of society as a whole cannot override” (p. 3). Meanwhile, Mayeroff states that the primary ontological necessity is the one of care that allows a person to actualise herself (1971). Furthermore, according to Rawls (1971), the life of a community must be built on the principle of justice, guaranteeing to everybody the full respect of rights, which are not subjected to political bargaining. In contrast, according to Mayeroff (1971), life must be ordered with principles that inspire us to act with care. In summary, it is possible to state that the theory of justice is based on the ontological premise that a community is constituted by self-sufficient people. However, the theory of care assumes that each constitutively relational person needs others.

During the last decades of the past century, great consideration was devoted to Rawls’s thesis. Nonetheless, growing attention has emerged for the principles shaping an ethics of care, mainly from the cultural perspective disclosed by feminist thought. Carol Gilligan (1982), based on data collected through empirical research, theorises two ethical voices, the “voice of care” and the “voice of justice.” The ethical theory underlying *Meleagris* considers the voices of care and justice as complementary. Indeed, one does not enact good care if what one does is not just. In contrast, one does not act justly if one does not care for the people or things for which one is acting. Returning to ancient Greek philosophy, this complementarity is confirmed in Plato’s *Phaedrus*, in which Socrates states that Zeus, who is responsible for the world, has the duty of arranging and caring for all things (246e).

1.2. Care and Virtues

The concept of virtue was born in ancient Greek philosophy. It finds precise theorisation among the Sophists. However, it is with Socrates and Plato and later with Aristotle that the discourse about virtue becomes the object of a deep philosophic examination. Socrates indicates the importance of persuading young people to “care for virtue” (Plato, *Euthydemus*, 275a) and, highlighting the importance of caring for the soul, suggests that from virtue originates the richness needed by the soul to acquire the best possible form (Plato, *Apology*, 30b). In *Apology* (29e), Socrates clarifies that virtue is among the things, along with wisdom and truth, that must be cared for, and he defines his mission as persuading Athenians “to care for virtue” (Plato, *Apology*, 31b). Even in Aristotle’s opinion, virtue is essential for seeking a good quality of life (*eudaimonia*). In this regard, he defines “virtue” as “the sort of state that does the best actions concerning pleasures and pains” (Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, II, 1104b 27-28). Based on the assumption that searching for good connects to acting according to virtue (Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, I, 1099a 15–16), Aristotelian ethics can be defined as an ethics of virtues.

The concept of virtue is clearly explicated in the *Rhetoric*: “Virtue, it would seem, is a faculty of providing and preserving good things, a faculty productive of many and great benefits, in fact, of all things in all cases” (1366a–b). Virtue becomes crucial when one must act, and every action is guided by an evaluation taking shape when analysing the situation. The risk is that the analysis and the resultant decision can become unbalanced between the opposite extremes in which a situation occurs. Therefore, the essence of virtue should be found in being able to stay in the mean between the extremes of excess and deficiency: “Virtue, then, is a mean, insofar as it aims at what is intermediate” (Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, II, 1106b 27-28).

In the classical and mediæval periods, the concept of virtue was central, and it remained important in the post-mediæval and modern periods, when other ways of interpreting ethics emerged. Then, virtue ethics declined during the positivistic–analytical period (Pellegrino & Thomasma, 1993). The concept of virtue has only recently been revived in philosophical debate after having been long forgotten (Foot, 1978). In this renewed interest in virtue ethics, Aristotelian thought plays a central role. According to Nussbaum (2012), this can be explained by an ever-increasing dissatisfaction with certain formalistic ethics, which, being fundamentally interested in guaranteeing moral reasoning of universal value, result in being far from the requirements of practical life. However, according to Berges (2009), the limit of the current rediscovery of the ethics of virtues is that it forgets the contribution of Plato, while a valid and rigorous ethics of virtues cannot prescind from the study of Platonic thought. If it is true that some dialogues are aporetic and fail to completely define the essence of the virtues they examine, they nevertheless present a method for analysing ethical issues.

The theory of ethical education underlying the MelArete programme considers Aristotelian thought as central to the construction of the conceptual framework of an ethics of virtues; likewise, it simultaneously considers the Socratic thought emerging in the Platonic dialogues as essential to interpreting the concept of virtue through the consideration of the concept of care, and to providing precise methodological indications to examine virtues. Another contribution to the theory construing ethical education as an education on virtue from the perspective of care originates from a phenomenological analysis of experiences of care. As a practice, care reveals its essential qualities through the ways of being of a person when one relates to others and to things. Phenomenological research (Mortari & Saiani, 2014; Mortari, 2022) suggests that the ways of being that characterise a good practice of care can be defined using the same concepts through which virtues are referred. Indeed, care is revealed in the thoughts and deeds of generosity, responsibility, patience, courage, respect, justice, gratitude, and so on.

1.3. *Virtues and Education*

An education in care can result in an education on virtues, given theoretical assumptions about ethical education’s conceptualisation as an education to care and the essential nucleus of care’s comprising virtues. A question arises: Is an education on virtues possible? Doubt is raised in Plato’s *Meno* (96 c–d). The argument is presented that because it is impossible to find teachers of virtues, it must be concluded that virtues cannot be taught. The discussion about the possibility of teaching virtues is also addressed in *Protagoras*, where Socrates highlights that “the wisest and best of our citizens are unable to transmit to others the virtues that they possess” (319e). Subsequently, after stating that he could name many personally good men who could not

make anyone else good, he concludes, “Looking at these things, Protagoras, I just don’t think that virtue can be taught” (Plato, *Protagoras*, 320b). If, at first glance, it might seem that Socrates excludes the possibility of an education on virtues, an analysis of the Greek text and the consideration of the example he offered in the Platonic dialogues lead to reconsidering the issue. In *Meno*, where the possibility of teaching virtue is discussed, the Greek word ‘*didakton*’ is used (89c, 89d, 93b, 96c), which is translatable as ‘teachable.’ Effectively, if we imagine teaching as an instructional action of transmitting something to someone else, virtues cannot be taught, because, as Socrates points out, they cannot be transmitted to others. However, as Socrates exemplifies in his *paideia*, education differs from instruction, which is clear when he states that he never promised to teach anything and has not done so (Plato, *Apology*, 33b). In the Socratic perspective, education is considered a practice of caring for others to make them learn to care for their souls (Plato, *Apology*, 29d–e). This care for the soul is realised by caring for virtues (Plato, *Apology*, 31b 5) because only virtues generate the richness of what life needs (Plato, *Apology*, 30b). Nonetheless, if education is not instruction and virtues are not teachable in that they cannot be transmitted, how is it possible to educate others to care for them? Socrates indicates the educational method in the dialogues, in which he urges his interlocutors to reason about virtues to catch their essence. The importance that Socrates attributes to the practice of reasoning about virtues is clarified in his *Apology*, where he states, “It is the greatest good for a man to discuss virtue every day” (38a). If the quality of an ethical act depends on the rightness of the deliberation on which it is based, then knowledge of what induces decisions is essential. Otherwise, mistakes will be unavoidable (Plato, *Phaedrus*, 237b–c). Correspondingly, reasoning on virtues is fundamental because only by knowing their essence can one make the right ethical choices.

If the method of educating to virtues suggested by the Socratic *paideia* is engagement in eidetic thinking, namely, examining a concept to catch its essential meaning, Aristotle conceives of virtues as a way of being that develops through practice. He states, “We become just by doing just actions, temperate by doing temperate actions, brave by doing brave actions” (Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, II, 1103b 1-2). In ancient culture, the essential duty of a human comprised learning the technique of existence. Because learning a technique requires practice, it is possible to conclude that a virtuous way of being also takes shape through practice. Precisely because of the centrality given to practice in ethical education, Aristotle states, “It is not unimportant ... to acquire one sort of habit or another, right from our youth” (*Nicomachean Ethics*, II, 1103b 23-25). If it is clear that Socrates highlights the centrality of reasoning while Aristotle suggests the priority of practising, it must be clarified that in their reflections about ethical education, some common elements also exist. According to Socrates, practice, even with a marginal role compared to an eidetic exam, is also important for cultivating virtues. In fact, in the *Republic* he suggests that virtues of the soul require habit and practice (518e). Aristotle does not ignore the role of thinking. He maintains that ethical acting is acting according to the right reasoning (Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, II, 1103b 33). Indeed, it must be clarified that the Aristotelian concept of virtue as habit, which is at the core of all interpretations of Aristotelian virtue ethics, does not refer to unreflective behaviour but to a way of being that takes shape due to the work of reason (Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, II, 1105a 28–33). In other words, it must be recognised that acting according to virtues requires the continuous guidance of critical and reflective reason (Pellegrino & Thomasma, 1993).

Given this theoretical framework, the MelArete project utilises a theory of education to virtue from the perspective of care, and according to Socratic and Aristotelian methods. Indeed, in designing the programme, importance has been given to reasoning on ethical concepts and the practice of virtues. However, an issue arose when designing educational activities on the practice of virtues. How can we translate the Aristotelian suggestion of considering the importance of practice without establishing a priori what constitutes the ethical way of acting in a precise situation? It must be recognised that authentic educational action cannot aspire to shape humans from the outside by imposing predefined ways of behaving. The challenge has been to seek a method that allows children to pay attention to their ethical experiences without directing them in advance. The solution was to design activities that involve children reflecting on ethical practices. In this way, children are not urged to act precisely, but are invited to think about how they and others act.

1.4. Friendship and Citizenship

MelArete, especially in its second edition, can be defined as a project of education on virtues for citizenship because the concept of virtue has ethical and political interpretations. This is true for virtues addressed to others to seek their good and, as a community, to seek the common good. Socrates refers to virtues that are proper for human beings and virtues that are proper for citizens (Plato, *Apology*, 20b). Consequently, it is possible to distinguish personal virtues, which orient the cultivation of the soul and are exercised towards oneself to shape one's being, and political virtues, which concern living with others in the world. Moreover, according to Aristotle, there are virtues exercised towards oneself and virtues exercised towards others. In his opinion, "the best person is not the one who exercises virtue [only] towards himself, but the one who [also] exercises it in relation to another, since this is a difficult task" (Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, V, 1130a 7–8). Among other virtues exercised towards others which, following the Aristotelian concept, can be interpreted as a political virtue, there is friendship. According to Aristotle, friendship is necessary for life because "no one would choose to live without friends even if he had all the other goods" (*Nicomachean Ethics*, VIII, 1155a 5–6). Socrates states something similar in *Lysis*, where we read, "I would rather have a good friend than the best quail or gamecock known to man, and ... more than any horse or dog. There's no doubt in my mind ... that I would rather possess a friend than all Darius's gold or even than Darius, himself. That's how much I value friends" (211e 2–7). Friendship is necessary for life and important for human flourishing because it enhances ethical development by making people better in reflection and in action (Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, VIII, 1155a 16). According to Aristotle, three typologies of friendship exist: friendship based on utility, where people "love the other not in his own right, but insofar as they gain some good for themselves from him" (*Nicomachean Ethics*, VIII, 1156a 10–12); friendship based on pleasure, where people "like a witty person not because of his character, but because he is pleasant to them" (*Nicomachean Ethics*, VIII, 1156a 12–14); and ethical (*The Eudemian Ethics*, VII.7, 1241a 10) or complete friendship (*Nicomachean Ethics*, VIII, 1156b 7), where people "wish goods to their friend for the friend's own sake" (*Nicomachean Ethics*, VIII, 1156b 9–10). Good will, which can be conceptualised as the disposition to promote the good of the other, pertains to the last typology of friendship (Aristotle, *The Eudemian Ethics*, VII.7, 1241a 10). Ethical friendship is an important example of a caring relationship because it is nourished by the logic of gifts. The goodwill or benevolence which characterises friendship involves doing "someone a good turn without aiming to receive one in

return” (Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, VIII, 1162b 36–1163a 1). One does not desire good for another due to an ulterior motive or interest; one desires good for another due to one’s devotion to him, not for oneself.

What makes Aristotelian reflections particularly interesting for designing experiences of ethical education for citizenship is his interpretation of friendship as a political virtue. This interpretation is clearly argued where he suggests that friendship is fundamental for a community: “Friendship would seem to hold cities together, and legislators would seem to be more concerned about it than about justice. For concord would seem to be similar to friendship, and they aim at concord among all, while they try above all to expel civil conflict, which is enmity” (Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, VIII, 1155a 22–26). This concept is also taken up in *The Eudemian Ethics*, where Aristotle states that “the promotion of friendship is regarded as the special task of the political skill” (VII.1, 1234b 23). Since friendship is considered the basis for building and maintaining a community, an education in it must conceive of it as an indispensable aspect of ethical education for citizenship. Indeed, the cohabiting that—according to the philosophy of care—essentially characterises our being in the world needs justice and concord, a feeling that takes shape precisely in friendships. This is why it can be hypothesised that the solidaristic and supportive network of living together that shapes a community finds a promising and fruitful strengthening in diffusion of friendships. A society that cultivates the greatest possible relational meaningfulness is one in which schools aim to form citizens willing to collaborate in respect of and in appreciation for each other’s differences for the common good. This disposition, on which programmes on an ethical education for citizenship should centre, can be called “political friendship” (Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, IX, 1167b 2). Political friendship is fundamental for living in a community seeking for and engaging in the common good because people who cannot cultivate citizenship from the perspective of political friendship “seek to over-reach in benefits [to themselves] and shirk labours and public services. And since each wishes this for himself, he interrogates and obstructs his neighbour; for when people do not look out for the common good, it is ruined” (Aristotle, *Nicomachean Ethics*, IX, 1167b 11–14).

Based on this theoretical framework, which conceptualises friendship as a fundamental ethical virtue for caring relationships and an essential political virtue for caring citizenship, the MelArete programme involves children in educational activities designed to give them the opportunity to reflect on what friendship is and how it takes form in their lives.

2. Literature Overview: Approaches to Ethical Education

A literature review on ethical education makes clear that different pedagogical cultures have been developed in this field. In particular, the majority of authors refer to character education, in its traditional form or in its current forms, the cognitive–developmental approach or moral reasoning, and care ethics education (Howard, Berkowitz & Schaeffer, 2004; Althof & Berkowitz, 2006; Graham, Haidt, & Rimm-Kaufman, 2008; Cooley, 2008). Character education, in its traditional form, was developed in the United States at the end of the 19th century. Through the first four decades of the 20th century, it was characterised by its purpose of instilling traditional values and inculcating desirable habits in youth. In the 1960s, after a period of vacuum in this field, a renewed interest in promoting ethical education in schools emerged with the appearance of the values clarification movement, which declined under criticism of

being relativistic and lacking scientific evidence regarding its impact. The 1970s and early 1980s were dominated by the cognitive–developmental approach, which raised criticisms about the appropriateness of inculcating a predefined set of virtues and, relying on Kohlberg’s research on the stages of moral development, was instead interested in promoting moral reasoning through discussions about moral dilemmas (Kohlberg, 1975; Kohlberg & Hersh, 1977; Turiel & Rothman, 1972; Rest, 1980; Nucci, 1985). The cultural dominance of the cognitive–developmental approach decreased in the late 1980s and 1990s under the criticism of feminist theorists, who emphasised the importance of caring relationships, empathic responses and moral sentiments, which are stressed and promoted by care ethics education (Noddings, 1984, 1988, 2002a, 2002b 2010a, 2010b, 2016; Noddings & Slote, 2002; Slote, 2010).

In recent decades, we are seeing a return to character education, an expression that nowadays is often used as an umbrella for varied approaches and methodologies to foster personal development, encompassing educational purposes related to moral reasoning, social-emotional learning, citizenship education, risk behaviour prevention and many other endeavors (Ottens, 2000; Pattaro, 2016). As character education, in its current form, remains difficult to define because existing approaches refer to distinct philosophical frameworks, pedagogical strategies and outcome goals (Althof & Berkowitz, 2006), it could be useful to directly give voice to associations and authors that recognise themselves in this pedagogical culture. According to Lickona (1991), character education is “the deliberate effort to develop a good character based on core virtues that are good for the individual and good for society” (p. 228). The Character Education Partnership asserts it is fostering “the deliberative effort by schools, families and communities to help young people understand, care about and act upon core ethical values” (cited in Lickona, 1996, p. 93). According to the ASCD, the Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development, character education includes “any deliberate approach by which school personnel, often in conjunction with parents and community members, help children and youth become caring, principled and responsible” (cited in Singh, 2019, p. 3). As per Howard, Berkowitz and Schaeffer (2004), it is “an attempt to prepare individuals to make ethical judgments and to act on them, that is, to do what one thinks ought to be done” (p. 189). As for the Jubilee Centre (2022), it “includes all explicit and implicit educational activities that help young people to develop positive personal strengths called virtues” and “is about helping pupils grasp what is ethically important in situations and how to act for the right reasons, so that they become more autonomous and reflective in the practice of virtue” (p. 7). Watts, Fullard and Peterson (2021) state that it is “the conscious process of cultivating worthwhile and positive dispositions” that they call “character virtues or character strengths” (p. 12).

The last two decades have been characterised by an important effort to rigorously study the effectiveness of character education programmes, so the literature refers to the aspiration to a “science of character education” (Berkowitz, 2002; Berkowitz, Bier & McCauley, 2017). Based on research on what works in character education, Berkowitz (2021) proposes six “design principles for how to nurture the development of human goodness, as well as other parts of human growth and academic learning” (p. 3); in clarifying these principles, the author uses the acronym PRIMED, which refers to the following elements: prioritization of character education, relationships, intrinsic motivation, modelling, empowerment, and developmental pedagogy. Kristjánsson (2015) directly refers to Aristotle to outline “a theoretical account of character education—as a form of moral education focusing on the development of virtues—designed

along broadly Aristotelian lines” (p. 2). From this perspective, virtues are believed necessary for human flourishing.

Comparing the theory of ethical education underlying MelArete with the several approaches outlined in the literature is not the focus of this essay and would require a broader space. Nonetheless, we can try to clarify commonalities and differences. Similar to character education, MelArete considers virtues central to ethical education, but without confusing education with indoctrination, as happened in the traditional form of this approach. Indeed, like the cognitive–developmental approach, MelArete gives importance to the development of reasoning and the encouragement of critical thinking by involving students in discussing ethical dilemmas, but without falling into abstractionism or rationalism as do some activities in this educational ethical approach. Similar to care ethics education, MelArete assigns a primary value to care but creates distance from an interpretation of care that is too situational or pre-eminently affective, because it considers care a practice informed both by emotions and thoughts, and considers the position that decisions in situations are also oriented by general principles, primarily obedience to the needs that reality reveals. Unlike current character education approaches, MelArete does not refer to the concept of character. Indeed, it refers to virtues as the essential ethical nucleus of care. Even if it is not defined as a character education programme, it embraces the call for research to evaluate the effectiveness of educational activities. Hence, data are collected in the classes involved in the programme, and they are analysed through qualitative methods to study the effectiveness of the proposed educational activities in fostering children’s ethical thinking (Mortari & Valbusa, 2019; Mortari et al., 2023; Mortari, Valbusa & Ubbiali, 2023; Mortari, Ubbiali & Bombieri, 2023). Finally, even if MelArete shares the importance of conceiving an education on virtues as fundamental for human flourishing, it diverges from Aristotelian character education because it does not take Aristotle as its main theoretical reference, but integrates Aristotelian and Socratic ethical thoughts and frames the cultivation of virtues in the theoretical perspective disclosed by the philosophy of care.

3. The Educational Programme: An Activity Designed to Reflect on Friendship

Grounded in this theoretical framework, the MelArete educational programme was designed to involve children in reflecting upon ethical concepts and experiences. The educational purposes of the curricula designed for kindergartens and primary schools are the same. However, some differentiations in activities are introduced according to the ages of the students involved. The main educational instruments used are as follows:

- Socratic conversations: children are invited to reason together on the essential meaning of ethical concepts and virtues, such as those suggested by words such as ‘good,’ ‘care,’ and ‘friendship.’ The researcher, acting as a facilitator, guides the conversation by asking questions to help children better clarify, deepen and problematise their ideas, to encourage a co-construction of thinking within the class.
- Stories: narrations exemplifying virtues, such as generosity and respect, are presented to children to encourage their reflection on the virtuous actions of the characters, which are animals living in the ‘Wood of Virtues.’ In kindergarten, stories are animated with puppets, while in primary school, they are handed to

children on an illustrated sheet and read by the researcher. Furthermore, in kindergarten, reflections on stories are conducted together through a conversation, starting from some questions posed by the researcher. In primary school, before sharing their reflections through a conversation, children are required to answer some questions individually in written form.

- Vignettes: Ethical dilemmas are presented in graphical form to involve children in discussions about what is the virtuous way, for example the courageous way or the just way, to act in a precise situation. The situations illustrated in the vignettes differ in kindergarten and primary school. In the first case, characters are animals, while in the second case, they are humans. Furthermore, in primary school, children also engage in a written individual activity before discussion.
- Experiential diary: children are invited to keep a personal journal where they collect their own thoughts on or consider gestures of gratitude. This virtue was added to the others on which the programme focused because to reflect on experiences of gratitude allows one to reflect on the experiences of good that one receives and that nourish life.

Furthermore, within the programme, a particular activity has been organised entitled “The Thoughts of the Sages” in primary school and “The Wise Animals of the Wood” in kindergarten. This activity encourages children to reflect on the concept and experience of friendship, starting from some philosophical ideas about it. In designing the activity, some philosophers’ sentences on friendship were selected and, in some cases, reformulated in easier language to facilitate children’s understanding. In primary school, these philosophical sentences are bound inside a notebook given to the children. On each page is a cartoon of a philosopher who states his/her idea. Beside it is a space where each child, individually, is asked to answer in writing the question: “What do you think about this?” Each child is invited to choose and comment on at least two of the philosophers’ thoughts. Subsequently, children are encouraged to discuss them, also considering the conceptualisations of friendship that they supplied through previous activities. In kindergarten, the organisation is quite different because the conversational activity about the philosophers’ ideas is included in a ludic frame. The researchers hide puppets of animals from the “Wood of Virtues” in the school hall or garden. The puppets hold jars between their paws, inside which are philosophical sentences on friendship. After a brief introduction, the researchers invite the children to look for the animals and bring the jars to the centre of the classroom. Next, the jars are opened, and researchers read the philosophers’ ideas to the children. For each philosophical sentence, a conversation is conducted starting from the following questions: “Do you agree with this sentence? Why? What do you think?” At the end of the conversation, the researchers propose that the children make a group drawing of a gesture of friendship.

The philosophical sentences proposed to the children are as follows:

- Socrates: “I would rather have a friend than all the gold of the richest man in the world” in primary school; “It is more important to have a friend than to have a treasure” in kindergarten (see Plato, *Lysis*, 211e 2–7, reformulated sentences).
- Aristotle: “No one would choose to live without friends even if he had all the other goods” (*Nicomachean Ethics*, VIII, 1155a 5–6).

- Pythagoras: “Friends have all in common” (see Turner, 1947, pp. 380–381).
- Epicurus: “The wise man suffers for his friend’s pain as much as he suffers for his own pain. And for a friend, he is ready to do anything, even to die, because if he betrays his friend, his life will be disrupted by his infidelity” in primary school; “The wise man suffers for his friend’s pain as much as he suffers for his own pain” in kindergarten (see *Vatican Sayings* 56 and D.L. 10. 121, reformulated sentences).
- Seneca: “From an enemy a friend may derive” (see *Epistulae morales ad Lucilium*, 95, 63, reformulated sentence).
- Cicero: “A true friend is seen in times of trouble” (see *De amicitia*, XVII, 64, reformulated sentence).
- Simone Weil: “Do not wish that someone gives you their friendship: Act as a friend towards them” (see Weil, 1970/2015, p. 43, reformulated sentence).

During the conversation about these philosophical sentences on friendship, the researchers take care that the conversational climate is also characterised by friendship. Therefore, children are invited to respect others in their persons and thoughts, to wait for their turn to speak, to listen and pay attention to others’ ideas and to recognise the value of dialogue, since it is an opportunity for cognitive enrichment and personal development.

4. *Friendship in Children’s Ideas*

The research implemented to study the educational effectiveness of the MelArete programme has confirmed that the activity presented above can stimulate children to reflect on the concept and experience of friendship, illustrating interesting and profound ideas. Indeed, philosophical sentences are an effective starting point to encourage them to reflect and discuss with each other, even trying to mediate between different perspectives. In this regard, it will be interesting to present some children’s ideas, collected during the implementation of the activity in two classes of two kindergartens and two classes of two primary schools in the south of Italy, with the involvement of 4-5-6-year-old and 10-11-year-old students.

Reflecting on the Socratic sentence in the kindergarten, a child commented that “friends are always close and always hold hands.” According to him, friendship is important because it answers the human needs of others. It is the condition that allows us not to be alone. Other children highlighted that friendship is important because it allows people to have fun: “I agree [with Socrates] because friends are for fun”; “With friends, we always have fun and play.” According to another child, “it is better to have money” because, in his opinion, with money, one can buy toys. Another comrade added, “You can buy TV, PlayStation games to play with your cousins.” Then, the researcher asked, “Is it better to have lots of toys or lots of friends?” A child, showing the effort to mediate between the different positions that emerged in the conversation, replied, “I like to play together.” This answer suggests that having games is beautiful. However, the best condition is having the opportunity to use them with friends.

In a primary school class, the reasoning developed among the children is that money is finite. On the other hand, friendships “do not finish” and “are infinite,” they said. At that point, the researcher asked, “And if you have a fight with a friend, what happens?” One child replied,

“You can always remedy it afterwards.” Another explained how it is possible to remedy, i.e., “by apologising or by making a kind gesture to the other person.” Agreeing with the Socratic idea, a child clarified that a friend can brighten your day: “Instead with money, that is gold, you cannot do anything if you are sad.” According to these ideas, friendship improves one’s quality of life.

Reflecting on the Aristotelian sentence, a child in primary school commented, “I do not like this judgment, because a person even without friends can be happy through family or maybe cousins....” According to him, it is important to emphasise that not only friendship ties, but also family ties make a happy life. Another child highlighted that what Aristotle means is that “his life, without friends, is meaningless.” His classmate added that “what Aristotle says is right because having friends means happiness in life.”

In kindergarten, a conversation arose about the possibility of conceiving of pets as friends. One child said, “I always hug my cat. I love him.” Another replied, “It doesn’t help having a cat; he scratches you.” So the first child reiterated, “Even if he scratches me, I love him anyway.” This dialogical exchange is significant because, starting from the children’s reflections, one could open the question about our relationship with animals: What relationship do we feel we must have with animals for a good quality of life? Are animals part of or outside of the human world? If they are part of the human world because we are inside the world of nature, how should our relationship with nature be cultivated? It is an ethical and political question because it concerns ways to live together and with other beings in a shared environment.

Discussing Pythagoras’s sentence, children in kindergarten seemed to interpret the idea of having everything in common as having the same interests and doing something together. For example, one said, “Friends play together.” Another interpretation that emerged during the conversation among kindergarten children concerns the idea of sharing something. In this regard, one child said, “If one has two snacks and a classmate does not have a snack, he gives him the other one.” The researcher then raised the following question: “And if he has only one?” The answer that emerged was “He divides into two.”

The primary school children, commenting on Pythagoras’s sentence, also referred to play, though they noted that children do not always have the same desires regarding which game to play. In such cases, friendship consists of trying to mediate between positions: “According to me, they don’t have all in common, because ... for example, I want to play ‘hide and seek,’ while [my friend] wants to play another game. These games are combined.” In addition, another child added, “For example, you want to play ‘hide and seek.’ I want to play ‘dodge ball,’ and ... we play while I hide, and you with the ball have to hit me.”

Dialoguing Epicurus’s sentence, in kindergarten a conversation arose about events during which a friend falls and gets hurt. In these cases, according to some children, “you must cure him” and “you care for and cure him.” When the researcher asked how one feels when seeing a friend who has been hurt, the children responded that they were “sad” and “worried.” In primary school, one child raised the possibility that a friend is suffering because of an offense, and stated, “For example, if you offend one of your friends, you and he feel bad because you realise that you were wrong.” Another child referred to the reciprocity that could characterise a friendship:

“Maybe if you help a friend, when you are in a bad situation, your friend helps you, maybe with words that can make you feel good.”

As is evident, the children’s reflections are not always a strict interpretation of the philosophical sentences presented to them. However, for the involved children, the philosophical sentences become the starting point for reflecting on friendship according to their thoughts and experiences. Discussing Seneca’s sentence, the kindergarteners considered situations in which one quarrels with a friend: “When [a classmate] argues with me, then we make peace, and she becomes a good friend.” In addition, “I get angry, but then I make peace.” The children’s experience of friendship as it emerges from these thoughts suggests that difficult relationships can be transformed into good ones.

In primary school, a discussion arose on the term ‘may’ in the sentence “Seneca says that from an enemy may derive a friend.” “It is not sure,” said a child. In addition, another child stated, “In my opinion ... that may be that he is sure because maybe it is an encouragement to the people who read him.” During the dialogical exchanges, a political reflection about the coexistence of peoples emerged regarding what happens when they are involved in a war, which is bad because it also breaks relational bonds. In particular, a child said, “If a people is at war ... maybe there were these two children who were from different peoples and went to school together. Then, in this war, they were divided. A person, if he is in that war situation, cannot become [a] friend again because war is ugly; one does ugly things.” Indeed, this child is reasoning about the situation opposite to the one considered by Seneca. That is, he is reflecting on the possibility that two people who are friends can become enemies. A classmate clarified, “Yes, but if they went to the same school and were already friends, then the friendship was already born and therefore means they were not enemies.”

Commenting on Cicero’s sentence, the kindergarteners shared experiences that corroborated the presented philosophical idea. For example, one child, who was afraid of the dark, said that when it is dark, he runs away. Then, the researcher asks: “What would a friend do when it’s dark?” The child answers: “He would turn on the light.” Other children connect the need for friendship with the need for care: “A true friend cares for you”; “when you get hurt, a friend comes to cure you.” Another child clarified that a friend supports her in moments of sadness. Referring to a classmate, she said, “She always consoles me when I cry.”

A similar thought emerged in primary school, where a child highlighted, “You need a shoulder to lean on here, that is, because you know he will help you through this bad time, and you need that friend.” In this statement, the child suggested the need to have a friend in a difficult life moment to avoid bearing such moments alone.

In kindergarten, the conversation about the sentence of Simone Weil was encouraged by the researcher through the question, “How do you become friends?” A child answered, “You become friends ... when you go to someone’s house, love each other and play together.” This thought highlights that friendship arises when people share spaces of life and interests, when they spend time and do things together, and when the relationship is nourished by affection.

In primary school, a child interpreted Simone Weil's sentence this way: "Friendships are not given as gifts; they are created." Other children found in the presented philosophical idea an opportunity to reflect on the importance of taking the first step to re-establish a friendly relationship when quarrelling: "If you quarrel with someone, you don't wait for him to apologise, but you go directly to tell [sorry] to him," said a child.

Thoughts and experiences highlighted by children in their comments to the philosophical sentences make clear that friendship is considered important to enhancing one's quality of life and to establishing positive and supportive relationships for the construction of caring communities.

In conclusion, we can state that involving children in reflecting on friendship is not only necessary, as the theoretical framework outlined above made clear, but also possible, as the empirical data have shown.

Conclusion

This article has presented the MelArete project, which is structured on a theory of ethical education conceived as education to virtue in the perspective of care and, consistently, in an educational programme aimed at involving kindergarten and primary school children in reflecting on ethical concepts and experiences.

While preserving the dialogue with the main traditions of ethical education explored in international literature, the theoretical framework on which the MelArete project is based reveals its own originality and innovativeness, particularly in its integration of the Socratic and Aristotelian perspectives about virtue education and in its conceptualization of virtue education within the theoretical horizon disclosed by the philosophy of care. As argued, the focus on friendship makes the second edition of MelArete a project of ethical education for citizenship. Indeed, in line with Aristotle's interpretation, friendship is understood as a political virtue, capable of nurturing caring relationships that foster the flourishing not only of individuals but also of the community.

The MelArete programme designed for kindergarten and primary school children is strictly grounded in the presented theoretical framework. Among the activities designed to engage students in reflecting about the concept and experience of virtues, there is the one presented in this article, which encourages children to think about friendship based on the thoughts of some philosophers. The ideas collected through this activity show the richness of the involved children's ethical thinking, as they were able to engage in dialogue with the presented philosophers, drawing important insights from the philosophical sentences to conceptualize friendship starting from their own experience. In the conversations among students who reflected together on the philosophers' sentences, the process of conceptualization was a co-constructive process, in which each child contributed to the construction of the ideas of friendship by listening to others' perspectives as well as by expressing his or her own, in a mutual enrichment of thought.

The theoretical and empirical parts of this article should be considered closely related: in fact, if the theory of ethical education underlying the MelArete project argues why ethical education is important, the presented educational activity, which is focused on the specific virtue of friendship, shows how ethical education to virtues in the perspective of care can be concretely implemented.

The second edition of the MelArete project is still being implemented in other Italian kindergarten and primary school classrooms, and research is being conducted on the various promoted activities, with the aim to evaluate the program based on a rigorous analysis of the collected data. This article is not the place to delve into the heuristic aspects related to the empirical study we are conducting, but the findings that have emerged so far confirm the effectiveness of the programme in promoting the expression and development of children's ethical thinking. In this article, we have focused on the presentation of some of the children's ideas emerging from the specific activity we described, with the intention also to show the richness and depth of the involved students' ethical thinking in dialogue with the philosophers' selected sentences about friendship.

Friendship is an important experience in children's lives, and encouraging their reflection on it as a virtue, including its significance as a political virtue capable of nurturing caring relationships and communities, is essential to fostering the development of their ethical awareness. The MelArete project aims to reach this goal by bringing ethical education into schools, a privileged place to promote reflection on relationships, care for the others, and the common good.

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Is Pedagogical Ethos Teachable and Learnable? The Development of a Didactic-Methodical Approach for the Practice of Ethos in Teacher Education

Gabriele Schauer and Eveline Christof

Introduction

Teacher education should meet the requirement of training future teachers in the best possible way in terms of subject matter, subject didactics, and pedagogy. The pedagogical profession also demands that attitudes be addressed and conveyed in the context of the tasks and functions of education and society. However, within the context of fields of action in schools, areas of tension and sometimes also of contradiction appear that cannot or be solved satisfactorily by pedagogical action. In this context, Helsper speaks of antinomies, referring to the structures of the school field that are always co-determining or shaping the pedagogical actions of teachers (cf. Helsper, 1996). Therefore teachers (and this includes experienced as well as prospective teachers) are required to take responsibility in challenging school situations based on general moral maxims and to make their own decisions, which should always have the well-being of their students and the best possible learning support as a goal. In situations with an open outcome, therefore, action must be taken individually on the basis of one's own pedagogical ethos. Pedagogical ethos requires the assumption of responsibility for the learning, education, and development of children and adolescents within the framework of a socially legitimized mission and, at the same time, the assumption of personal responsibility for the consequences of actions within one's own sphere of influence (cf. Oser, 2018). Ethos refers to attitudes in regard to one's own principles and how they shape one's actions: ethos involves one's own individual moral decision-making capacity.

1. The Process of Creating a Manual for Teacher Education

The project, which focused on the topic of pedagogical ethos in teacher education, was called ELBE, "Ethos in the Teaching Profession" (ELBE). This resulted in a "Handbook for Practicing a Professional Attitude." The project focused on the connection between fundamental questions of pedagogical ethos and the practicing of ethos in the sense of professionalization. The team of researchers focused on the question "Is pedagogical ethos learnable?" and then, as a consequence, "Is pedagogical ethos teachable in teacher training?" The goal of the work of the 10 researchers—all of them professionals in the field of teacher training—was to create a manual, the ELBE-Manual, to introduce pedagogical ethos as practicing moral decision-making skills in university teacher training. In a research process lasting several years, the German-Austrian research team designed a manual (Rödel, Schauer, Christof, Agostini, Brinkmann, Pham Xuan, Schratz, & Schwarz, 2022) for practicing moral decision-making skills. They engaged in an intensive process of studying the history and current debates surrounding the topic

of pedagogical ethos. Milestones in their own theories of pedagogical ethos for teacher education were drafted, in which reference was also made to current professional theories (cf. Oser et al., 2021, *The International Handbook on Teacher Ethos*, and Schratz et al., 2008, The EPIK Model).

The manual has been designed for application in the field of teacher education, and its intention is to help prospective teachers become familiar with the topic of responsibility and pedagogical ethos within the context of their teaching actions. The manual was designed for practical use in university courses in the field of teacher training. It consists of 24 examples of pedagogical practice. The team of researchers analyzed practical experiences drawn from portfolios of student teachers using the method of document analysis (cf. Hoffmann, 2018). The examples were taken from internship reports of student teachers at the University of Innsbruck and are thus documents reporting lived experience of everyday teaching. They tell of difficulties, ambiguities, and challenges, but also of experiences of successful and “fruitful” moments.

Following the theory work, the team designed a didactic approach for practicing moral decision-making in order to develop pedagogical ethos. The didactical model consists of two bigger parts. The whole process always takes examples from lived experience as its starting points. Firstly, there is a three-step process, in which ethos as a moral decision-making ability, in the sense of Aristotelian *phronesis*, is practiced. The three-step process is composed of (1) looking for individual interpretations and experiences in the context of the example; (2) explaining one’s own positions and personal reasons; (3) expressing irritation regarding the situation and responses and establishing distance from possible interpretations.²⁹ In the second part—called the a-b-c scheme—the ambivalences and ambiguities shown in the examples are discussed, and the ethical premises are taken into account. Firstly, the ‘appropriateness’ of a situational, practical experience of action can only be thematized, assessed and judged in retrospect and, secondly, this ‘appropriateness’ does not consist of acting according to normative guidelines within fixed limits, but of perceiving the particularity of a situation and thus responding and acting in the sense of moral decision-making. Going through this process, (future) teachers get an idea of—and also get in touch with—their pedagogical ethos.

In an empirical phase, the ELBE manual was used in 15 university seminars at three locations—Berlin, Vienna, and Innsbruck—to design seminar sessions, and the testing was accompanied by a survey of the lecturers.

2. *Theoretical Background*

Why is ethos, or more specifically pedagogical ethos, a topic in teacher training? Teacher education should meet the requirement of training future teachers in the best possible way in terms of their subject, but also in terms of didactics and pedagogy. The pedagogical profession also demands that teachers develop appropriate attitudes, because they have to assume important tasks and functions in society, such as socializing, educating, and forming the next generation. A large number of competency models in teacher education are limited to skills and abilities that

²⁹ Irritation refers here to a sense of unease linked to the recognition of ambiguity, uncertainty, or discomfort generated by the depicted situation, while distancing refers to a stepping back from the situation and positioning oneself, recognizing and acknowledging its bothersome aspects. These irritations and the distancing can be triggered by the situation itself, by discussion led by students, or by reflection on questions explicitly introduced by teachers.

professional teachers acquire due to their functions in the school field (cf. EPIK, Schratz & Schrittmesser, 2011, INTASC Standards, COACTIV, Oser 88 Standards, Standards der KMK, ...). In the COACTIV model by Baumert and Kuntner (2011), reference is made to values and beliefs, which also have an influence on teachers' actions. The formula for the professional action of teachers could therefore be stated as follows: Values and beliefs, as well as knowledge and skills, together result in the professional competence of teachers.

However, since pedagogical action cannot be standardized and there is no technology relating to how to act in the classroom (cf. the "technology deficit of education," Luhmann, 1996), the question remains open as to what teachers refer to when making everyday decisions, what ultimately justifies their actions. Competency models and mission statements in teacher education provide standards and normative frameworks for how professional teachers should act, but not for how they should ultimately make their very concrete decisions in a challenging school situation. Professional teacher action is clearly different from non-professional action in a pedagogical situation because teachers do not act in their function from a personal, private perspective, but within the framework of their function, their public mission, which they have to fulfill in the institution of the school. On the one hand, this public mission is framed by rules, structures and norms concerning the school field; on the other hand, it consists of a pedagogical ethos, a moral obligation, which is oriented towards the norms of society and towards one's own moral principles. Pedagogical ethos means taking responsibility for the learning, education, and development of children and adolescents within the framework of a socially legitimized mission and, at the same time, taking personal responsibility for the consequences of actions within one's own sphere of influence (cf. Oser, 2018). Ethos means attitude in the sense of one's own principles that shape one's actions—ethos as one's own individual moral decision-making capacity. When these fundamental principles are related to one's own professional pedagogical actions, this forms a teacher's own pedagogical ethos. However, a teacher's own pedagogical ethos cannot be articulated per se; it exists as a personal principle, but only becomes visible when an immediately unresolvable conflict, a dilemma, a kind of crisis in action, arises that demands a decision and an action. Teachers are often called upon to make a decision and to strike a balance between justice, caring, and truthfulness (cf. Oser, 2018). Ethos as an implicit and situation-bound professional and experiential action cannot be learned or practiced in teacher education, but the moral decision-making ability that manifests itself in an attitude can be trained. In situations with an open outcome, therefore, action must be taken individually on the basis of one's own pedagogical ethos.

What is ethos and, more specifically, pedagogical ethos? Ethos is understood as a sum of values, as a value attitude, or as a responsible attitude. The ethos of teachers can be defined as values and value orientations in professional action. Values and value orientations are standards of orientation and guiding principles by which individuals and groups are guided in their choice of action. One's own pedagogical ethos shows itself in difficult school situations as successful practice, which is based on the moral decision-making ability of a person. In this context, moral decision-making means being aware of one's own judgment patterns, which enables the possibility of alternative judgements as well. For this judgment, it is important to consider what is "right" or "responsible" as an ethical action in a school or classroom setting. This cannot be determined solely by laws or by universal norms and values. We assume that the complexity of moral decisions in a sphere of inter-bodily connection with other actors in pedagogical situations manifests itself as positionings. Positionings represent pre-reflective forms of action and

behavior towards certain situations, individuals, or challenges, which are, however, mostly implicitly structured and can only be made explicit in retrospect. Therefore, it can only be decided in retrospect whether a certain situation involved a form of successful practice and whether professional actions took place. But is pedagogical ethos learnable and, as a consequence, is it then teachable in teacher education?

The thesis in this project was, Ethos cannot be taught in the sense of instruction, but must be trained for and practiced as a moral decision-making ability founded on the basis of a particular example. Therefore, there is a focus on the questions, How does a (prospective) teacher position him/herself in practice on the basis of ethical values and professional experience? How does the (prospective) teacher take up a position with regard to the subject matter and the students and thereby assume pedagogical responsibility?

Based on this thesis that pedagogical ethos cannot be learned or taught, some principles regarding how it is possible to practice pedagogical ethos with students were developed. The practice of pedagogical ethos can be supported with certain steps. These steps comprise finding and justifying different readings of a situation, experiencing phases of irritation and distancing, and recognizing and considering alternative possibilities for action. Another goal is to sensitize teachers to the ambiguities in these practical situations and to practice a reflective approach to the need to make decisions and take responsibility as a teacher, even in ambivalent situations.

3. The Didactical Setting to Develop Pedagogical Ethos

Ethos shows itself as successful practice in which a person positions him/herself or takes a stand and assumes responsibility, on the basis of his or her evaluation and professional experiences. Ethos emerges only in practical situations and in the experience of the situations. Ethos is based on a moral decision-making capacity. This can only be practiced, but not taught in the sense of instruction or didactically guided competence building.

Therefore, a didactical setting was developed in order to practice moral decision-making. The goal of this program is to develop the moral decision-making ability and judgment formation of prospective teachers. The basis of this approach is that ethos in the above sense, as an implicit and situation-bound professional and experience-related action, cannot—strictly speaking—be practiced, but that the moral decision-making ability in the sense of an ethos can be trained. The process is started with short examples from real practices. The examples, as mentioned before, were taken from the internship reports of student teachers at the University of Innsbruck. They are therefore documents reporting lived experience from pedagogical practice.

The three-step process starts (1) with the collection of different ways of reading the presented example. Later, the steps are illustrated with an example. In a next step (2), students are asked to position themselves and justify their attitude. This is followed (3) by a deliberate creation of irritation, such as by taking another position in this situation. Additionally, new alternatives of ways to act can be collected by the students. This is the three-step process “collect-position-irritate.”

The next phase of the process addresses the ambiguities of the situation in the example. An example of the ambiguities in a specific practical situation will be given later.

The last step of this setting—called the a-b-c scheme—also consists of three parts. First (a), a question is asked about ethos as situated action and as successful practice in the example. Then (b), the prospective teachers (the students) look for ethos expressed as an attitude within the context of responsibility. Finally (c), the teacher students' views of ethos as a bodily, resistant statement based on profession-specific and professional experience are gathered.

Now, we will briefly explain why we use examples as a starting point in practicing pedagogical ethos. Günther Buck pinpoints the value of having a specific example. He states that the example “presents a particular with the invitation to consider it from the point of view of the general” (Buck, 1989, p. 98). In the example, the “presentation of a general in the particular” (Lippitz, 1987, p. 116) can be seen. In this case, all the examples are school situations; they have “field character” and show the material quality and concreteness of the specific field which is presented by the example. An example illustrates the intersubjective and thus relational experiences which can be recognized by others more easily. The meaning of an example is not revealed as a rule that can be objectified, but arises in intuitive comprehension.

The aim is to enable student teachers to reflect on and learn from their own subjective experiences, which play a crucial role in shaping their understanding of ethical decision-making within the teaching profession. By analyzing a concrete situation, a multitude of phenomena of the same or an analogous nature can be discovered through reflection and further thinking. Because future situations also belong to the field of the school, they follow the same principles. In working with examples, student teachers precisely gain a recognitional vision of the concrete that contains the possibility of (future) cognition regarding a multitude of phenomena of the same or an analogous nature, obeying the same principles (cf. Buck, 1989, p. 40).

4. An Example of Didactic Implementation

To show how this didactic procedure involving the three-step process works, we will now focus on an example from the manual of the ELBE research group. This example was written by a student during the course of reflecting on the whole teacher education process. This situation seemed to be important enough for him/her to discuss it:

The students seemed to be relatively restless during this lesson, and I had already admonished them once, telling them to be quieter and pay attention. This only lasted for a few minutes and the noise level in the class rose again. I knew this class better by this point and this commotion puzzled me, so I simply asked what was going on today. One student explained to me that two hours ago the math test had taken place and therefore they just couldn't concentrate properly. Then I decided to postpone the—admittedly rather dry—grammar topic until the next lesson and instead play a turn of “Vocabulary King” with them. I had done this exercise with them a few lessons before, and it seemed to me that they had a lot of fun doing it, but they still took it seriously and engaged with English. This seemed like a good compromise for me. (cf. Rödel, Schauer, Christof, Agostini, Brinkmann, Pham Xuan, Schratz, & Schwarz, 2022, p. 50)

It is important to have a look at this example. This situation seems to be one that could happen very often (as mentioned before, cf. Buck, 1989). Yet for the student who wrote this example, it

was special; because this procedure had not been planned to be like this, the student teacher was irritated, and the situation remained in his or her mind. He or she asked himself/herself if he/she was acting right from a professional perspective, if this was a successful practice. In this school situation, you can feel the character of the school field, too. It is not simply like an interview. When someone talks about an incident, here the quality of the material is much higher and more concrete (Lippitz, 1984, p. 16), so that everyone knows what is going on. This experience could be recognized by others in this classroom, and everyone who is a participant in the field of schools can comprehend and talk about this illustration.

An example like this can be part of a seminar for teaching pedagogical ethos because it can provide a starting point for talking about subjective (pre-)experience. In addition to subjective experiences, the examination of one's own subjective theories is also relevant to the discussion of pedagogical ethos and the understanding of school situations. Subjective theories have an action-guiding and action-controlling function (cf. Dann, 1989). They influence the professional actions of teachers (cf. Baumert & Kunter, 2006), and consequently have a significant influence on the planning and implementation of lessons. In addition, they already have an influence on the actions and analysis of the actions of prospective teachers—and so on their own positioning, too. Therefore, to develop one's own professional action and moral decision-making ability, it is necessary to start with an examination of one's own values, one's own subjective theories or beliefs, so as to understand one's own and other perspectives and to discuss them in the context of professionalization.

By analyzing this concrete situation, a multitude of phenomena of the same or an analogous nature can be discovered through reflection and further thinking (cf. Buck, 1989, p. 40). This will be elaborated and illustrated in the next section.

5. The Three-step Process: “Collect—Position—Irritate”

Building on the ELBE project, a small team of university lecturers designed a whole course with six or seven units at three universities in Vienna and Innsbruck. Four lecturers held their entire courses using this didactical procedure in master courses and bachelor courses in teacher education. Some other lecturers included this procedure in their own seminars in just one slot. We stayed in contact with the lecturers, and they collected a considerable amount of feedback from the students involved in these courses. In this way, initial experiences with the didactic approach and the manual were gained. A detailed presentation of the results can be found in Schauer, Christof & Rödel (in press).

The first step in every seminar session dealing with practicing moral decision-making skills is that the students have to read a selected school situation from the ELBE manual. The meaning of an example is not presented as a rule that can be objectified, but arises as intuitive comprehension. It is very important to collect these different ways of reading, in order to understand the situation holistically. This is possible by asking questions like these:

- How do you feel about the situation?
- What comes to your mind?

- Did you have similar experiences?
- Why do you think they act this way in this situation?

It is also possible to talk about similar experiences, or the way anybody would act in such a specific situation. To get a general overview of the situation and not just an individual opinion, it is important to include the subjective thoughts of all individual students. This viewing from the multiple perspectives of the other students is important because it makes it possible to always examine each example from new, previously unknown perspectives and viewpoints. Thus, on the one hand, questions and considerations can be formulated as experience-based and approached from one's own perspective. On the other hand, the plurality of different perspectives is revealed as offering possible and perhaps desirable oppositions for a deeper examination of the underlying realities of a particular school situation (cf. Rödel, Schauer, Christof, Agostini, Brinkmann, Pham Xuan, Schratz, & Schwarz, 2022).

In the next step in this process, the students are asked to position themselves within the context of the example and to justify their position. If we only ask them for reflections, there is nothing fixed. So there are some more questions to discuss:

- What exactly is the “compromise” referred to in the example? How do you judge the compromise?
- Why do you think the teacher/the student teacher is doing the right or wrong thing? How do you explain your conclusions?
- Why do you think your explanation is more correct than those of your colleagues? Defend your explanation in front of the others!
- On which theories or general explanations is your statement—and maybe the explanation of the others—based?
- When you compare your own view with those of your colleagues, where is there consensus and where not, and are there any completely new perspectives?

It is important to position oneself in order to realize one's own subjective theories, one's individual thinking, and also to understand the mental position in the group. It explains how people act or how they would like to act. Moreover, it makes it possible to reflect upon one's own beliefs and pedagogical attitudes.

After reflecting on beliefs and pedagogical attitudes, the next step is to provoke irritation. The purpose of triggering targeted irritation is to create a pause and to distance oneself from the situation. In this way, one's own routines can be questioned. Phenomenological practices, such as bracketing (as a return to judgment—cf. Husserl, 1939), stopping, and interrupting (both seen as a return to experience—cf. Heidegger, 1927, 1949) are significant to this process. Bracketing and thus referring back to judgments (cf. Husserl, 1939) means refraining from making definitive statements and (provisional) judgments about a particular issue, temporarily postponing judgment, as if placing the issue in parenthesis. It is neither a judgment nor a non-judgment (cf. Brinkmann, 2021, p. 40). Stopping (cf. Heidegger, 1927, 1949) or distancing oneself from a situation allows for more time to reflect on the experience (Brinkmann, 2021b, p. 44), making

space for new considerations, thoughts, and the acceptance, perception, and exploration of new ideas. This approach interrupts the usual and normal, as well as familiar routines in one's actions and thinking (cf. Waldenfels, 2007). In this way, familiar orders can be disrupted, allowing new thoughts to arise and to be recognized for their otherness. So, bracketing involves first consciously experiencing and thematizing one's own experiences. This is achieved in the work with examples by collecting one's own perspectives and interpretations. Stopping (as a return to experience—cf. Heidegger, 1927, 1949) occurs when topics or ways of acting are further questioned with additional reflective questions. In interrupting (as stepping back from what is approaching—cf. Waldenfels, 2007), when the research group is triggered by irritations, the participants try to create new perspectives. Thus, one's own actions and arguments are questioned, leading to the emergence of new ways of thinking. The goal is to provoke irritation, promote distancing and encourage reflection, ultimately with the aim to embrace unknown and tacit knowledge, enabling it to be accepted, perceived, seen and felt. In this way, familiar orders can be disrupted and strangeness can be reflected as otherness. This process enables one to “reflexively orient one's own experiences in the horizon of foreignness to other knowledge” (Brinkmann, 2021, p. 190).

The next part of the three-step process demands a positioning of the students in relation to the actions described in the given situation by discussing following questions:

- Take the position of a person standing outside who is only observing the situation, for example another teacher. How does the situation appear to them? Does this other view change your opinion?
- In the description of the scene, we cut the last part; it actually ends like this: “...This seemed like a good compromise to me, *and I had the feeling that it was also very well received by the class.*” If you know this, then how do you evaluate the action, now that you know that the last-minute change of plans “worked”? What exactly “worked” here? Is it “working” from the point of view of the class or from that of individual students?
- Imagine that in the next lesson, a large number of students demand to play the substituted game again. This creates a conflict in the class: a few students say they would rather do a grammar unit because there is a test coming up and they still need to catch up. How would you act in the trainer's place and how would you justify your actions to the students?

First of all, when the students talk about the reactions, everything seems to be clear. Perhaps, at first, the reactions of the teacher, or the thinking we are talking about, seems to be a professional act. But now everything might be different again and not everything would seem to be perfect. This is important for reflection. With this irritating factor included the students have to think about their decisions again, and maybe they reverse them. With this additional loop they develop a distance from the situation and from their own decisions. This step is really important for practicing the moral decision-making ability, and the process of making these decisions shows one's own pedagogical ethos.

5. *Ambiguities of the Situation Described*

The next step is to find ambiguities in the situation, in order to deepen one's own awareness of issues. Each example from the manual (cf. Rödel, Schauer, Christof, Agostini, Brinkmann, Pham Xuan, Schratz, & Schwarz, 2022) contains ambiguities of interpretation and positioning and thus challenges the students to take a stance on the situation described in the example and to engage in discursive discussion with their colleagues. These school situations show conflicts or ambiguities. Ambiguity is a characteristic of practical situations in which positioning is needed. Implementing the different ambiguities in processing the situations can result in different perspectives on professional practice. Thus a professional approach to one's own actions can be discussed. Ethos means responding to this ambiguity with a moral decision-making capacity that is situationally, emotionally, and bodily grounded (cf. Rödel, Schauer, Brinkmann, & Schratz, 2022, p. 171). Accordingly, in this context, moral decision-making ability is grounded in a morality that claims to be universally binding. Otherwise such morality would lack any general binding force.

In this framework, these obligations refer to the responsibilities within the school community and thus to the rules and norms of the educational and schooling system. Building on these considerations and reflections, ambiguities in the examples are identified through the intensive examination of readings, positionings and irritations (three-step). These ambiguities are then discussed with reference to professionalization theories, incorporating the topics addressed in the examples. The focus lies on various areas of tension that are revealed in the examples. These ethical ambiguities are to be deepened in the context of "Ethos in the Teaching Profession." For this purpose, the teachers' decisions discussed in the example are collected, the ethical positioning of these decisions discussed, and the assumptions of responsibility by the persons involved in the example are shown. In addition, the different areas of tension will be illuminated with the help of theoretical references and theoretical literature, which can reinforce positions, but can also cause irritation (cf. Rödel, Schauer, Brinkmann, & Schratz, 2022, p. 173).

In relation to the above situation, the following ambiguities are dealt with by the students:

- Ambiguity 1: Responding vs. not responding (opening vs. not opening).
- Ambiguity 2: Direct control vs. indirect control / direct exercise of power vs. indirect exercise of power / open vs. veiled hierarchies.
- Ambiguity 3: Relationship to the students vs. educational mission.
- Ambiguity 4: The individual vs. the group / inequality vs. equality.

If we focus, for example, on Ambiguity 1) Responding vs. not responding (opening vs. not opening), we have to concentrate on the following passage: "One student explained to me that two hours ago the math test took place and therefore they just couldn't concentrate properly. Then I decided to postpone the—admittedly rather dry—grammar topic until the next lesson and instead play a turn of 'Vocabulary King' with them." To interpret this: the prospective teacher shows empathy in this situation regarding the restlessness of the students and does not simply ignore it and continue with the topic. The student teacher decides to discard the lesson plan and respond to the students by choosing a task that is more fun. The teacher takes a risk that this will cause them to "lag behind" in the material (cf. Rödel, Schauer, Christof, Agostini, Brinkmann, Pham Xuan, Schratz, & Schwarz, 2022). Each example contains ambiguities of interpretation and positioning, and thus challenges the students to take a stance on the situation described in the

example, to participate in discursive discussion and engage with the stances of their colleagues. After the students talk about their reflections on the ambiguities, the next step is to talk about the meaning of these reflections for professionalization too. We can only notice if a teaching reaction is professional after finishing a situation and reflecting upon it.

7. A Model of Teacher Professionalization—EPIK

Another task of the didactic framework is to discuss these ambiguities from the perspective of teacher professionalization. For this purpose, we use a specific model of teacher professionalization, the EPIK model. The EPIK model originates from teacher and school research and was developed by Michael Schratz et al. (2008) at the University of Innsbruck, among others. EPIK is an acronym for *Entwicklung von Professionalität im internationalen Kontext* (“development of (teacher) professionalism in an international context,” Nairz-Wirth, 2011, p. 167). The domain approach of EPIK (cf. Paseka, Schratz & Schritteser, 2011) assumes that the professional action of teachers in school events is manifested in the interaction of the multiple facets of the decisions made in each lesson, depending on the grade level, subject, and type of school. This should also be taken into account when processing the situations from the manual. In order to prepare future teachers for these nuanced requirements in teaching, the necessary competencies in professional action are localized on the level of superordinate cross-sectional topics in the scientific debate and summarized in competency fields, called “domains” in the EPIK approach (cf. Schratz et al., 2008). Thus, this is a normative model with a view to establishing successful action as a professional teacher, and is suitable for a reflexive examination of school situations. The domains are defined as follows:

- REFLECTION AND DISCOURSE means having a critical approach to one[s] own actions, recognizing the nature of a specific situation, developing self-observation strategies, recognizing general truths in specific situations, developing a larger repertoire of choices, and drawing conclusions.
- PROFESSIONAL AWARENESS means being aware of one’s own expertise in a specific subject, realizing the freedom of being a teacher and setting oneself boundaries.
- PERSONAL MASTERY means the power of individual prowess, having one’s own vision, knowing what to do and how to do it at the right time, being able to say why one is doing something and finding one’s own way to handle things.
- COLLEGIALITY means intensifying the form of dialogue, seeing oneself as a member of a professional learning community, being socially competent and open-minded.
- ABILITY TO DIFFERENTIATE mean recognizing pupils’ different learning needs, striving to develop individual learning strategies and having the knowledge and skills to deal with these differences.

In the model of Schratz et al. (2008), professionalism is considered as an expression of professional action. Professionalism in this model refers to professional action. On the one hand, it refers to the further development of the profession in the social context; on the other hand, it refers to the promotion of professional action by individuals (Paseka et al., 2011, p. 8).

The EPIK concept of Schratz et al. (2008) seeks to be understood as a heuristic model to make teachers' actions systematically visible in the context of professionalization (Schrittesser, 2011, p. 112).

Schratz et al.'s (2008) theoretical framework not only includes the five domains, but also refers to the contradictions and tensions within situations. Both the actors and the situation itself are addressed. Thus, considerations for successful practice are very complex and overlap between the given domains. Therefore, these domains of professionalization are interconnected in many ways (Schrittesser, 2011, p. 110).

The task of the trainee teachers is to discuss the common considerations in the context of professionalization, after an intensive examination of a school situation. For this purpose, the positioning and the alternatives for action mentioned are reflected upon once more with regard to the five domains.

Figure 1: EPIK Model (cf. Schratz et al., 2008)

Again, reflective questions will be integrated into the seminar:

- How do the EPIK domains show up in the positioning/alternative actions?
- What normative considerations arise for action?
- What needs to be considered in terms of domain XY for the situation described?
- Is a professional approach to the situation, in relation to all EPIK domains, evident?

Answers to these reflexive questions are intended to facilitate a profession-specific professional exchange for consideration of future courses of action.

8. *Merging Pedagogical Ethos and Teacher Professionalization*

Let us now examine the ambiguities arising from the example, and the arguments based on the theory of professionalization described above. This should explain why a professional teacher would decide for one or the other variant. There are two important elements to practicing ethos in teacher education. First, it is essential to have a theory and a knowledge of pedagogical ethos in order to understand the concept and the topic. Only when the topic itself becomes clear do considerations and exercises about it become understandable. With regard to the second part, namely teacher action and professionalization, it is not enough just to think about pedagogical ethics and practice decision-making skills. It is also important to think about these considerations and the resulting action strategies from the perspective of professionalization.

To return to the situation mentioned before: is it professional to postpone the planned content of a lesson and instead play a game based on students' reactions? In the context of the discussed professionalization model, the domain "reflective and discursive ability" is evident here. In the sense of a reflexive approach, the teacher has reacted empathically, reflected on the actions, and adapted the pedagogical action. However, with regard to the domain "professional awareness," the teacher is also aware of the task of imparting knowledge and making progress with the learning material. The teacher's decision and reaction to this discrepancy relate, one, to the area of Personal Mastery and, two, to his/her own moral attitudes and values. The student teachers' task is to find and discuss these different approaches to professional action in relation to the school situations. Thus, in dealing with the perceived ambiguities, first off, one's own actions, values and moral decision-making ability are to be addressed and, in a further step, these pedagogical actions and arguments are to be analyzed in the context of professionalization in the seminar. Skills such as concentration, error tolerance and ambiguity tolerance, and judgment, and critical faculties, as well as social and moral skills such as empathy, or attitudes such as composure, are all acquired primarily through practice (cf. Rödel, Schauer, Brinkmann, & Schratz, 2022).

9. Student Feedback to This Didactic Approach

The student teachers experienced this practice when dealing with many different school situations by working through them with the three-step process (and additionally the a-b-c scheme) mentioned above. Feedback was obtained from lecturers and, in particular, from students, on whom we want to focus here. In the following, the students' experiences with the topic of "pedagogical ethos" and the related didactic approach are presented. They reported that an "exercise effect" occurred after going through several examples with the same schemes as shown before. Regular use of the same didactic procedure meant a certain security for students in analyzing and finding alternative action considerations. Thus, for the effective practice of a moral decision-making ability, the repetition of the methodological-didactic work with the students was beneficial, and a greater variety of methods would, in their view, have been counterproductive in this case.

Furthermore, well-chosen school situations were also partly responsible for the success of practicing moral decision-making skills. The students were able to connect the given examples very well with their own experiences (as students or teachers), since all examples contained certain aspects which are “very typical” for the school setting. Therefore, for the implementation of pedagogical ethos in teacher education, it is important either to use appropriate school situations (as presented in the manual), or to include the practical experiences and problematic situations which the students themselves have to deal with in their everyday school life. In any case, the students praise the very “practical” and “hands-on” parts of the university didactic implementation. They also really like to bring in their own examples and to discuss them with others in the seminar, because they recognize the relevance of this topic for their own teaching.

However, students initially had difficulty connecting to the school situations from the manual, because some situations did not include a great deal of contextual information, such as the age of the students discussed in the example, or what happened before the situation. Some of the situations intentionally reveal less contextual information so that different perspectives on the situation can be discussed. However, the students commented that it is this contextual information that is perceived to be missing in the examples that is needed before the latter can be productively applied by students and lecturers.

To give some insight into student feedback, here is an excerpt from a final paper:

The most exciting thing for me was to solve my own slipper problem [i.e., a problem pertaining to the dress code]. As trivial as it sounds and [as] insignificant as the situation seems, the question of ethos becomes more important (it doesn't have to be a matter of life or death). Above all, I was concerned about the situation as a pupil, and I could not have said is it the pupil's fault or the teacher's fault. Now I can think about the situation in a completely different and more holistic way, which is a great gain, as many problems in everyday school life will be of this kind (slippers, mobile phones, eating in class, using the toilet, etc...). The examples of the seminar were very wisely chosen according to practical aspects. It is also interesting to reflect on the emotion that arose in part during the discussion, which alone helps to remind oneself from time to time in everyday school life that it is possible to think more clearly with a cool head. (Master course in teacher education studies at the University of Music and Performing Arts Vienna, 2022)

The extent to which the didactic approach of the ELBE manual affects students and their pedagogical ethos are explored in greater depth in the follow-up project PETAL (Pedagogical Ethos of Trainee Teachers, Schauer, 2024).

Conclusion

The feedback from most students who have attended one or more sessions on the concept of pedagogical ethos has shown that they have engaged very deeply with the examples and have been able to take away some ideas, insights, and knowledge for themselves. Beyond the knowledge and skills that can be taught in teacher education, student teachers have many questions and problems that confront them with challenging situations. These situations often

come with many fears of possibly doing the wrong thing in a difficult situation. Students have also come to realize that there are no universally binding values, no universal rules and recipes for crisis situations that they can refer to in the future. What is 'right' or 'responsible' as an ethical action in a school or classroom context cannot be justified by laws or universal norms and values. Any statement made in a situation may be justified by the agent's own convictions—but it may also be otherwise, depending on judgment and justification. Ethical action in pedagogical situations cannot be clearly determined and therefore cannot be taught in teacher education (Haupt et al., 2021). What teacher training can do, however, is to address this issue in education, to help one reflect on one's own beliefs, convictions, and attitudes—one's own pedagogical ethos—and to evaluate it with the help of theoretical approaches. To this end, it is necessary to create opportunities and frameworks in teacher education and to establish appropriate forms for teacher students to practice moral decision-making skills. Ultimately, the work presented here, with examples in the form of case studies, represents an approach that needs to be explored through further research.

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Exploring the Symbiotic Relationship between Dialectics and Dialogical Approaches to Education in the Era of Artificial Intelligence: A Philosophical Perspective

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Introduction

Dialectic and dialogue are commonly recognized as distinct approaches to learning and intellectual development, with their relationship being a topic of debate within the international academic community. The central question revolves around whether meaning is achieved through the integration of different perspectives (dialectic) or through the emergence of diverse perspectives (dialogue). Advocates of the dialectical approach argue that meaning is constructed through the synthesis of diverse perspectives, while proponents of the dialogical approach assert that meaning arises from the differences in perspectives. However, this relationship is complex. I contend that these approaches are interdependent and mutually evolving. Unity cannot exist without differences, and differences are not recognized unless we strive to unite various perspectives. The unity of different perspectives is provisional, and different interpretations of the unified perspectives give rise to new perspectives, which are subject to continual (re)unification. Epistemologically, I understand dialectics as a method of reasoning employed to explore truth through dialogue (Nikulin, 2010). Dialectic and dialogue are inseparable; one cannot exist without the other. There appears to be a symbiotic relationship between dialectic and dialogue, and exploring this relationship may transform educational practices that are often divided into either dialectic or dialogue. Transforming educational practices entails creating learning environments that are profoundly participatory, interactive, and collaborative. This approach fosters shared understanding, cultivates agency, and promotes the co-development of individuals as diversely competent beings. Through dialogue and dialectical engagement, learners participate in collective knowledge construction, thereby empowering themselves to take ownership of their educational journeys while embracing a multitude of perspectives and capabilities. Such an approach nurtures holistic growth, equipping individuals to navigate and to contribute meaningfully to an interconnected and complex world.

In this paper, I argue for the symbiotic relationship between dialectic and dialogue by drawing on the works of several scholars (for example, Buber, 1944; Mirković, 1980; Baxter & Montgomery, 1996; Nikulin, 2006; Douglas, 2010; Hegel, 2018; Dafermos, 2018), who provide insights into the complex, contradictory, and reconciliatory relationship between the two concepts. I also attempt to discuss how dialectic and dialogue can be construed in the era of artificial intelligence systems, with which human actors can have an endless dialogue about any topic of interest. Before engaging in the philosophical debates on this topic, I will first present distinct discussions regarding dialectic and dialogue. Following this, I will examine the symbiotic relationship between the two and their application in educational practices. This

exploration will include an assessment of the impact of AI on both dialectic and dialogue. Finally, I will provide a concluding note on the interconnectedness of dialogue and dialectic.

Dialectic

Dialectic traces its origins back to ancient Greece, where it was developed by philosophers such as Socrates, Plato, and Aristotle. The term “*dialectic*” is derived from the Greek word “*dialektiké*,” which means “*art of conversation*.” Billig (1987) suggests that the Sophist Protagoras was the first to assert that every issue has two opposing lines of argument. Views, opinions, or attitude exist where there is a context of controversy and contradictions. However, the Greek philosophers most closely associated with dialectical methods are Socrates and Plato, who viewed dialectic as the pursuit of truth through reasoned discussion and the resolution of contradictory arguments, as illustrated masterfully in Plato’s Socratic dialogues. Plato held dialectic in such high regard that he proposed in his republic that philosophers receive training in it (Baxter & Montgomery, 1996).

According to Kahn (1979), Heraclitus, an ancient Greek philosopher born around 535 BCE in Ephesus, was renowned for his philosophical contributions centered on the concept of change and flux in the natural world. He is often referred to as the “Philosopher of Change.” Heraclitus proposed that everything in the universe is in a constant state of transformation. Kahn translates Heraclitus as saying,

One cannot step twice into the same river, nor can one grasp any moral substance in a stable condition, but it scatters and again gathers: it forms and dissolves, and approaches, and departs.... [A]s they step into the same river, others and still other waters flow upon them. (Kahn, 1979, p. 52)

Although dialectical elements can be identified in the writings of mediæval and early modern philosophers like Augustine, Aquinas, Descartes, Spinoza, Kant, and Rousseau, Mirković (1980) argues that dialectics became a distinct philosophical worldview in the nineteenth century through the works of the German philosopher Hegel and his student Karl Marx. In Hegelian-Marxian dialectics, the influence of Heraclitus’s dialectical view of the universe was crucial.

Baxter & Montgomery (1996) state that Hegel was dedicated to philosophical idealism, positing that human reason, or thought, serves as a creative force underlying both the natural world and the driving force of human history. His intellectual endeavors are evident in his attempts to formulate a philosophy of consciousness development and, by extension, an ontology of reality, conceptualizing reality as a manifestation of mind. Each concrete entity exists within a totality defined by what it is not, emphasizing constant motion, development, and change.

Hegel’s perspective on truth involves the realization of the interconnectedness and fluidity of phenomena, a concept he terms “*becoming*.” Criticizing the prevailing philosophy of his era, Hegel rejected the representation of phenomena as autonomous, finite, and fixed entities, referred to as “*being*.” Instead, he proposed that our perception of phenomena is organized around the principle of “*Nothing*,” signifying that our understanding of something relies on an awareness of its negation. This understanding acknowledges that everything undergoes

continuous flux and transitions to new forms through the interplay of opposing forces. Consciousness, according to Hegel, is the synthesis of Being, Nothing, and/or Becoming—an understanding that a phenomenon and its opposite merge, and each immediately vanishes due to the presence of the other (Hegel, 2018). Hegel considered Becoming a higher truth, a deeper reality than the static superficialities of Being, whether applied to the development of individual consciousness or the evolution of societal knowledge. He viewed Becoming as the teleological unfolding of the idea or *Spirit (Geist)*—the immanent and rational order of the universe. The theological implications of *Geist* are evident, as Hegel envisioned Becoming as an evolutionary process through which humanity comprehends God’s plan for the universe.

Contradiction, arising from the interplay of Being and Nothing, was not perceived by Hegel as a negative phenomenon, but rather as essential for achieving the heightened consciousness of Becoming. However, it is important to note that Hegel’s philosophy and theology primarily revolve around the consciousness of the mind, with indirect implications for social experiences. Hegel asserted that ideas hold precedence and shape the world (Gordon, 2022), emphasizing the need for a thorough understanding of ideas before their effective implementation into the material realm.

Karl Marx undertook the task of formulating a dialectics of social experiences, building upon Hegel’s dialectics as the groundwork for his own theory, termed dialectical materialism (Baxter & Montgomery, 1996; Dafermos, 2018). However, Marx diverged from Hegel’s idealism and embraced a materialistic interpretation of reality. He argued that the ideal is a mere reflection of the material world shaped by human activity, in contrast to Hegel’s notion of the ideal as an existing concept of the mind (Marx, 1961, cited in Baxter & Montgomery, 1996). According to Marx, consciousness is rooted in the actuality of people’s existence rather than in ideas independent of the material world, as posited by Hegel.

Central to everyday life is the process of production, where individuals engage in activities to satisfy fundamental needs such as the acquisition of food, drink, shelter, and clothing. This organization of production gives rise to the division of labor, resulting in alienation among workers due to their fragmented control over productive activities. Consequently, this division of labor leads to exploitation, generating private property and capital for the ruling class. Despite these challenges, humans possess the capacity for consciousness, enabling them to reflect on their oppressive circumstances and create new material conditions that liberate them from such oppressions.

Mirkovic (1980) argues that Marx was the first scholar to systematically incorporate a social scientific perspective into the study of dialectics. Marx transposed Hegel’s dialectics from the realm of the mind into the tangible practices of society. Rather than disregarding consciousness, Marx reimagined it as a social phenomenon. His contribution to the study of dialectics was significant, as he was the first to apply a social scientific approach to this field. Prior to Marx, dialectics had largely been confined to the mind, as expounded by Hegel. However, Marx revolutionized this approach by moving the dialectical method from abstract thought to the concrete practices and dynamics of society. In doing so, he sought to ground dialectical thought in the material conditions and social relations that constitute human existence.

One of Marx's significant departures from Hegel's dialectics was his emphasis on the material and social dimensions of human experience. While Hegel's dialectics predominantly focused on the evolution of ideas and consciousness, Marx redirected attention to the material conditions of production, exchange, and class relations. In this manner, Marx aimed to illustrate that dialectical processes are not merely abstract concepts but are profoundly rooted in the concrete realities of social existence.

Moreover, Marx's reimagining of consciousness as a social phenomenon was a pivotal contribution to the study of dialectics. Rather than dismissing or downplaying the role of consciousness, Marx recognized its significance within the social fabric. Consciousness, in Marx's view, is not an isolated or individualistic phenomenon, but is shaped and influenced by the broader social and historical context in which individuals are situated. This understanding of consciousness as a social product has profound implications for how we comprehend human agency, ideology, and the dynamics of social change.

In essence, Marx's incorporation of a social scientific perspective into the study of dialectics laid the groundwork for a more holistic and materialist understanding of human history and society. By shifting the focus from abstract metaphysical concepts to the concrete realities of social life, Marx's approach has had a lasting impact on fields such as sociology, anthropology, and critical theory. It has also opened up new avenues for exploring the interplay between structure and agency, power and resistance, and the complexities of social transformation.

Mirkovic's (1980) assertion that Marx was a trailblazer in systematically integrating a social scientific perspective into the study of dialectics is well-founded. Marx's reconfiguration of dialectical thought not only expanded the horizons of this intellectual tradition, but also enriched our understanding of the intricate interconnections between thought, society, and history. As we continue to grapple with the complexities of contemporary social life, Marx's insights into dialectics serve as a compelling reminder of the enduring relevance of his contributions to social theory and praxis.

Baxter & Montgomery (1996) observe that dialectics has evolved into broader interpretations: ontological and epistemological perspectives. Dialectics as ontology involves the comprehension of reality as a dynamic interplay characterized by the conflict of opposing forces. In this context, it emphasizes the inherent dynamism and transformative nature of the world, where conflicting elements engage in a perpetual process of change and development. On the other hand, dialectics as epistemology constitutes a method of reasoning that seeks understanding through the collision of divergent arguments. This approach to dialectics focuses on the process of acquiring knowledge and insights through the confrontation and synthesis of opposing viewpoints. It implies a methodical engagement with contradictory perspectives, fostering a deeper and more nuanced understanding of complex phenomena.

These dual facets of dialectics, whether viewed as an ontological framework or an epistemological approach, contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the dynamic and interconnected nature of reality, both in terms of its inherent characteristics and the methods employed in the pursuit of knowledge. The interplay between ontological and epistemological

dimensions enriches the philosophical discourse surrounding dialectics, offering insights into the intricate relationships and transformations that shape our perception of the world.

In my opinion, the process of attempting to synthesize ideas does not simply involve closing off existing ideas, but rather allows for the emergence of new ideas and the expansion of possibilities for dialogue. When we engage in the act of synthesis, we are not merely seeking to reach a conclusion or find a single solution. Instead, we are opening ourselves up to the potential for new connections, insights, and perspectives to emerge. By bringing together different ideas, perspectives, and information, we create the opportunity for a richer and more nuanced understanding of a given topic or issue. This process of synthesis is essential for fostering innovation, creativity, and critical thinking. It enables us to move beyond the limitations of binary thinking and explore the complexities and nuances of the world around us. Through synthesis, we can uncover new possibilities, challenge assumptions, and generate novel approaches to solving problems. In this way, synthesis serves as a catalyst for intellectual growth and the advancement of knowledge. It encourages us to embrace the inherent complexity of the world and to engage in open, inclusive, and dynamic dialogue that allows for the co-creation of new ideas and perspectives.

In the next section, I will discuss the phenomenon of dialogue.

Dialogue

Like dialectics, the genesis of dialogue traces back to the ancient Greek word for conversation. The term “*dialogue*” is etymologically rooted in the Greek words “*dia*” and “*logos*,” signifying “through” and “speech” respectively. The early documented instance of written dialogue is discerned in Plato’s philosophical writings, where he employed this format to delve into intricate ideas and arguments through the interactions of characters. This form of philosophical dialogue emerged as a prominent feature of ancient Greek intellectual life, with influential thinkers like Socrates, Aristotle, and others utilizing it as a means of inquiry and debate. Various kinds of dialogue, including political, philosophical, and dramatic forms, historically surfaced in Ancient Greece (Dafermos, 2018). Dialogue involves an exchange and the alternation of questions and answers.

According to Maranhao (1990), tracing back to Plato, dialogue persistently occupies a programmatically liminal position, characterized by its interstructural nature—existing between two states or conditions. It remains essentially unstructured, deliberately avoiding closure and finality, perpetually serving as a vehicle for reshaping old elements into new patterns (Turner, 1967, pp. 97-98, as cited in Maranhao, 1990, p. 47). Dialogue serves as a meeting ground, *communitas*, manifesting itself in diverse spontaneous and ritual modes of discourse, where nature and structure converge.

Maranhao (1990) discusses the significance of dialogue within the context of the modern hermeneutic tradition, drawing on the perspectives of scholars such as Gadamer, Ricœur, and Bakhtin. These scholars emphasize the interconnected nature of speech, highlighting its intertextual and interlocal dimensions. Plato’s dialogues, for instance, not only juxtapose ideas and concepts, but also involve interlocutors who represent both real and unreal beings. The

focus of these dialogues is not on events and causality, but rather on understanding abstract concepts such as justice, the good, and truth. The aim is to explore how these concepts can be articulated and comprehended more deeply. While Aristotle structured dialogues around dramatic plots and themes, reflecting temporal sequences, Plato's dialogues lack systematicity and definitive conclusions. However, scholars argue that Plato's dialogues exhibit varying degrees or different types of systematicity. Long (2013) asserts that Plato perceives philosophy as a process characterized by continuous questioning rather than by the provision of definitive answers; consequently, Plato's dialogues are designed to stimulate readers to engage in independent thought rather than merely assimilating the ideas of the authors. This approach mirrors Socrates' dialectical method, which entails the questioning and critical examination of ideas.

Moreover, Socrates, a central figure in these dialogues, often presents contradictory viewpoints, underscoring the fluid and dynamic nature of dialogue. This stands in contrast to Aristotle's view of dialectic as a method for testing propositions and establishing arguments. Overall, the tradition of dialogue as expounded by these scholars underscores its multifaceted and evolving nature, characterized by the blending and crossing of voices rather than the rigid delineation of positions.

According to Nikulin (2006), dialogue assumes the status of a distinctive form—a written emulation of oral discourse—without which human existence as individuals and the expression of selfhood would be unattainable. Aristotle, in his contributions to dialogue, introduced innovations that transitioned it from spontaneous live conversation towards a more rationalized literary genre. One such innovation is Aristotle's incorporation of a prooemion, which systematically employs an alternation of short rejoinders with extensive reasoned accounts, a method frequently utilized by Plato. Nikulin (2006) also references Martin Buber's categorization of dialogue into three types. The first type is real dialogue, regarded as the only one of genuine value, in which each participant seeks the other in their uniqueness, endeavoring to establish a "living" communication. Real dialogue can manifest through both words and silence. For Bakhtin, real dialogue represents the fundamental and classic form of speech, communication, and interaction. Technical dialogue emerges from the attempt to convey and exchange information, while monologue masquerading as dialogue involves individuals ostensibly addressing others but essentially speaking to themselves, futilely attempting to escape their selfhood.

Three modes of perceiving another person are outlined by Martin Buber (Nikulin, 2006). The first mode is observation (*Beobachten*), which entails the analysis of objective characteristics in the other. The second mode is contemplation or looking on (*Betrachten*), wherein one anticipates spontaneous revelations without deliberate pursuit. The third mode is penetration or in-becoming (*innewerden*), which occurs when the other communicates, thereby entering one's life through an appeal. Unlike the first two modes, this mode of perception does not seek to define the essence of the other, recognizing the potential inclusion of entities beyond human beings, such as animals, plants, or stones. The capacity for dialogue fundamentally characterizes the human being as one who possesses a voice or, more precisely, as a pure voice. Each speaking voice yearns to be heard, and every heard voice longs for a response, thereby illustrating the intrinsic desire for dialogue.

Mikhail Bakhtin, a prominent Russian intellectual renowned for his dialogic theory, is regarded by some as one of the most influential intellectual figures of the 20th century (Holquist, 2002). He critiqued the prevailing linguistic, literary, philosophical, and political theories of his time for their tendency to monologize human experience. Bakhtin (1984) aimed to challenge closed, determinate, and totalizing concepts that obscured the open, unfinalizable, and heterogeneous nature of social life. His analysis particularly emphasized the literary genre of the novel as an exemplar of dialogic expression. The essence of dialogue lies in its simultaneous differentiation from and fusion with the other. Parties engaged in dialogue must integrate perspectives while preserving the uniqueness of individual viewpoints. In contrast to monologue, dialogue is characterized by multivocality, encompassing the presence of at least two distinct voices. Bakhtin (1981) posited that all processes arise from the contradictory unity of two opposing tendencies: the centripetal forces of unity and the centrifugal forces of difference. The multivocality of social reality emerges through the contradictory interplay of these centripetal and centrifugal forces.

The self is constructed in the ongoing interplay of the centripetal and the centrifugal. According to Bakhtin, the self is possible only in the fusion with another: “I achieve self-consciousness, I become myself only by revealing myself to another, through another and with another’s help.... Cutting oneself off, isolating oneself, closing oneself off, those are the basic reasons for loss of self” (Bakhtin, 1981, as quoted in Todorov, 1984, p.96). Self is constructed out of the two contradictory necessities—the need to connect with another (the centripetal force) and the simultaneous need to separate from the other (the centrifugal force). The centripetal and centrifugal dialogue is the indeterminate process in which the self is in a perpetual state of becoming, a consequence of the ongoing interplay between fusion with and separation from others.

The social life is an ongoing dynamic tension between forces of unity and difference, order and disorder. The interplay cannot be reduced to a single, static binary opposition: centripetal and centrifugal forces are multiple, varied, and everchanging in the immediate context of the moment. The tension between centripetal and centrifugal themes, beliefs, ideologies, and values takes concrete form in everyday interaction practices of social life.

The concept of chronotope is important in understanding the contexted nature of centripetal and centrifugal forces. Chronotope literally means “time-space” (Bakhtin 1981, p. 84), and the term captures the notion that everyday dialogue is enacted in a concrete temporal-spatial context. “Every entry into the sphere of meaning is accomplished only through the dates of chronotope” (Bakhtin, 1981, p. 258). Chronotopes both constrain and enable human dialogue. Chronotopes that have become standardized through shared meanings constrain the range of communicative events that are regarded as appropriate in those contexts. Technology as standardized chronotopes can limit the possibilities of dialogue. For example, a married couple might have a shared understanding that confrontational exchanges between them are inappropriately enacted in public settings or late in the evening when they are tired. A chronotope that serves as a common temporal-spatial locale for the enactment of certain communicative events has a chronotopic aura that facilitates those events. For example, candlelight and flowers might have an aura of romance for a couple that facilitates the enactment of intimacy. People shape their

chronotopic landscape, and in turn their shared chronotopes influence the dialogues and meanings that can be sustained.

In alignment with Marx, Bakhtin viewed individual consciousness as a social process rather than the cognitive workings of an autonomous entity (Baxter & Montgomery, 1996). However, unlike Marx, Bakhtin did not confine his conceptualization of the social milieu to economic production. For Bakhtin, social reality encompasses all aspects of human experience constituted through communicative or symbolic practices. Consequently, Bakhtin's understanding of consciousness extends beyond class consciousness to include all foundations of conscious awareness concerning oneself and others.

Thus, dialogue is a fundamental aspect of human existence, providing the foundation for growth, understanding, and meaning making. It serves as the arena in which individuals navigate experiences, exchange ideas, and construct their understanding of the world. Beyond individual interactions, dialogue is pivotal to cultural and societal development. Through dialogue, communities negotiate values, address shared challenges, and envision collective futures. In this context, dialogue functions as both a method and an ethos, embodying a commitment to mutual respect, collaborative inquiry, and the co-creation of meaning. Dialectic complements dialogue by acting as a dynamic force that expands its scope, fostering critical thinking, analysis, and the examination of contrasting perspectives. This interplay between dialogue and dialectic creates a mutually reinforcing relationship, wherein each element shapes and enhances the other. Dialogue provides the contextual framework within which dialectic operates, while dialectic enriches dialogue by driving it towards greater depth, complexity, and understanding. Together, dialogue and dialectic form a symbiotic relationship that is essential for both individual growth and societal progress. Their interplay not only deepens collective understanding but also enables critical engagement with the world around us.

In the subsequent section, I will examine this symbiotic relationship in greater detail.

Symbiotic Relationship between Dialectic and Dialogue

From a philosophical standpoint, symbiosis transcends a mere biological association between different species. It is not simply defined as “any association between different species” or “persistent mutualism,” but rather as a profound interconnection that becomes “a source of new capabilities” and modes of existence (Douglas, 2010, pp 5-13). In its essence, symbiosis reflects the complex web of life, wherein the relationships among species are not static, but dynamic, revealing an ongoing dialogue between cooperation, coexistence, and competition. It underscores the intertwining of life in a manner that provides new insights into the nature of existence and relationality. Such symbiotic relationships may range from mutually beneficial to neutral or harmful. For instance, mutualism is exemplified in the relationship between bees and flowers, where both species derive benefits from pollination and nectar collection. Conversely, parasitism is observed in the interaction between ticks and mammals, with ticks benefiting from feeding on the mammals' blood. Predation is illustrated by the relationship between lions and zebras, where the lion benefits from killing and consuming the zebra. These relationships can be extrapolated to human interactions in various contexts; however, this paper primarily draws inspirations from the conceptualization of symbiosis as mutual beneficialism and as a source of

novel creativity and imagination, particularly in the context of the interplay between dialogue and dialectic.

However, the symbiotic relationship between dialectic and dialogue is often overlooked due to the varying orientations and appropriations of dialectic and dialogic worldviews, which align with the prevailing socio-political narratives in different societies. This oversight can also be attributed, in part, to a superficial understanding (though I do not claim a comprehensive understanding either) and the disciplinary siloing of these two approaches to learning and intellectual development. Research indicates that the integration of dialogue and dialectic fosters active participation and promotes the creative process in learning and supervision (Gordon, 2022; Yerushalmi, 2024).

Tracing interconnected links between dialogue and dialectic to the Greek term for conversation, Fink (2012) posits that the literary genre of dialogue emerged through the ingenuity of Socrates' adherents, who sought to provide a written manifestation of dialectic. Dialogue embodies a conversational style of philosophical reasoning that necessitates the involvement of two individuals: the questioner and the respondent. The questioner prompts the respondent to assert a position, and subsequently subjects this assertion to scrutiny through a series of interrogative steps. The questioner aims to lead the respondent to refute the initial assertion through the process of addressing these questions. If successful, the respondent is refuted; otherwise, the initial assertion may endure, at least temporarily. A notable virtue of dialectic lies in the fact that the questioner is not obligated to possess expertise in the subject under discussion. This characteristic rendered the role of the questioner particularly suitable for Socrates, who famously asserted that his wisdom resided in acknowledging his lack of substantial knowledge on any given subject. The virtue of "holy insecurity" encapsulates a willingness to suspend assumptions, engage collaboratively in the exploration of alternative ideas, and permit new understandings to emerge. Within this framework, the binary of "either-or" is supplanted by the integrative approach of "both-and" wherein alternatives are synthesized, and complexity is embraced. This process culminates in apperception—a heightened awareness of all entities as interconnected and part of a larger whole (Scott, 2011). Scott further contends that this perspective embodies the essence of Buber's philosophy: an overarching consciousness of interconnectedness paired with a unifying apperception. To possess this virtue entails recognizing not only the relationships among the components within a system but also the dynamic interplay between oneself and others.

Dialectic, as explained by Cronenberg and Headley (2019), moves beyond the binary approach of absolute acceptance or rejection of a proposition or the competitive determination of the superiority of one participant's ideas. Instead, it is a dynamic process aimed at expanding knowledge, synthesizing ideas, and fostering improvement. Within this process, participants sequentially pose questions, identify contradictions within propositions, and collaboratively develop new perspectives, which remain provisional and open to further inquiry. This collective endeavor enables the exploration of diverse viewpoints, the scrutiny of relevant aspects, and the contemplation of alternatives. While deliberations may sometimes lead to an entirely new proposition, the dialectic process typically retains certain elements of the original proposition, ensuring continuity and openness to dialogue. The resultant propositions preserve characteristics of their predecessors while integrating new elements, potentially sourced from additional inputs,

thereby contributing to a continuous evolution (Farjoun, 2018). Consequently, dialectics should not be perceived as a rigid process aimed at achieving a shared understanding; rather, it is a dialogic process of integrating diverse perspectives to reach a shared understanding at the moment of discourse.

According to Gordon (2022), the concept of dialogue has a longstanding presence in human interactions, predating recorded history. However, scholarly attention directed toward dialogue, as it is currently understood, has emerged more recently in comparison to the extensive focus on dialectic. Scott (2011) elaborates on Buber's concept of dialogue by identifying seven virtues that are essential to meaningful and transformative conversations. These virtues include *awareness*, which involves focusing on the other, listening, and understanding their perspectives, while also being mindful of our own thoughts, feelings, and words. *Confirmation* refers to respecting the other as an equal and thoughtfully acknowledging their views, even in disagreement. *Empathic* inclusion involves connecting personally with the other's situation, allowing one to share their experiences. *Presence* emphasizes active engagement, where individuals respond authentically and commit to both learning from and expressing themselves to the other, while maintaining personal convictions and affirming the identity of their dialogue partner. Additionally, *openness* is the virtue of receptivity to new ideas and perspectives, remaining flexible and willing to expand one's views. *Mutuality* speaks to the shared responsibility of both participants in the dialogue, engaging in a reciprocal exchange that influences and shapes each other's understanding. Lastly, *trust* is fundamental, providing a foundation where individuals can be vulnerable and honest without fear of judgement or manipulation. Together, these virtues foster a dynamic, respectful, and productive dialogue, promoting both personal and collective growth.

Bakhtin, another advocate of dialogue, posited that one's identity and development are achievable only through relationships with others (Defermos, 2018). He envisioned a world composed of multiple voices and meanings, asserting that truth emerges through collective exploration and dialogue among interested parties. For Bakhtin, "voice" encompasses not only the individual's vocal expression but also theories, perspectives, or propositions. While he emphasized the importance of individual voices, Bakhtin also advocated for the merging of these voices to create a shared perspective (Baxter, 2004).

Although Bakhtin is often said to have opposed dialectics in the search for universal rationality, which might undermine the emergence of multiple voices (Matusov, 2011), Brandist (2002) suggests that Bakhtin may have contrasted dialogue with structuralism—specifically, with structuralism's focus on linguistic meaning while excluding the various dimensions of meaning conveyed by subjects. As cited by Brandist, Bakhtin stated that "dialectics was born from dialogue in order to return to dialogue at a higher level (a dialogue of personalities)" (p. 168). This suggests that Bakhtin may have preferred the concept of a "dialogic dialectic," which is fundamentally rooted in the interaction between multiple voices, perspectives, and subjects. According to Bakhtin, dialectics is not a monological progression; it begins within dialogue and ultimately returns to it at a "higher level." This "higher level," which he terms a "dialogue of personalities," reflects a more advanced form of interaction in which individuals engage in mutual recognition and development. This underscores Bakhtin's belief that dialectics, in its most authentic form, is an open, ongoing process driven by continuous, dynamic exchanges

between participants. In this model, dialectics evolves through dialogue, with each conversation shaping and transforming the others involved.

Nikulin (2010) views dialogue as the foundational origin of dialectic, characterized by spontaneity and unpredictability. However, dialectic aspires to emancipate itself from its foundational origin, seeking to transcend it and efface the remnants of the dialogical within its structure, evolving into a rigorous science and method. While dialogue fosters open-ended exchange and unpredictability, dialectic pertains to the art of probing and debating the veracity of opinions, directed at uncovering latent contradictions and tensions. This relationship underscores a tension where dialectic depends on dialogue for its genesis but seeks independence by prioritizing logical analysis over spontaneity. Thus, dialectic conversation is centered on the synthesis of arguments with the goal of resolving differences, whereas dialogic conversation seeks to establish a space for reciprocal accommodation without necessarily achieving resolution. In the realm of personal relationships, relational dialectics, as articulated by Baxter and Montgomery (1996), manifests as a uniquely patterned and intricately colored communicative phenomenon. Within this framework, the dialogic complexities inherent in personal communication are woven with common dialectical threads, including contradiction, change, praxis, and totality.

Similarly, in contrast to Bakhtin, who asserts that dialectic reduces voices, emotions, and ideas to a singular abstract consciousness (Rule, 2011), Freire (1970; 1974) posits that dialogue and dialectic are mutually interconnected. True dialogue possesses a dialectical nature, characterized by the interaction of opposing ideas, which can be referred to as dialectical dialogue, essential for the development of critical consciousness. This form of dialogue enables participants to critically examine their social reality, fostering the continuous emergence of new understandings. The ultimate aim of dialectical dialogue is to promote social transformation and emancipation. Praxis, in Freire's philosophy, represents the synthesis of dialectical tension and dialogical engagement, uniting reflection and action for social change. Through dialogue, individuals critically examine their conditions, while the dialectic reveals underlying contradictions, enabling transformative action. Freire's approach weaves these elements together to advocate for an education system that fosters critical consciousness and human liberation, transforming learning into an active, co-creative process that addresses societal inequalities.

In a similar vein, Ravenscroft et al. (2007) argue that dialectic and dialogue, rather than being contradictory, are complementary in nature, each highlighting distinct yet essential aspects of the learning process. They describe dialectic as addressing the cognitive dimension, while dialogue engages the social and emotional facets. Together, these dimensions foster both mutual understanding and the pursuit of reasoned consensus, which are synergistic rather than conflicting. The authors further suggest that the balance between dialectic and dialogue in effective learning depends on the specific context. Similarly, Williams and Ryan (2020) propose that decisions reached through dialectic should not be seen as fixed endpoints but as provisional conclusions subject to practical testing. This iterative process involves ongoing dialogue and subsequent refinement. Dafermos (2018) adds that both dialectical thinking and dialogue are inherently continuous and open-ended processes. As they evolve historically, they create new opportunities for mutual enrichment and sharing, potentially leading to transformative and unpredictable outcomes.

Thus, based on the above discussion, it is obvious that the interrelationship between dialogue and dialectics is grounded in their complementary and symbiotic functions, wherein each enriches the other through a dynamic process of communication and critical engagement. Dialogue serves as a space for individuals to express diverse viewpoints, fostering an open environment for the sharing of perspectives and experiences. Conversely, dialectics provides the structured framework necessary for the critical analysis of these perspectives, aiding individuals in identifying contradictions and reconciling opposing viewpoints, while also allowing for the emergence of new, nuanced understandings. This relationship is integral to meaningful communication and the cultivation of critical thinking. Dialogue establishes the platform for ideas to emerge, whereas dialectics equips individuals with the tools to scrutinize, synthesize, and refine these ideas. Collectively, they facilitate constructive conversations that challenge preconceptions and promote deeper insights into complex issues. Beyond individual exchanges, this interplay extends into broader social and cultural contexts, where dialogue fosters inclusivity, empathy, and mutual respect, and dialectics encourages the critical examination of social structures, beliefs, and power dynamics, thereby contributing to societal progress and transformation.

This dynamic relationship between dialogue and dialectics enables different voices to emerge, converge, and diverge, thereby expanding the horizons of critical thinking, consciousness, and both individual and social transformation. Dialogue allows for the expression of diverse perspectives, while dialectics provides a framework for evaluating and synthesizing these viewpoints, fostering deeper reflection and the potential for transformation. Through this process, individuals engage with one another in ways that challenge preconceived notions, enhance understanding, and contribute to the rethinking of social structures and norms. Consequently, both personal growth and collective progress are facilitated, with dialogue and dialectics serving as catalysts for the continuous evolution of ideas and social change.

This synthesis between dialogue and dialectics underscores their reciprocal relationship, wherein dialogue facilitates the emergence of ideas, while dialectics offers the critical framework necessary to test, refine, and transform those ideas. This interplay allows for contestation and contradiction, which in turn creates new opportunities for dialogue. Consequently, this symbiotic relationship is essential for the genuine transformation of individuals and their social development.

In educational practices, Bakhtin's theory of dialogism is often associated with dialogic approaches, while Vygotskii's cultural-historical theory aligns more closely with dialectic methods. However, contemporary interpretations of sociocultural theories that draw from Vygotskii's work frequently eschew explicit references to dialectics. There is an ongoing debate regarding the compatibility and irreconcilability of the dialogic and dialectic approaches advocated by thinkers in the context of education. Matusov (2011) is among the scholars who argue for the perceived incompatibility and irreconcilability of Vygotskian and Bakhtinian approaches to education. He posits that Vygotskii's ideas are rooted in Hegelian universalism, characterized by a monological, developmental (diachronic), and activity-based philosophy, whereas Bakhtin's ideas are pluralistic, fundamentally synchronic, dialogic, and centered on discourse and genre-based approaches that embrace the coexistence of competing and conflicting

ideas. Matusov further contends that Vygotskii's sociohistorical approach is instrumental, defining consciousness through activity and mediation, while Bakhtin's perspective is ontological, defining consciousness through embodied experience, responsibility, respect, relationships, and dignity. Nonetheless, I contend that this interpretation oversimplifies and inadequately captures the complexities inherent in the contributions of both thinkers.

In contrast, Stetsenko (2007) advocates for the integration of the perspectives of both Vygotskii and Bakhtin, positing that such compatibility can enhance the ethical dimensions of human learning and development. She argues that both scholars advanced a deeply relational understanding of human development and consciousness, fostering an agentic, activist stance toward human life and existence. Both thinkers highlight the process of becoming the emergence of the self ("I") in, with, and through others.

In the subsequent section, I will further explore the perspectives of Bakhtin and Vygotskii, illustrating their interconnections and elucidating how they inform our educational practices and enhance our understanding of what it means to become agentic human beings.

Bakhtinian Dialogue and Vygotskian Dialectic in Education

Both Vygotskii and Bakhtin, as stated by Smolka et al. (1995), share the perspective that human consciousness originates from social communication and undergoes development through internalization. Consciousness is socially and historically constructed; thus, it is the highest form of knowing and learning that emerges through reflection and refraction (Sullivan, 2010). For Vygotskii, consciousness emerges in and through dialectical ways of knowing, while for Bakhtin, it arises in and through dialogue (Sullivan, 2010). However, their divergence lies in their interpretations of dialogism. Vygotskii adopts a dialectical methodology in conceiving phenomena, seeking unification, systematization, and synthesis of multiple voices and consciousnesses. He envisions a rational dialogue leading to a unified view of truth, emphasizing the attainability of general knowledge and universal truth through negotiations and challenges (White, 2014).

In contrast, Bakhtin introduces polyphonic dialogism, asserting the unfinalizable nature of dialogue. Grounded in his observation of Dostoevsky's polyphonic novels, Bakhtin sees human consciousness as continuously evolving, contesting all forms of knowledge and truth without converging on a unified perspective. For Bakhtin, the emphasis is on the perpetual contestation of diverse truths rather than their attainment (White, 2014). However, both scholars emphasize the role of language, dialogue, and interaction for developing self, theoretical or scientific thinking, and transformation of human beings.

Dafermos (2018) notes that dialectically oriented dialogism can be a potent tool for advancing development, particularly in the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), where higher-level understanding emerges through collective efforts and negotiations. However, criticisms of Vygotskii emerge, with some scholars arguing that his approach may be adult-centric or ethnocentric due to the unequal status between participants (Matusov, 2011).

Wertsch (1985) points out Vygotskii's focus on individual consciousness at the ontogenetic level, whereas Bakhtin directs attention to the interrelationships among multiple consciousnesses and their sociocultural contexts. This distinction reflects their divergent approaches, with Vygotskii centered on individual cognitive development and Bakhtin exploring the complex interplays of consciousness within broader sociocultural dynamics.

Furthermore, Bakhtin delves into the concept of answerability, emphasizing the responsibility individuals bear in relation to others and to the broader world. Both Bakhtin and Vygotskii posit that human existence in the world is not preordained but necessitates individuals to actively shape their place by taking responsible actions in their interactions with fellow humans and the environment. According to Clark and Holquist (1984), every uttered word not only responds to a past word but also anticipates a future one. The unfinalizable nature of dialogue, as they point out, underscores human potential by representing an ongoing exchange between what already exists (the given) and what is yet to be created (the future).

Nevertheless, as noted by Dafermos (2018), Bakhtin's interpretation of dialectics as dialogism is just one perspective among many. An alternative view sees dialogism as an essential mode of thinking rooted in the fundamental connections between individuals or voices. In this interpretation, the truth or knowledge emerging from dialectical thinking is intricately tied to dialogism, emphasizing the collective and negotiated nature of the process. Different interpretations of dialectics, as suggested by Dafermos, open avenues for diverse perspectives on the interplay between dialogism and the construction of knowledge.

However, Matusov's (2011) comparative analysis of Vygotskii's and Bakhtin's approaches to consciousness offers a thought-provoking perspective that challenges the traditional understanding of these two influential figures in Western Cultural Psychology. Matusov argues that Vygotskii and Bakhtin, rather than espousing similar ideas, actually put forth contrasting conceptions of subjectivity. While both authors posit that individual consciousness is a social product, they do so through different theoretical frameworks. According to Matusov, Vygotskii's approach is characterized by its diachronic, monologic, and activity-based nature, emphasizing the developmental aspect of consciousness and the internalization of social influences as individuals mature. In contrast, Bakhtin's perspective is described as synchronic, dialogic, and discourse-based, highlighting the ongoing interplay of external voices in shaping an individual's consciousness across the lifespan. Matusov's analysis raises important implications for education and pedagogy. He suggests that Vygotskii's view, with its emphasis on the instrumental role of sociality in consciousness, may risk treating children as passive recipients of knowledge rather than active, conscious beings with their own rights and agency. In contrast, Bakhtin's ontological view of consciousness as inherently pluralistic aligns with a pedagogical approach that values and promotes the diverse voices and perspectives of children. Matusov further contends that Vygotskii's approach could be seen as limiting and potentially dehumanizing from Bakhtin's perspective, while Bakhtin's dialogic approach may be viewed as overlooking the developmental aspect of individual consciousness. Ultimately, Matusov concludes that the conceptualizations of Vygotskii and Bakhtin are not only distinct but also irreconcilable.

However, as claimed by Voloshinov (1986, p. 11), for Bakhtin, "consciousness becomes consciousness ... only in the process of social interaction. Individual consciousness is ... [a]

tenant lodging in the social edifice of ideological signs” (cited in Rommetveit, 2014, p. 41). For Vygotkii, the “social dimension of consciousness is primary in time and in fact. The individual dimension is derivative and secondary” (Vygotkii, 1979, p. 30, cited in Rommetveit, 2014, p. 41). Vygotkii viewed the relationship between thought and speech as dialectical, with inner speech emerging from the internalization of social dialogue or speech (Vygotkii, 2012). Vygotkii proposed that egocentric speech “turns into” inner speech rather than fading away, demonstrating a dialectical transformation. These statements allude to the possibilities of compatibility, as both Bakhtin and Vygotkii recognize the role of social interaction in developing consciousness. Both thinkers recognize the importance of social interaction and communication in cognitive processes. They view dialogue as a crucial mechanism for the development of thought and consciousness.

Vygotkii and Bakhtin’s approaches, despite their differences, complement each other in various ways (Cornejo, 2012). While Vygotkii’s model is influenced by Hegel’s universalist perspective and highlights the interplay between thinking and speaking, Bakhtin’s approach is fundamentally dialogical. Some scholars argue that recognizing the fundamental similarities between Vygotkii and the Bakhtin circle could have significant implications for educational research, learning, cognition, and development. Despite their differing conceptualizations, both Vygotkii and Bakhtin share beliefs regarding the importance of voice and selfhood in consciousness. This mutual emphasis on certain aspects of human development and cognition allows for a complementary understanding when considering their theories together. Vygotkii’s focus on the role of language and culture in cognitive development can be enriched by Bakhtin’s emphasis on dialogue and the social nature of language. Similarly, Bakhtin’s ideas about the polyphonic nature of language and the dynamic interplay of voices can provide valuable insights into Vygotkii’s concept of the zone of proximal development. By integrating these perspectives, researchers and educators can gain a more comprehensive understanding of how language, culture, and social interaction shape cognitive processes and learning experiences. This integrated approach has the potential to inform educational practices that are more attuned to the diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds of learners, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness of instruction and promoting equitable educational opportunities for all students.

In my opinion, Vygotkii’s conceptualization of consciousness is rooted in psychology, underscoring the social dimension of development and the significant role of the *cultural-historical unfolding* of knowledge in its formation. Conversely, Bakhtin’s perspective adopts a linguistic approach, accentuating the dialogical nature of consciousness as shaped by social interactions and communicative exchanges. While Vygotkii prioritizes the interplay between knowledge acquisition and social interactions as pivotal in molding consciousness, Bakhtin’s framework centers on the dynamic and interactive aspects of consciousness, where individuals actively participate in dialogue to construct their understanding of the world. These contrasting perspectives reflect distinct philosophical orientations towards the genesis and evolution of agentive becoming and human consciousness. It is noteworthy that psychology devoid of language and language bereft of psychology are inconceivable, as cognitive development relies on the social and communicative functions of speech, and language itself is shaped by individual thought processes. Together, their theories reveal that speech serves not only as a tool for individual cognition but also as a medium for collective meaning-making, enriching learning in both personal and social dimensions. Therefore, Vygotkii considers speech as one of the higher

psychological functions and resources for recreating and restructuring human consciousness (Veresov, 2021), while Bakhtin may consider critical dialogue as a source of authorial agency and consciousness. Critical dialogue is inherently dialectical, as it involves problem identification, problem-solving, and problem-posing (Freire, 1974).

By synthesizing the perspectives of Vygotskii and Bakhtin, one can discern a shared focus on the profound interconnection between psychology and language in the formation of human consciousness. Both theoretical frameworks underscore the dual functions of speech: as a cognitive resource, and as a social conduit. As a cognitive resource, speech empowers individuals to internalize and organize their thoughts, thereby facilitating personal understanding and fostering intellectual growth. Concurrently, as a social conduit, it enables interaction, dialogue, and the co-construction of meaning, thus enhancing collective meaning-making processes. This dynamic interplay between individual cognition and social interaction enriches both personal development and communal learning experiences, illustrating the inseparability of the psychological and linguistic dimensions in human learning, intellectual development, and agentive becoming.

However, a significant question arises regarding dialogue and dialectic in the era of generative AI tools, which facilitate continuous dialogue and interaction as long as we have access to effective electronic communication systems. These AI tools allow for inquiries and discussions on a wide range of topics and issues. They often appear omniscient, capable of responding to any query, and we can engage with them in infinite dialogue and dialectic, although the accuracy of their answers may be questionable. Ironically, AI tools do not comprehend words or sentences in the same manner that humans do; nevertheless, they possess the ability to generate responses and sometimes produce complex and intriguing ideas. Thus, what kind of dialogue and dialectic can we establish (if we can) with AI tools such as ChatGPT? Is it possible to engage in a genuine dialogue with them? Furthermore, can we engage dialectically with these systems? What implications might interactions with artificial tools hold for education, as well as for our learning and intellectual development? This following section explores and discusses the onto-epistemological implications of these tools within the context of higher education.

Artificial Intelligence and the Nature of Dialogue and Dialectic

Hegel's concept of dialectical logic characterizes systems by their components and by the nature of the connections between them. In his work "Phenomenology of Spirit" (Hegel, 2018), Hegel distinguishes between mechanical systems and organic (or living) systems, each exhibiting distinct characteristics. In mechanical systems, all components exist simultaneously and are connected externally, interacting in fixed, causal manners. Conversely, organic systems are dynamic; their components undergo development, growth, and differentiation over time. In this paradigm, the entire system generates its components, which Hegel refers to as "organs of the system," and these components are interrelated through the holistic functioning of the system. For instance, Veresov (2021) contrasts a car engine, where all components interact mechanically, with a tree, which organically grows branches that sprout smaller branches over time. This distinction underscores the shift from rigid, external causality in mechanical systems to reciprocal, purposive unity in organic systems.

Hegel's mechanical dialectic pertains to inorganic, external processes, governed by contingent causality and devoid of internal purpose. Relationships within such systems are defined by external interactions, as exemplified by the functioning of a machine. In contrast, the organic dialectic introduces self-determination and internal unity, wherein contradictions within the system propel its development. Living systems exemplify this, as the interdependence between parts and the whole engenders a dynamic, evolving unity. This dialectical progression—from mechanical to organic—reflects Hegel's broader philosophical framework, culminating in the self-realization of spirit (*Geist*). Within this context, spirit represents the ultimate stage of development, in which systems achieve freedom and self-consciousness through internal contradictions and holistic unity.

When metaphorically applying Hegel's framework to AI systems, one might contend that AI resembles a mechanical system. Essential infrastructures—such as electricity, internet connectivity, and devices like smartphones or computers—must be present for AI to operate effectively. These infrastructures interact in fixed, external ways, analogous to the components of a machine. Furthermore, enhancements in speed, computational power, and data quality augment the efficacy of AI communication, underscoring the mechanical nature of its evolution. Unlike organic systems, AI systems lack inherent self-determination or internal unity; their development is contingent upon external forces and infrastructures.

Hegel's dialectical logic, whether applied to natural or technological systems, emphasizes the dynamic interplay between parts and wholes. While mechanical systems demonstrate foundational yet static interrelations, organic systems represent a higher stage of complexity, characterized by internal purpose and holistic development. This distinction not only provides a framework for understanding living systems and human consciousness, but also offers insights into the limitations of contemporary technological systems such as AI, which remain bound by external dependencies and mechanical causality.

Consequently, AI systems are best understood through the lens of Hegel's mechanical dialectic, as their operation depends significantly on external infrastructures and fixed, contingent relationships. These systems lack the self-determination and internal unity characteristic of organic dialectics, instead relying on human actors to design, train, and refine them. The quality of AI output is directly correlated with the knowledge and intelligence of human developers, as well as the data and algorithms they employ. Human actors provide the foundational inputs—ranging from computational frameworks to ethical considerations—upon which AI systems operate. This dependency reinforces the mechanical nature of AI systems, where progress and efficiency are externally imposed rather than internally driven. Consequently, the potential of AI is constrained by the intelligence and expertise of its creators, underscoring its status as a contingent, mechanical construct within the broader dialectical framework.

Thus, ontologically, understanding AI systems through Hegel's mechanical dialectic suggests that these systems exist as external, contingent entities, lacking intrinsic purpose or self-determination. AI systems do not possess an independent self and agency; they function only within a network of human-constructed infrastructures, such as electricity, internet connectivity, and computational resources. Their "being" is defined entirely by their relationships with external factors and their capacity to perform tasks dictated by human actors. Ontologically, this

positions AI as a tool—a highly complex and efficient one—but not as a self-contained entity capable of evolving or self-realizing in the way organic systems can. The existence and extinction of AI systems are socio-political decisions, shaped by human priorities and governance, rather than natural processes.

In Martin Buber's (1944) dialogic philosophy, there are three main types of relationships that shape human interactions: the *I-It* relationship, the *I-Thou* relationship, and the *I-You* relationship. The *I-It* relationship is defined by one party treating the other as an object or a tool, rather than as a subject with its own consciousness and internal life. This relationship is utilitarian and functional, with the "It" being something to be used, manipulated, or observed, rather than engaged with. The *I-Thou* relationship, in contrast, is a reciprocal and transformative exchange in which both parties recognize each other as subjects with unique internal lives. There is a mutual, subjective engagement, and the interaction is marked by a deep, meaningful connection that goes beyond mere utility. The *I-You* relationship lies somewhere in between, involving mutual recognition of the other as a human being, but without the same level of depth or transformation as is seen in the *I-Thou* relationship.

When comparing AI dialogue to Buber's *I-It* relationship, we see that AI fits squarely into this category. In interactions with AI, the human user treats the AI as a tool or instrument, rather than as a subject. AI is programmed to respond to input data based on pre-set algorithms, but it does not possess subjectivity, self-awareness, or an internal life. The interaction is one-sided and functional, with no mutual recognition or reciprocal engagement. AI is not a participant in the dialogue, but merely an object that provides responses according to its programming. This interaction is not transformative or meaningful in the way Buber's *I-Thou* relationship is; the AI remains a mechanical entity, devoid of consciousness, that responds mechanically to inputs without understanding or adapting to the deeper meaning or emotional dynamics of the conversation.

Recent studies (Matusov et al., 2024) suggest that while AI lacks a dialogical self, it may possess a discursive self (referring to Hermans, 2022). A dialogical self is characterized by personal "I-positions" that engage in subjective, multivocal, and context-sensitive interactions, rooted in identity, selfhood, and consciousness. In contrast, a discursive self refers to impersonal "objectified it-positions," devoid of personal subjectivity and self-reflection. These "it-positions" represent external influences on the self, such as societal norms, institutional discourses, or predefined roles, rather than personal, dialogical engagement. However, the question of whether AI tools possess any form of self remains debatable, as the concept of self is often considered exclusive to human beings. AI might be more accurately described as a discursive tool that responds to inquiries and prompts. It does not possess any self or subjectivity, which is manifest in onto-epistemological perspectiveness and 'mineness' of experiences (Northoff & Gouveia, 2024). This raises questions that warrant broader philosophical discussion and debate.

Nonetheless, AI appears to embody aspects of *demosophia*, a philosophical concept coined by Christakis (2014), which combines the Greek words *demos* (the people) and *sophia* (wisdom), meaning "*the wisdom of the people.*" This concept is rooted in democratic ideals of inclusivity, dialogue, and collaboration, where collective input from diverse individuals contributes to more

informed, equitable, and sustainable solutions to societal challenges. AI systems can present the idea of collective wisdom by synthesizing shared knowledge, experiences, and facts from diverse digital landscapes. Additionally, the multimodal capabilities of AI enable dialogue with users across various contexts, including those with physical impairments. Its dialogic nature—marked by iterative exchanges—can foster collective creativity and decision-making processes that transcend geographical, cultural, and disciplinary boundaries.

Critically, AI systems reflect the political power structures that determine how ideas are organized, structured, and disseminated. From this perspective, AI can perpetuate systemic biases, leading, as Noble (2018) describes it, to an “*algorithm of oppression*.” AI does not operate in isolation; its training datasets are rooted in social contexts rife with power imbalances and historical injustices. The historical misuse of science to categorize, rank, and exclude individuals based on arbitrary traits echoes in modern AI systems. These systems risk normalizing exclusionary practices by propagating knowledge that often mirrors the perspectives of dominant groups, marginalizing or distorting the voices of minority communities. For instance, algorithms trained on biased datasets can reinforce stereotypes, exclude underrepresented narratives, and reproduce inequities in access to resources. Research has shown that AI detectors may flag non-native English speakers’ writings as AI-generated (Liang et al., 2023), raising concerns about the perpetuation of prejudices against certain communities. This phenomenon underscores how AI, while promising inclusivity, can inadvertently reinforce existing hierarchies and systemic inequities.

Engaging in dialogue with AI systems embedded within superstructures of fixed ideologies presents complex risks that can undermine social understanding and cohesion. These systems are often shaped by the dominant narratives and epistemologies present in their training data, which may unintentionally prioritize mainstream or widely accepted perspectives while marginalizing alternative or critical viewpoints. Consequently, they risk reinforcing homogeneous ways of understanding social issues, thereby limiting the scope of inquiry and suppressing the plurality of voices essential for a well-rounded discourse. This dynamic fosters echo chambering (Sharma et al., 2024), wherein users are continually exposed to ideas that align with their existing beliefs, and epistemic bubbles. Over time, such feedback loops can amplify biases and cultivate an environment where extreme positions are normalized, diminishing the space for critical engagement and nuanced dialogue. As Nguyen (2020) argues, echo chambers are more deliberate and insidious structures wherein dissenting perspectives are actively discredited and excluded. Within echo chambers, members are conditioned to systematically distrust external sources, leading to a self-reinforcing cycle that solidifies existing beliefs and entrenches biases. Thus, breaking out of an echo chamber frequently necessitates a profound and intentional re-evaluation of deeply held beliefs, a process sometimes described as “radical rebooting.” Epistemic bubbles as socio-techno social structures in which certain voices or viewpoints are unintentionally excluded, often as a result of the incidental dynamics of social networks or algorithms, thereby creating an incomplete epistemic landscape (Nguyen, 2020), may be addressed easily by addressing algorithmic issues.

Furthermore, the algorithmic tendency to curate information based on user behavior can exacerbate ideological divides, as individuals are increasingly unlikely to encounter perspectives that challenge or broaden their understanding. This erosion of pluralistic dialogue not only

perpetuates misunderstandings but also intensifies social fissures, increasing the risk of hostility between groups with divergent viewpoints. Marginalized communities, whose perspectives may already be underrepresented in mainstream narratives, are particularly susceptible to being further sidelined in AI-mediated interactions. This can reinforce feelings of exclusion and alienation, fueling discontent and polarization.

To conclude, echo chambers and epistemic bubbles represent significant threats to the integrity of ethical, fair, just, and inclusive dialogue and dialectic. By selectively filtering or actively discrediting diverse perspectives, these phenomena create environments in which individuals are insulated from opposing viewpoints and critical engagement. In epistemic bubbles, the unintentional exclusion of relevant voices limits exposure to the plurality of ideas necessary for fair and balanced discourse. Echo chambers exacerbate this issue by fostering systematic distrust of external perspectives, actively undermining the legitimacy of alternative viewpoints. This dynamic not only distorts the flow of information, but also entrenches biases, perpetuates misinformation, and reinforces ideological divides.

The implications for dialogue and dialectic are profound. In ethical and inclusive exchanges, all participants must have equitable opportunities to share and critically evaluate ideas. However, echo chambers erode this foundation by promoting homogeneity and suppressing dissent. This undermines fairness, as certain voices are delegitimized or excluded, as may be justice, as marginalized perspectives are systematically silenced. Without genuine engagement across diverse viewpoints, the dialectic process of synthesizing new understandings through critical examination becomes impossible. Instead, the cycle of self-reinforcement within these structures perpetuates polarization and hostility, further fracturing societal cohesion.

To counteract these challenges, it is important to dismantle the conditions that sustain echo chambers and epistemic bubbles. This includes fostering pluralistic dialogue by promoting diverse, credible perspectives and developing educational initiatives that equip individuals with critical media literacy skills. Additionally, creating spaces for equitable participation and deliberation can help rebuild trust and bridge divides. By addressing these epistemic challenges, society can work towards a model of dialogue and dialectic that upholds the principles of ethics, fairness, justice, and inclusivity, which are essential for navigating the complexities of a pluralistic and interconnected world.

Conclusion

Dialogue and dialectic are inherently interdependent, and exploring this symbiotic relationship offers transformative potential for advancing intellectual development in higher education. As foundational processes of human intellectual becoming, dialogue and dialectic shape the way we engage with the world, with others, and with ourselves. Whether addressing personal or professional concerns, we initiate dialogue with those closest to us. In this way, every attempt to develop a shared understanding of issues, events, and concerns is dialectical in nature. This understanding is never final or absolute; it is always provisional, subject to modification as new information emerges, thus opening avenues for further dialogue. Meaning making is, therefore, an ongoing, multi-voiced process, a series of dialectical moments where ideas and perspectives are organized, scrutinized, and synthesized. This unfinalizable process generates continuous

dialogue, leading to an evolving consciousness and an ever-developing mechanism of intellectual advancement.

Both dialogue and dialectic are aimed at fostering higher levels of human thinking and intellectual maturity. However, the true potential of higher education lies in exploring and nurturing their symbiotic relationship. This creates spaces and tools for diverse, dynamic meaning-making activities, particularly in the context of democratic development and academic freedom. A healthy symbiosis between dialogue and dialectic provides the necessary conditions for impartial and evidence-based debate on any idea, issue, or concern. However, this openness can be threatened by political or ideological forces, as superstructures may view such organic discussion as uncomfortable or destabilizing.

Likewise, AI systems have the potential to serve as tools that extend the spaces and tools of dialogue and dialectic. By assisting with the exploration, organization, and structuring of ideas, AI can expand the possibilities for discourse and inquiry. However, AI cannot truly replicate the essence of human dialogue and dialectic, which is grounded in complex socio-cultural and psychological processes. These processes are integral to constructing selfhood, agency, and personhood, all of which are unique to human interaction. AI, lacking consciousness and emotional depth, cannot engage in the relational, social, and collaborative nature of human learning. While AI-generated knowledge can be valuable when prompted appropriately, it risks reinforcing the passive, one-way model of education where knowledge is received rather than actively constructed. Additionally, AI tools could facilitate unethical academic practices such as cheating, plagiarism, and deepfakes, undermining the epistemological integrity of education.

Given these risks, it is crucial to reframe teaching and learning practices to ensure that AI supports, rather than replaces, the dynamic, critical, and collaborative processes of human learning. Higher education institutions must adopt problem-based, collaborative approaches that leverage AI's capabilities in areas where it excels while preserving the irreplaceable human aspects of education. As AI increasingly performs tasks such as creating lesson plans or generating assignments, there is a need to rethink traditional pedagogical models. This redesign must involve collective dialogue and dialectic between educators, AI developers, and learners to ensure that AI is used ethically and effectively in education. Embracing this paradigm shift will enable institutions to adapt to the evolving educational landscape, fostering a more authentic, ethical, and intellectually enriching environment for all.

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Unfazed by the More-Than-Human Face: Renegotiating Progress through Ethical Address

Erica Hagström

In this paper, I explore relationships between the human and the more-than-human, and claim that this relationship concerns education in two ways. One way is through the educational possibilities raised by this relationship, and the other is through the ways this relationship will affect the welfare of future generations. To make my claims, I examine and concretize relationships between the human and the more-than-human through arts-based research approach developed through creative writing, via a poem and two pieces of fiction. For clarity, these passages are italicized.

In earlier work, I questioned the human-centeredness of educational becoming. I started with the question posed by Biesta (2014), who asked what if it would mean if something “radically different might break through” (p. 49). I chose to connect this question to human relationships with animals, and more specifically, to a relationship with a horse (Hagström, 2016, 2018). In this study, I made a link between the works of Biesta (2015a) and work by Irigaray and Green (2008), a link which I now wish to deepen. Biesta (2015a) emphasized the need to open up to other existential possibilities of ways of being in and with the world. These existential possibilities expose the ways in which we humans must let the world encounter and address us rather than having us see it as an object to be understood. According to Irigaray and Green (2008), education ought to teach how to respect the world and contemplate it. Instead, it has too often been the case that education in Western culture has taught us how to grasp and master the world, according to Irigaray and Green (2008).

While I previously focused on the link between these studies in relation to animals, I now want to expand this idea by having it address the more-than-human. Continuing from the link between the ethical implications for education with regard to respecting it and contemplating it that Irigaray raises and Biesta’s (2015a) thoughts on other existential possibilities, I now connect this link to Biesta’s (2015b) work on whether what we desire in education is, in reality, desirable. Brought together, these arguments invite us to explore and discuss ethics in education in times of transformation such as the current one. I investigate this invitation during a fictional walk in the forest, contemplating whether the more-than-human face can exist, and if it does, how it would appear.

Is it putting my feet down, one after the other, on a bit of mud and grass sticking up in the midst of the slippery ice and creating a little safe spot of grip to keep me going? The melting ice makes it difficult for a two-legged with no grips to get through. Is it the water crossing the path making the ground muddy? Water is rippling across the path, down the slope and then under the snow again, making a trickling sound barely

recognizable under the strong wind. Is it the one bare grey juniper sticking out in the middle of a stand of junipers? Is it the interruption of my steps and train of thought? When and how does a more-than-human face appear? How do they have to merge and crystallize for me to notice? Does it help to lend more-than-human a face? Or does it help more to lend the more-than-human a voice or a sound?

Education Imbued with Imaginaries of Anthropocentrism

Imaginaries of anthropocentrism affect multiple forms of living in ways that might not be desirable, either for themselves or for future generations (in which human generations are included). Building on my earlier research (Hagström, 2016, 2018), I maintain that the question stretches into ecological and ethical dimensions, too. In line with the ecofeminists, as are Adams and Gruen (2014), I argue that it is crucial to simultaneously address questions about ecological, animalist, and feminist issues. Intersectional theorization as a way forward is also highlighted by Calarco (2015).

I call into question how these educational imaginaries, rooted in the idea of human exceptionalism, affect what, whose, or how multiple forms of living (including the human) count as human or non-human. Further, I ask, how do these educational imaginaries affect what, whose, or how multiple forms of living (including that of humans) count as “we,” and what, whose, or how these multiple forms of living (including human living) count in regard to their being ethically taken into consideration. Education and ethics cannot be separated.

The word “unfazed” was chosen for this essay even though, and because, it sounds similar to “face.” It might be heard as *unfaced* with its ‘c’ (unvoiced sibilant /s/) softened to a voiced ‘z,’ and I believe that this thought regarding it is coherent and makes sense in this context, too. But I have chosen “unfazed” with a ‘zed’ because of its meaning of being untouched, unmoved, unruffled, or unworried by the encounter with a more-than-human face.

I argue that because of the anthropocentric imaginaries with which education is imbued, the world is shut out, and multiple forms of living are alienated. Through landslides, wildfires, and storms, the world shouts at us. But as the world is faceless and voiceless, and since we seem to have lost our senses and our sensibility, there are few accessible ways in which it can address us. We remain unfazed by the more-than-human face.

Ethics and Education with and without Faces

In my earlier work (Hagström, 2018), I explored approaches to openness as regards being addressed by the more-than-human. Using the animal ethics of Calarco (2008), I have built on Lévinas’s idea of the face of the Other. I have linked the idea of “being faced by animals” to the horse’s face, which I then extended to the horse’s questioning corporeality (Hagström, 2018). Here, I am pushing this thought of ethical address forward by exploring possibilities for being addressed by multiple forms of living beings.

However, Calarco (2008) presents a perspective in which the ethical address can only appear as a human or animal face, which he presents as “being faced by animals” (p. 63). He argues that animal ethics and environmental ethics are distinct, but complementary. In Calarco’s (2008)

critique, I admit, there are connections with acknowledged problems of environmental thought, in which “environment” becomes a concept that gets generalized too easily, at least with regard to any specific animal. In part, I adhere to this critique because the phenomenon of the more-than-human is multiple in its forms of living. But it hasn’t always had a recognizable face in the world as humans know it. Methodologically, I approach the risk of being “too general,” drawing on Haraway (2008), by emphasizing relations, spaces, and encounters in their specificities.

Why, then, cling to the notion of the face? It is because the notion of the face is connected to the notion of ethical address. It is theoretically embedded into ethics through the work of Lévinas and, further, connected to education through the work of Biesta that builds on Lévinas’s work. Also, building on Lévinas’s work, the face is connected to animal studies through the work of Calarco and others. The question is, without a face, how might it be possible to be addressed by the more-than-human?

Haraway (2008) suggests a priority of vision and the face-to-face when describing relations between humans and animals, specifically in the setting of dogs and agility. Faces may question and address. With horses, there are many possible ways for the face-to-face to occur, but not when riding. And in any relationship with other animals, corporeality is present. As the face asks questions, so may corporeality, as I have argued elsewhere (Hagström, 2018). What the more-than-human has in common with the human is not faces or bodies, but living. And in this living, we are all interdependently connected. This section is followed by a poem:

Seeing an elk seeing me

*fast walk in the forest before dinner
twigs break somewhere
I look around
my feet keep walking on the path*

*my sight is muddled by the dusk
the high grass is yellowish grey
the sky is grey, the fir trees are black
the grey cliffs are high*

*still as the cliff, still as the sky and the fir trees
an elk is seeing me, I stop and*

*start fiddling with the high grass
hoping the elk stays on for a bit*

*I move around a little, glancing towards the elk
who is still seeing me*

*the yellowish grey grass is high
the sky is grey, the fir trees are black
the high cliffs are grey*

*the elk turns around
climbs up the cliff, disappears in the woods*

my sight is muddled by the dusk

On the More-Than-Human

Furry and four-legged, elks bear similarities to horses. This may imply that they would emerge more prominently for me in a text, given the context of my previous research. Also, the eyes, nostrils and mouth on an elk's head form a recognizable face. But the elk's appearing and disappearing in this piece points to a merging of life and living in various forms, such as the fir trees, the grass, and the "I."

From this point on, I want to highlight the more-than-human, and to do so, I will start out with Haraway (2008). Haraway (2008, p. 341) acknowledges the adoption of the locution "more-than-human" from van Dooren's work *Seeding Property: Nature, Human/Plant Relations and the Production of Wealth* (2007). In Haraway's work, the notion comes into play in an aside during the sharing of stories about dog breeding:

Discovery of gold radically and permanently changed the food economy, species assemblages, politics, human and *more-than-human* [emphasis added] demographics, and natural social ecology of California and other parts of the North American West. (Haraway, 2008, p. 101)

Haraway (2008) maintains that the stories she presents regarding dogs need to be told in order to tease out the "personal and collective response required now, not centuries ago" (p. 97). According to Haraway (2008), "Companion species cannot afford evolutionary, personal or historical amnesia" (p. 98).

I follow the track from Haraway's use of "more-than-human" via van Dooren's (2007) work, which links to Curry (2008). I'll start out with the work of Curry, then return to van Doreen.

Curry (2008) maintains that "an inclusive ecocentrism is impossible to envisage without recognizing and appreciating our immersion in this vast and intricate discursivity, the more-than-(but including)-human" (p. 59). He maintains that this thought builds upon Gregory Bateson's work on how mind and nature form a "necessary unity." Also, Curry (2008) brings forth the idea that this concept has been furthered in ecological-phenomenological terms by Abram and in ecofeminist terms by Plumwood. Curry (2008) argues for a relational pluralism that is necessarily ecocentric. He contrasts ecocentrism with anthropocentrism, stating that ecocentrism "locates value and/or agency within nature as such, including (but not limited to) humanity: what David Abram aptly calls a 'more-than-human world'" (p. 54). Curry (2008) continues, "As part of such a project, right thinking can help to clear a space for a different mode which is better able to apprehend and appreciate the intrinsic value of more-than-human nature, or rather wildness (including human)" (p. 64).

The formulation of the more-than-(but including)-human (Curry 2008, p. 59) is what van Dooren (2009) built upon when further developing his work on banking seeds and the conservation of agricultural diversity, in which he concluded, “banking well is about banking in and with more-than-human communities. It is about imagining and conserving biosocial natures through a sharing of diversities” (p. 390). In van Dooren’s work, the “more-than-human” becomes important because “it describes communities and places in which human projects and desires are not completely dominant” (2009, p. 375). Further, according to van Dooren (2009), “These are multi-species communities in which a space is held open for other organisms to live and possibly even flourish” (p. 375). This offers us a view where the *more-than-human* embraces humans, but where there are more beings than just humans. I want to emphasize the connection of these insights to education through the care for future generations of more-than-(but including)-human life through the banking of seeds and the subsequent conservation of agricultural diversity.

Van Dooren (2009) also draws from the work of Plumwood in order to criticize the instrumentalization of non-humans, in which “one ... attaches no real or essential value to their living for their own sake, or to the broader relationships that comprise agricultural environments” (p. 380). This brings forth a critique of a “reductionist and economically convenient understanding of ‘nature’” (van Dooren, 2009).

Through elks, dog breeding, and seeds, I have highlighted the notion of the more-than-human. In the following section, I’ll focus on the connection with the face.

Dressing up the More-Than-Human with a Face

Imaginarities of anthropocentrism show themselves through the desire of humans to recognize and prioritize faces. But then again, not each and every human face is equally recognized and prioritized.

The more-than-human might or might not present a face. This leads to the question of whether the more-than-human needs to be lent a face or dressed up with a face to be rendered visible.

One example is the Swedish fictional figure *Skogsmulle*, created in the 1950s by the Swedish non-profit NGO *Swedish Outdoor Association* (Friluftsförbundet, 2024). This organization disseminates knowledge on *The Right of Public Access*, a right protecting public access to nature, recognized in the Swedish constitution. *Skogsmulle* is a character used in teaching materials meant to help children learn about nature. This figure, two-legged, with arms, face, and a tail, and with a specific greeting phrase, is widely known in the Swedish context and used in formal and informal outdoor education. (This name also carries an inferred connotation signifying people who love and care for the forest, sometimes in a derogatory sense.)

What I wish to highlight here by paying attention to *Skogsmulle* is the apparent need and desire to present a human face with two eyes above a nose in order to be addressed and to be able to respond to the address. Maybe this manner of conjuring a face, calling out “*Kollikok!*” from the forest, is helpful for humans in being able to extend concerns about the other. Sometimes, dressing up the more-than-human with a face may be helpful, although there is a deep risk of erasing the specificity of how the more-than-human, with or without a face, might exist. Further,

it is not at all helpful when humans mix up their own needs, wishes, and desires with those of the other, which has its own needs, wishes, and desires.

I will now leave the two eyes above a nose behind, and instead of a *face*, I will pay attention to *someplace*, or more specifically, to how the being addressed by the more-than-human in its specificities may break through. The face, or rather place, has no nose here, but the ethics of the face remains in terms of its being questioned through the address by the more-than-human. This section is followed by a piece of fiction.

Someplace

I leave the forest lane, which is wet and muddy due to wheel tracks, and I turn in on a dry and very small track. Here, it's not a forest, really, but rather a fir tree farm. This part of the woods consists of narrow and strict rows of fir trees, where the sun can't reach to the lower branches. They're all brown, edgy and give me scratches.

For me, this is the only way possible to enter this impervious part of the woods. As I follow this straight line, other small paths emerge in various directions. One of them is spacious enough to let me come through. I climb over a fallen fir tree. I raise my eyes, and there's light between the dead branches. A clearing opens up, and I enter.

The sunshine is reflected on the grey granite and makes the high yellow grass translucent. Big stones are toppling over and around each other. I'm enclosed by high fir trees.

From here, I can see how the upper branches facing the sun are green. I turn around to look towards the sun. Little gnats twirl around in the air. I stand still, and I feel that this is someplace. How come this isn't just somewhere, but someplace?

Days pass. I want to find that someplace again. This time, I approach the entrance in the narrow fir tree rows from the opposite direction, reminding myself that the hunting tower should be opposite the track's entrance and the small meadow should be only a short distance away. At this point, I find a narrow line and start to follow it.

But where are the paths trodden by deer and martens, showing ways other than the human-made mechanical track, yet too impenetrable for me to follow? That fallen fir tree that stopped me in my tracks, with the green color standing out amongst brown branches, where is it?

I see a few stones, but the sunshine isn't reflected on a big piece of granite. Instead, the granite is covered with moss. Disappointment hits me. Am I too eager to find it again, so that it's no longer waiting for me? I enter the clearing. I cross over the moss and turn myself towards the sun. I look in various directions, but it doesn't look the same. I wait.

The sun glitters on a little granite stone. It's formed like the back of a sofa with the soft moss as a seat, inviting me to sit down. I sit and see that there are heathers popping out of the moss.

Willow warblers, wrens and blackbirds all are singing. I hear noises of twigs breaking. I feel the presence of the elks, the deer and the foxes, but I don't see any of them with my eyes.

This isn't somewhere; this is someplace.

After I have left the sunny stone and warm moss sofa and walked a few steps further into the woods, I realize that this wasn't someplace. Now, I see in front of me a big section of granite, scratches from deer in the moss and toppling stones. Also, a bit to the left, a fallen fir tree with a crown of green color stands out amongst the brown branches. My senses reorient my position. If this is someplace, then, what was the other place?

Desirability in and of Education

Grasping and mastering, on the one hand, and respecting and contemplating, on the other hand, intermingle when the addressing breaks through. For Irigaray and Green (2008), respecting and contemplating would be desirable in education.

Further, from the angle of Biesta (2015b), the question is whether what we desire in and from education is, in actuality, desirable. As Biesta (2015b) pointed out, "We want teachers to open up new vistas, new opportunities, and help children and young people to interrogate whether what they say they want or desire is actually what they should desire" (p. 82).

If the emphasis were instead to be put on respecting and contemplating the world rather than on grasping and mastering it, then a renegotiation would be needed, one in which value would not be primarily economical and measured in economic growth. The values in the exploitation of natural resources need to be replaced by the contemplation of what values are desirable. Counting and measuring are all well and very helpful, in many ways. In context, for instance, the measuring of global warmth is crucial for rendering visible the magnitude of the climate crisis.

Put into the context of what is desirable for education in a more-than-human world, a renegotiation of economic growth and of social justice for the currently living and future generations would be needed. I wish to invite all of us to think about how human senses have been distorted in their relationship to anthropocentric imaginaries. I argue that the distortion of human senses has led to a bereavement of sensing when it is addressed by the more-than-human. The grasping and mastering of the world do not intermingle with, but rather fully outweigh, respect for and contemplation of the world.

Renegotiation of Progress

I started from the idea that education is imbued with anthropocentric imaginaries. I continued through with a linking from my previous research (Hagström, 2016, 2018) of Irigaray's (Irigaray & Green, 2008) ethical implications for education to Biesta's (2015a) thoughts on other existential possibilities. I then explored this angle further by connecting it to Biesta's (2015b) questioning of whether what we desire is, in reality, desirable in education. In order to address this last question, I steered the discussion into focusing on progress.

I would argue that within anthropocentric imaginaries, progress gets caught up in becoming focused on the more, the bigger, the stronger, and the faster. One might consider each of these better, but for what or whom? Progress gets distorted and confused with economic growth. Progress, which is central to any relation to education, needs to be renegotiated in order to make it more fully educational.

In relation to this discussion, I have chosen to introduce Nisbet's (1994) work on the history of the idea of progress in relation to Dewey's (1916) article "Progress." The idea of progress is a powerful motivator in Western history, as Nisbet (1994) points out, because the idea brings together the past, the present, and the future. Nisbet (1994) implies that the idea of progress is not just desirable, but also possibly a historical necessity, even something close to a law of nature. Dewey (1916) affirms the idea that humans may wish to believe in this idea of the historical inevitability of progress, saying, "We [have] confused rapidity of change with advance, and we [have taken] certain gains in our own comfort and ease as signs that cosmic forces [are] working inevitably to improve the whole state of human affairs" (p. 312). Here, Dewey invokes cosmic forces, although this passage might be read as having an undertone of a *laissez-faire* attitude in that humans read the signs in ways that are most convenient for them. A main point for Dewey (1916) is that progress is something that should not be taken for granted by humans, but inevitably seems to be taken this way: "Progress is not automatic; it depends upon human intent and aim and upon acceptance of responsibility for its production" (p. 315). What Dewey (1916) brings forth is the concept of responsibility. This is not a given, and I claim that it is at risk of being ignored.

If progress is a dogma that holds Western civilization back, as Nisbet (1994) affirmatively states, then there might be a need to take a closer look at whether this dogma is desirable in and for education in a time of transformation such as we are facing now.

While Dewey (2016) emphasizes the need for intelligence, I think that in combination with intelligence, our senses and sensibility need to be affirmed. To do this, we must constantly renegotiate the anthropocentric imaginaries that dominate the imaginaries of education.

It might be time to return to how the imaginaries of progress play out when joining forces with anthropocentrism, as well as with economization, and what might be lost to progress in relation to education. Humans need to accept responsibility for the production of progress, as Dewey (1916) points out. The connection to responsibility potentially makes an emphasis on progress more educational, I would argue, because it brings forth the connection between ethics and education. Progress without responsibility is not desirable in, of, or for itself, or for education. If progress is pursued without responsibility, it renders visible the ways that these anthropocentric imaginaries affect what, which, whose, and/or how multiple forms of living are

included in what is counted as “we.” This means that it affects what, which, whose, or how multiple forms of living (including human living) are being taken into account ethically. This distinction cuts through living in various contexts, splitting life from death.

Concluding Remarks

In this paper, I explored and discussed relationships between the human and the more-than-human. To do this, I articulated and concretized relationships between the human and the more-than-human through arts-based research in the form of creative writing, incorporating into the study a poem and two pieces of fiction about an elk, walks, and places in the forest. The more-than-human, of course, includes more than elks and forests, but as my methodological promise was to meet the risk of environmental ethics by being too general, drawing on Haraway (2008), I chose to concretize relationships to elks and forests in their specificities through the poem and the pieces of fiction. My intent here was to bring the reader to share these experiences in a concrete way and, further, to explore the themes within the pieces themselves, and continue the discussion on the themes of this paper in relation to the thinkers I have mentioned.

To conclude, I claim, first, that by being miseducated into over-focusing on grasping and mastering the world, human life has been led into being continuously unfazed by the more-than-human face. And second, I claim that there is still hope as regards changing this situation.

I argue that this hope concerns education in two ways. One way is with regard to the educational possibility of being addressed by the more-than-human, and the other way is with regard to the care for future generations.

Regarding the educational possibilities, instead of focusing only on being addressed by the human *face*, I paid attention to *someplace*. The piece of fiction called *Someplace*, as well as the fictional walk and the poem interlinking an elk, trees, grass and the “I,” concern this. Building on Biesta’s (2015a) work on “being addressed or being spoken to by what or who is other” (p. 239), I argue that it is the task of education to form our human senses so that they address the times when multiple forms of living address us. This may break through in the form of a *someplace*, in which I, with the senses and sensibility I have available, may be spoken to both within and beyond human language. If this address were only provided via human faces, then humans would suffer from a deprivation of sense and sensibility. This recognition reconnects us to what was discussed above, namely, who is counted as a “we.” Who, of all living beings, including humans, is being ethically taken into account? This question ultimately creates a division between the currently living and a full consideration of both the living and the dead.

The insight leads to another perspective that concerns education, which involves care for future generations. If progress is pursued within the anthropocentric imaginaries with which education is imbued, without taking responsibility for and/or without paying attention to caring for life, then this approach, too, separates the now-living from the combined world of life and death. It splits human suffering and death right here and now as regards the consequences of the climate crisis, which is creating a level of suffering and death that we keep on giving to future generations.

As a human endeavor, education builds upon hope for future generations. As Dewey (1916) accurately stated more than 100 years ago, raising a perspective I agree with, we have confused rapidity of change with advancement. This confusion is not desirable. We desire progress in terms of rapidity of change rather than paying attention to what kind of progress we should desire.

Humans might come to their senses if they are addressed by the more-than-human. In this confrontation, educational possibilities might arise through a renegotiation of the ways progress might exist. In order to renegotiate progress, it is necessary to loosen the anthropocentric shackles of the imaginaries and the practices of continuous rapid growth and attend instead to our responsibility for the productions of progress. In communities including the more-than-human (van Dooren, 2009, p. 390), or multi-species communities (van Dooren, 2009, p. 375), space for *other* living organisms is held open in order for them to flourish. As Haraway (2008) argues, there is a need for personal and collective response, and companion species cannot afford “evolutionary, personal or historical amnesia” (p. 98). Progress, in its educational sense, embraces an interlinked past, present and future, foregrounding intergenerational relations. Such relations are built upon care and hope for future generations within more-than-human communities.

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